
EXAMINING THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE DIGITAL PLATFORMS ADAPTATION IN THE UK

DBA Cohort 16

MARCH 31, 2022

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ABSTRACT:

Digital Platforms have experienced a significant growth in today's world. This study explores the idea of user's perception of digital platforms and the factors which influence their decision to adopt these platforms, particularly in innovative countries such as United Kingdom. There is still a knowledge gap regarding the way consumers perceive online platforms to conduct business. This affects the development of platform acceptance strategies and profit models implemented by platform owners, who have experienced a rapid decline in circulation revenues due to fierce competition originating from change in user's perceptions of platforms usefulness and value creation.

At the heart of this issue, one challenging area of research and business interest is to identify factors that consumers consider when deciding to adapt one platform. In order to address this, this thesis adopts a primarily positivist philosophy utilising a mixed method approach to address the research question: 'What are the factors that influence consumers' decision of using online platforms in the United Kingdom?' Moreover, the study examines how various attributes add to the perception of usefulness and value creation of such acceptance factors, as well as the degree to which they contribute to the acceptance intent of users for online platforms.

A conceptual model based on the Technology Acceptance Model including a set of external variables comprising system characteristics and individual differences was used to structure these influences and analysed using Structural Equation Modelling. Nine industry experts were used to identify additional influencing factors, a pilot study with business experts were used to verify the basic model and methodology and the model was evaluated using Partial Least Squares in the full-scale main study of 262 respondents.

The results indicate that user's perception indeed play an important role for digital platforms adaptation in the UK, embedded in the application of system characteristics. Five concrete system characteristics — compatibility, later payment, single payment platform, mobility, and convenience — are found to be positively and significantly linked to the perceived usefulness, with the latter two also showing a strong significant effect on perceived value creation. Furthermore, it is found that attitude towards the use of digital platforms has a strong positive relationship with the intention to use those platforms.

The implication of the research outcomes provides strong potential for the practical

proposition of user's perception in the digital platforms industry and identifies future directions for creating appropriate strategies for users' behaviour regarding platforms adaption.

1. CHAPTER 1

1.0. Introduction

Digital platforms are becoming an increasingly important chapter in the business world. The importance of digital platforms can be assessed by the list of most valuable companies in the world, such as Amazon, Facebook, Google, and Alibaba. All these companies are listed as the most valuable companies with surprisingly short histories and all of them are based on a digital platform business model. Digital platforms' importance has transcended into other companies with long histories as well, such as General Electric company which was listed nearly 120 years ago on the stock market is investing heavily on platformaization. Similarly, all the major industries in the world are focused on making digital marketplaces for them to not only thrive in future but to survive.

In contrast to other business models' platforms have to outperform the normal market trend. The global economy is fully dependent on digital platforms, to understand the importance of digital platforms in today's economy one needs to just look at Wall street's list of top ten venture-backed private companies and seven of them are digital platforms such as Uber (\$72 billion), Airbnb (\$31 billion) and WeWork (\$20.2 billion). These companies have one aspect in common and that is to facilitate the transactions between their users, for example, Uber and Lyft connect drivers with passengers, similarly, WeWork and Airbnb connect renters and property owners and other platforms such as Just eat and Meituan-Dianping help restaurants and their consumers to connect and Lufax connect capital providers and capital seekers.

The other good example of Platform importance can be extracted from the EU report (2015) regarding digital platforms which state that the digital platforms accounted for 35% of GDP in the European Union and 59% of GDP in the USA. The report suggests that the platforms will generate 332 billion USD in revenues by 2026 worldwide. These staggering figures shed light on the importance of digital platforms and highlight their advantage over the

conventional business model. The snowballing phenomena of digital platforms usage indicate the need for more research work in this field as it is the necessity of time.

Two-sided and multi-sided platforms are among the most important research subjects these days. The platforms provide gains to different groups of users when they interact via platform. For example, payment systems can be used by employers & employees, hardware devices can be used by game users & game developers, health insurance networks can be used by health insurance providers & subscribers, real estate platforms can be used by real estate buyers & sellers. These examples represent two-sided platforms with two different types of users.

Interacting with each other, users produce network effect. The network effect represents the benefit to each user as a function of the number of existing users on the platform. In the case of a two-sided platform, one can talk about a cross-side network effect. It is a dependency of one type of user on the users of the other type. A real-valued function expressing interest of one type of users in the opposite type of users comes into the dynamical system as an attachment function. Generally speaking, an attachment function is a representation of the users' preferences over some set of goods and services.

In the case of two-sided platforms users are either more or less reluctant to join a platform if the current number of users of their type is very high. This is called same-side network effect. In some two-sided platforms same-side network effect is negative, and proportional to the number of users of this type. For example, real estate buyers prefer platforms with a few buyers to keep prices low. However, some two-sided platforms may have a positive same-side network effect (like in the case of multi-player online games, where players benefit from the presence of other players). One has to bear in mind that intention towards platform adaption may vary depending on the nature of service sought therefore this study assume only the retail platform users (Amazon, Ebay, Uber), where users of both ends benefits from the participation. This study eliminated the users of other platforms which are not relevant to this research, such as banking.

In this research, author utilized new, dynamical systems, approach. It allows one to observe benefits from the platform owner point of view and to see the tendency of the users to adapt the platform.

Thus, the purpose of this research is to study how the users from each side of the platform perceived the usefulness and value creation of the platform, and to understand what critical factors impact on the decision of users is the most beneficial for platform owners.

By keeping in mind, the importance and relevance of digital platforms in this era, this research tries to capture this phenomenon from the user's point of view. This research investigates the factors which influence users' behaviour to adopt these digital platforms, as the core of any platform's success is its users and their perception of value attached with the usage of that platform. This research defines platforms as an external set of digital resources which creates value and are useful during their interaction between seller and buyers (cf. Parker et al. 2016). These platforms have the uniqueness of holding no physical assets as compared to other platforms which have physical infrastructure such as automotive sectors platforms (Fisher et al. 1999). Digital platforms are an ecosystem that enables the user to enhance the interactions between their users. Sometimes platforms do not have anything common between their user's value chain, such as in the case of the AirBnB model the platform only provide an environment that focuses on the interaction of its users (Jacobides et al. 2018).

Moreover, the platform adaptation and the factors which influence that adaptation are also a very important part of this research and there are many studies which are being conducted by researchers in the same field such studies on the driving factors of consumers' acceptance of information technologies. Such as Sindek and Graybaal, 2011; Graybaal and Hayes, 2011. However, a research gap remains, because none of these studies was specific to digital platform adaptation and also none in the context of the United Kingdom. To address this gap this study, focus on these two limitations in the field and tried to fill the gap among literature.

To conclude, this field of research is very important for upcoming researchers as digital platforms are at the forefront of future business models and it is now important more than ever to understand the dynamics of the digital platforms. Besides a few studies on Information technology and consumers behaviour, there is not much research available that address the adaptation of the digital platform from a consumer point of view. This research will explain the users' intentions to use digital platforms by exploring their perception regarding platform usefulness and abilities to create value for them by using Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

1.1. Research Gap:

This work is expected to make three key contributions. First, by empirically testing the digital platforms from a consumer perspective, we expand the limited existing literature on this topic, which is purely theoretical. While reviewing the existing research papers, we identified many gaps, and this study presents this novelty by studying the drivers of intention to recommend and adapt the platforms. Second, by incorporating value creation and usefulness to the extended TAM model (Venkatesh et al., 2012), this study expanded TAM more broadly and the generalisability of this to the different context. Besides this, a few papers gave further direction on exploring users' attitude towards the technology acceptance (J.B. Schoret al.,2016) as a determinant. attitude is a very personal and unexpected behavioural trait and challenging to characterise. The less personal and less controllable environment of the online environment where platforms reside, enhance the importance of studying the attitude dimension. Understanding the attitude towards acceptance dimension and the implications of the intention to recommend and satisfaction with platforms furnishes many advantages for users and practitioners to design strategies to mitigate risks and increase trust.

Understanding the determinants of intention to recommend and sharing intention may offer more efficient and effective ways to adopt platforms. Third, by testing platforms in country like UK, we enhance of generalisation and applicability of this study to other specific scenarios. While most research-tested models were more focused on specific platforms, e.g. the factors of choosing a sharing option were tested on B2C car-sharing - car2go and the C2C accommodation marketplace - Airbnb (Mohlmann, 2015), this study offers to enrich the understanding of platforms and to contribute to the understanding of digital platforms adaptation factors on a general level.

1.2. Importance of the study

Since the late 1950s, the consumer's acceptance concept is gaining importance (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The origin of consumer behaviour is embedded into the Adamic research (Kernan, 1995; MacInnis and Folkes, 2010) and it also started to get mixed the marketing research. In the late 1960s, there were few efforts to establish consumer acceptability as a distinct subject to elevate the prominence of this field of study (Kernan, 1995; Wells, 1995). Due to the growth of marketing research, consumer behaviour has remained a sub-discipline of marketing that examines the adjacent fields (Helgeson et al., 1985).

In the late 1980s, the growth of information services (IS) prompted the development of a range of models that examined the consumer adoption of technologies (Venkatesh et al., 2003). There are a variety of theories that examine user acceptance of digital technologies, including the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975), the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) (Rogers, 1995), the Technology Acceptance Model 2 (TAM2) (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000), and (Venkatesh et al., 2003), the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) (Rogers, 1995), the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1985) and the Technology Acceptance Model 2 (TAM2) (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) has become one of the most widely used models for analysing user acceptance behaviour (Sheppard et al., 1988; Chau and Hu, 2001). The TAM model gained prominence after an increase in inquiry studies into the payments environment in 2006 by Pigneur and Ondrus, and since then, further studies have been conducted to establish a foundation for the TAM model's user adaption aspects (Mallat, 2007).

Numerous scholars have conducted a study on the elements affecting online platform adaption (Kim et al., 2010; Dahlbarg et al., 2003; Schierz et al., 2010;), on the online purchase of digital applications, and digital marketing and its effect on consumer behaviour (Gao et al., 2012). However, there is a scarcity of research on consumer acceptability of digital platforms, and even fewer in the UK context.

The competition among digital platforms is rising and platforms owners are losing their users which give rise to the urgency of research on a business model for digital platforms which address the issues of attracting and retaining its users (Schweizer Medien, 2017a).

This research addresses this issue, as none of the research has explored the combination of consumers' perception of usefulness and value creation of a platform as an adapting factor for the digital platform. Few studies studied the TAM model for users' acceptance of technologies (McFarland and Hamilton, 2006, , Venkatesh and Morris, 2000, Legris et al., 2003), however, only a few variables were used as an external variable for acceptance. Those variables and many more variables will be used in this research to generate a user acceptance model.

This study is based on the well-established Technology Acceptance Model and collects data from managers and specialists in real-world settings. One of the research's aims is to construct a model that can be used to describe how consumers perceive the digital platform. Despite rising evidence that user perception is critical for digital platform adoption, little research has been done on how to modify that impression to improve digital platform adaption (Agarwal et al., 1996). The purpose of this research is to better explain user perceptions of a platform's perceived utility and perceived value generation, which will result in a better understanding of why people utilise digital platforms.

1.3. Intended contribution:

The research was conducted by keeping the goal in mind of finding antecedents that deter users' attitudes towards the usage of digital platforms. Moreover, the study aimed to find the distinction between individual and system characteristics and their contribution towards influencing the users' intentions towards platform adaptation. This research will help platform users to build a framework that will focus on the features which influence users' attitudes towards using digital platforms. Additionally, the research will explore the impact of antecedent variables such as value creation and usefulness of the platform. Studies showed that value creation impacts users' influence towards adaptation digital platforms using dynamic capabilities of the platform (Teece 2007, Davis et al., 1989), whereas platforms' perceived usefulness improves the adaptation towards the use of technologies (Venkatesh and Davis, 1997, 2001). Therefore, the research aims to explore the relationship between these variables and the usage of the platforms. Additional factors that affect the adaption of digital platforms are also highlighted in this research, which adds to the body of knowledge on the subject.

This thesis examines the factors which impact the user's behaviour towards usage of digital platforms from a user point of view, specifically in the UK. Based on the view that the topic under discussion has novelty in nature and that no research has been conducted using the antecedents, which are used in this research pertaining to the UK market specifically. This study will help to fill the research gap and help to better understand the importance of the various dynamics of the digital platforms user's behaviour.

This research will also contribute towards the TAM theory as the TAM model will be used during this research. The study combined semi-structured interviews with the business users and platform experts who use digital platforms, in combination with the survey conducted

among the users which use digital platforms to buy these products. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) will be used for data analysis to improve the understanding of the digital platform's adaptation.

1.4. Research Question

The main question constructed, by keeping in mind the problem, is as follows.

“What are the major factors and relationships which influence the intention of users towards digital platform adaptation and what are the challenges and opportunities from the users' point of view towards acceptance of digital platforms in the UK and to develop a construct which will help to clarify these issues and provide a competitive advantage to its users”

1.5. Research Aim and Objectives:

Keeping in mind the importance of digital platforms and the increasing popularity of these platforms among their users and the impact of platformaization in the UK's economy, this study has the following Aim and Objectives. Adaptation

1.6. Aim:

The purpose of this study is to investigate the elements that impact the usage of digital platforms from the perspective of their users to establish a framework for their users in the United Kingdom.

1.7. Research objectives

Many studies have shown a favourable association between attitude and intention to utilise digital platforms, and this relationship is supported by evidence (Davis et al., 1989). Similar to this, consumers' perceptions of value generation and the usability of a platform impact their attitudes toward the adoption of technological innovations (Davis et al., 1989; Venkatesh and David, 1996, 2000). As well as there is an association between systemic traits and individual characteristics (Mun et al., 2006; Bhatti, 2007). This association needs to be evaluated since it has been examined before, but only in the context of mobile payment investigations. However, it is unknown if these external elements apply to the adaption of digital platforms in the United Kingdom. As such, this research seeks to establish that link in the context of the United Kingdom. Based on the above rationale, the following goals were established:

- To create a conceptual model that examines the effect of variables affecting the adaption of digital platforms on consumers' sentiments regarding their intention to utilise digital platforms.
- To critically review the existing literature in consumers behaviour and their acceptance of the digital platforms
- To identify and implement new system characteristics and distinctive aspects associated with the adaption of digital platforms.
- To conduct an empirical study of the impact of current and novel variables on platform adoption in the UK consumer market.
- To give suggestions based on the findings from objectives 2 and 3, both from a consumer and industry expert viewpoint, to improve knowledge of consumers' acceptance of digital platforms.

1.8. Outline of the study

This research is divided into seven chapters. The first chapter presents the thesis, which serves as the foundation for the research. Chapter one discussed the relevance of digital platforms in the modern world and the role of external factors such as value generation and the perceived utility of platform users in influencing platform adoption behaviour. The chapter also discusses the significance of the study, as well as research gaps that have been identified and how this study solves such difficulties. This chapter additionally commented on the study topic, goal, and objectives, as well as give some insight on the expected contribution.

The second chapter examines the literature by providing a historical overview of the internet, e-commerce, and digital platforms. Later in the chapter, the chapter discusses success determinants, platform adaption issues, and customer perceptions of digital platforms.

Chapter three discusses technology acceptance and adoption theories; in this chapter, the researcher discusses many theories of technology acceptance before settling on the TAM model for this study. The chapter elaborates on the TAM model's expansion to incorporate value creation as an antecedent.

The fourth chapter served as a study framework and hypothesis formulation chapter, in which all of the variables were addressed, and hypotheses were established to test them during the data analysis part of the research.

Chapter five provides the technique for the research. It describes the study paradigm in-depth, as well as a strategy and a research design. The sampling procedures, data gathering methods, and data analysis methodologies that were employed in this research are detailed in detail. The two methodologies are described in detail: semi-structured interviews with industry professionals and a web survey of digital news consumers.

The findings of the data gathering method are presented in Chapter Six of this report. It shares the findings of the pilot research with industry specialists to put the original conceptual model's foundations to the test.

As a result, it establishes the foundation for undertaking the full primary investigation. Following the discussion of the primary study findings with industry experts, the findings are applied to a consumer-centric web survey to examine a comprehensive conceptual model with the intent of identifying the factors that are empirically related to the use of online digital platforms adaptation.

Finally, Chapter Seven brings the thesis to a close by providing a summary of the important results as well as suggestions for platforms involved in the strategic planning and execution of digital platform adaptation. The first portion of this chapter provides an overview of the research, while the second section concludes the study's goals.

There are numerous notable contributions to theory to be made by this study's effort to analyse platform usage in a UK environment, which is highlighted in Section 3. Section four provides practical advice for platforms interested in implementing new strategic models, as well as commentary on the outcomes' transferability. Section five makes recommendations for future research endeavours. Section six of the chapter concludes the chapter by discussing the limitations of the research. The thesis is supplemented by a set of appendices and a list of references, which are included after this publication.

2. CHAPTER 2: Literature Review

A review of relevant studies on digital platforms may be found in this section. It examines the history of the Internet and e-commerce, as well as the vocabulary associated with e-commerce and e-business. From the literature, this chapter summarises the characteristics, classifications, phases, advantages, and downsides of e-commerce, as well as the setting in which e-commerce adoption is taking place. It finishes with a chapter summary and addresses the motivations of suppliers, the success factors of consumers, and the obstacles to e-commerce adoption.

2.1. Internet and Digital platforms history:

In 1969, a government-funded project to construct a network known as the ARPANET was launched, which was the beginning of the Internet (Advanced Research Projects Agency Network). Stanford Research Institute and the University of California, Los Angeles became linked as a result of this collaboration. With the inclusion of institutions in Utah and California, the system has grown significantly. This provided each side with access to the mainframes of the other. It was the ARPANET that grew rapidly in size and eventually formed the core of the present Internet (Abbate, 2001).

At the start of the 1970s, technologies such as Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) and Electronic Funds Transfer (EFT) have been used to facilitate economic transactions conducted via an electronic medium, which has come to be known as digital platforms. (p.136) EDI is defined as "the process of transferring data between two firms engaged in economic transactions via the use of computers and computer networking" (Pham, 2003). As defined by the Federal Reserve, an electronic funds transfer (EFT) is the electronic exchange of money between firms (Turban, 2007). By the late 1980s, electronic data interchange (EDI) started allowing (B2B) transactions and digital platforms (Brousseau, 2003, p.45). As a bonus, due to the expensive cost of setting up EDI, numerous firms contracted with a company known as a Value-Added-Network (VAN) to speed up the process. A monthly flat cost-plus a per-transaction fee was charged by VAN for the provision of the required connection for data transfer (Schneider, 2007, p.5).

The European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) established the ENQUIRE software project in 1989, which is credited with laying the foundation for the development of the WWW (World Wide Web). The first internet website was made available to the public in 1991. The European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) promised in 1993 that the World Wide Web will be made freely accessible, and this promise was fulfilled in 1994. In 1995, a large number of digital platform companies were established such as Amazon.com, founded by Jeff Bezos, which is a noteworthy example.

2.2. Online Platforms: Definition and Classification:

A digital marketplace, according to the European Commission (2016), is defined as a "digital market that allows people or small businesses to "transact" (i.e., search for, match, and transact) effectively and efficiently through the use of a variety of internet-connected digital

communication devices." The following are some of the key features of online platforms: Information and communication technologies (ICTs) used to promote transactions across different user groups; data collection and usage related to these transactions; and third-party network effects, where platforms with many users are more useful to other users. As instances of this, digital platforms (such as Alibaba and Apple App Store), travel websites (such as Expedia), crowdsourcing platforms (such as InnoCentive), and crowdfunding platforms are all available (e.g., Kickstarter). Additional rules of engagement (for example, information types, pricing formats, ratings, and search techniques) are established by the platform to guide users as they search for, interact with, and match items.

A "buyer-seller perspective" on online platforms can be used to categorise them based on the types of transactions that take place (for example, service (a ride), money (a loan), or information (a review)) between buyers and sellers. This is because there is no globally recognised categorization system for online platforms. Alternative viewpoints include "platform viewpoints," which include focusing on the platform's goals and objectives alone, and (e.g., reviews, resource-sharing, matching, crowdfunding). The second method for categorising online platforms allows for the mapping of these facilitations to business models (i.e., activities that provide value for both buyers and sellers, as well as activities that generate value for the platform (Chesbrough, 2007)). Our limits force us to focus on resource categorising online platforms allows for the mapping of these facilitations to business models (i.e., activities that provide value for both buyers and sellers, as well as activities that generate value for the platform (Chesbrough, 2007)). Our limits force us to focus on resource sharing, matching, crowdsourcing, and review platforms as well as crowdfunding platforms as shown in Table. In addition, we focus on "virtual" online platforms that "do not keep real inventories of things or contents," according to our definition.

Table 2.0. Classification of online platforms according to business models and user groups.

Business Model \ User Group	Business to Business (B2B)	Business to Consumer (B2C)	Consumer to Consumer (C2C)
Resource Sharing	WeWork	Uber Eats, Deliveroo ⁸ , Ele. me,	Uber, Didi- Chuxing, Airbnb, Yard Club, Udemy
Matching	Upwork (formerly known as Elance)	Monster, CareerBuilder, LinkedIn (a recruitment platform)	e-Harmony, Match, TaskRabbit, Tinder, Instagram ¹⁰
Crowdsourcing	InnoCentive, ¹¹ Kaggle, Topcoder, NineSigma	LiveOps ¹²	

Review		Kelly Blue Book, <u>Shopzilla</u> , Shopping.com	Yelp, Rotten Tomatoes, TripAdvisor, Angie's List, <u>Meituan-Dianping</u>
Crowdfunding		Kickstarter, Indiegogo	<u>LendingClub</u> , Prosper

Virtual online platforms (see Table 2.0), which do not have any actual assets, act as "intermediaries" between different user groups. Examples of each of the five platform types are provided in the sections that follow this one. 1) Customers and drivers can use their real-time location data to get matched up for trips through Uber. 2) e-Harmony is a dating service that connects male and female members for dating based on their personal information and interests. 3) InnoCentive is a crowdsourcing platform that enables a large number of problem solvers to compete for the chance to provide the best solution to a problem given by a seeker by submitting their solutions to the platform. 4) As a review site, Yelp enables a big number of people to write evaluations and discuss their experiences with a wide range of companies. A crowdsourcing platform, Kickstarter, enables a person to raise money for a project by soliciting contributions from individuals, businesses, and other organisations.

2.3. Suppliers' motivations and consumers' success factors in Digital platforms adoption:

Digital platforms are discussed in this section in terms of the factors that encourage suppliers to use them and the factors that deter consumers. Businesses all around the globe are migrating to digital platforms as a result of the evolution of global communications technology. Several indicators were identified by Chong, Lin, and colleagues (2009) as being associated with Malaysian enterprises' adoption of collaborative commerce (e-commerce).

Two of these factors were the pressure from competitors and the support of top management. According to Jianhong and Hua (2011), the consumer mindset plays a critical role in the adoption of digital platforms, particularly social media. Many factors impact consumer opinion, including privacy, trust, economic conditions, social culture, and the reputations of service providers, among others. According to Chan et al. (2001, p. 5), three key factors of supplier usage of digital platforms were identified. To begin, the Internet makes it easier for companies to distribute their products and services. Second, rising competition in the business world encourages organisations to explore new choices, such as integrating digital platforms into their operations, to stay competitive. Third, globalisation drives enterprises to expand their networks into new international markets as a result of increased competition.

Another important factor is linked to the information age, in which businesses benefit from data collecting for marketing purposes. Fifth is the use of automation technologies to keep growing labour costs as low as possible. Finally, to suit the demands of both enterprises and customers, low-cost, high-quality products and services should be available.

The spread of digital platform education in China is being pushed by four factors, according to separate research. These factors are economic globalisation; local economic growth; information technology improvement; and government promotional efforts (Zhang et al., 2004). Return policies are a significant factor in the adoption of digital platforms by both customers and service providers, and they must be reasonable. In various studies, it has been noticed that the lack of return and refund policies is one of the obstacles that prevent consumers in Saudi Arabia from making use of digital platforms. On the bright side, several studies have shown that instituting a return policy increases sales volume (Whyatt and Koschek, 2010, p586, Business Fraud Awareness, 2010).

According to Fidler (2008), security features may be divided into two categories: physical (certificates of authenticity, HTTPS, and the lock icon) and intangible (certificates of authenticity, HTTPS, and the lock icon) (previous experiences and word of mouth). According to the research, consumers placed a higher value on ethereal features than they did on physical characteristics.

As reported by Xu (2008, p.334), environmental variables (including information, infrastructure, and demographic factors) have an impact on the adoption of B2C digital

platforms in his study. Al-Maghrabi (2011) conducted a study in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and concluded that the quality of the platform and its content add to the utility and enjoyment of the clients. Also mentioned was the importance of "positive word of mouth" from family and friends in spreading trust in a platform. The authors of Kim and Fesenmaier (2008) claim that early perception of a platform leads to fast decisions and judgement about its overall value and quality. Sung (2006, p.1167) outlined sixteen elements that businesses must consider to be successful while using digital platforms. These success criteria include the following:

- Customer relationship, i.e., each customer's homepage should be personalised.
- Consumer information privacy.
- Creation of value.
- Convenience of usage.
- The importance of developing a digital platform strategy.
- Working knowledge of the platform.
- The system's stability.
- The system's security.
- Innovation.
- Secure payment processing.
- Trust.
- The breadth of the merchandise.
- Convenience.
- Transportation services.
- Additional services such as toll-free numbers.

- The capability to examine the functioning of digital platforms.

Even though the many variables discovered in the literature are categorised in a variety of ways, they all serve the same purpose. [Jennex et al.\(2004, p.280\)](#) identified five infrastructure success factors for digital platforms: people factors (employing employees who are culturally and linguistically literate), technical infrastructure for developing applications for the organisation and interface with clients, a business infrastructure, and a regulatory interface. According to [Turban \(2000\)](#), many critical success factors (CSF) are comparable, such as senior management support and a user-friendly website, among other things. The privacy risk associated with e-services, according to [Featherman et al. \(2010\)](#), is larger when buying e-services online than when purchasing items or traditional services. Furthermore, perceived risk had a stronger influence on participants across the whole online purchase decision-making process. ([Martn et al., 2010](#), [Jones and Leonard, 2008](#)). According to [Limayem and colleagues \(2000, p.427\)](#), six factors influence online purchasing. The following are examples of such:

- Intentions "as intentions precede behaviour."
- Attitude.
- Individual innovativeness (individuals vary in their degree and rate of innovation uptake).
- Behavioural control (access to the site, loading speed, navigability, product description, transaction efficiency, and navigation efficiency).

E-commerce CSF has been identified by many researchers, including [Shah et al.\(2007, p.513\)](#), who identified competent customer service, legislation and business process reengineering, as well as the real-time integration of distributed resources, the real-time Internet (such as an ATM that provides real-time balance information over the Internet), and the richness of web page and brand content. Additional research was carried out by [Laosethakul and Boulton \(2007, p.10\)](#) on the following CSFs for online platforms: It is important to have a user-friendly website that is easy to find products for customers to choose from, as well as a variety of products to choose from and clear instructions. It is also important to have a reliable Internet connection, secure online data storage, knowledgeable IT

staff and a well-known brand. A study conducted by Chong et al. (2010, p.279) found that government support was a significant predictor of online banking intention in Vietnam.

2.4. Challenges to digital platforms adoption (Barriers)

Previous research on the barriers that prohibit countries from embracing digital platforms is summarised in this section. According to Abdulghader et al. (2011), the bulk of the barriers to digital platform adoption in the United Kingdom are in order of importance. There were several barriers to adoption, including concerns about Internet fraud and lack of necessary infrastructure, a lack of government support, the initial cost, a lack of knowledge about digital platforms, a lack of a secure e-payment system, organisational barriers, a lack of telecommunications infrastructure, and an insufficient level of coordination among stakeholders.

According to Mohanna et al. (2011), there is a myriad of factors that influence the adoption of digital platforms. Among the variables were technical infrastructure (Internet speed and connection, logistics, and ICT professionals), management organisations (government investment in information technology, the availability of digital platforms departments within enterprises, and legal difficulties), and social-cultural context (such as ethnic diversity and religious affiliation) (ICT literacy, trust in digital platforms, digital platforms awareness and training).

The researchers Kapurubandara and Lawson (2006) did another study in which they discriminated between internal and external barriers to the use of digital platforms. People's internal restraints include a scarcity of competence and concerns about their safety. Cultural (lack of popularity for online sales), political (instability in one's country's economy), social (lack of knowledge about digital platforms and ICT knowledge among senior management), legal and regulatory (lack of information about digital platforms and ICT knowledge among senior management) and other external barriers are all present (an insufficient legal framework for digital platforms, lack of standards in software and little government support).

In another research, Abid, Rahim, and colleagues (2011) identified several of the barriers previously mentioned as well as some new Thulani et al. (2010) agreed with the bulk of the problems highlighted above and added the insufficiency of digital platforms for specific commodities provided by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). According to Olatokun and Kebonye, security concerns are a serious impediment to the growth of SMEs

(2010). Lawrence and Tar (2010) identified four digital platform roadblocks in developing and developing countries, respectively. The first obstacle to overcome was infrastructure, which includes technology, telecommunications, the high cost of Internet access, and the accessibility of necessary equipment. Secondly, policy and aid are scarce from the federal government. The third kind of barrier is societal, and it includes issues such as trust, and a lack of human contact. The fourth kind of hurdle is socioeconomic, and it comprises factors such as economic conditions, payment and educational systems, as well as logistics.

As part of their research, Commerce Net published a report in 2000 that identified the top ten hurdles to the adoption of digital platforms in the United States (Turban et al., 2006, p.27). The most major causes were security, trust, and risk, which were followed by a lack of qualified staff, a lack of business models, a lack of culture, user authentication, a lack of public key infrastructure, organisation, fraud, and a lack of clear Internet navigation directions. Barbon is and Laspita (2005, p. 31) and Jones and Leonard (2008) agreed with Commerce Net in stating that a lack of trust is a barrier to consumer adoption of digital platforms. Karakaya and Charlton (2001, p. 49) agreed with Commerce Net in stating that a lack of trust is a barrier to consumer adoption of digital platforms. Karakaya and Charlton (2001, p. 49) concurred with Commerce Net in stating that a lack of trust is a barrier.

Customers have also complained about late or uneven delivery of products, especially over the Christmas season, which they say has caused substantial issues for them. When Papaza (2004) found that there were several possible hurdles and obstructions (digital platforms). The following are examples of such:

- Internet access is restricted.
- A scarcity of competent personnel.
- Inadequate computing equipment.
- A scarcity of communication infrastructure.
- Inadequate payment mechanisms.
- Inadequate faith in the platform.

- Limited familiarity with the platform.
- Insufficient collaboration between the public and commercial sectors.
- Inadequate collaboration between academia and private industry.
- The absence of legislation governing digital platforms.
- The prohibitively high cost of network infrastructure.
- Individuals' anxieties about their financial security.
- The high cost of Internet access.
- Delay in rural development.
- ICT professionals get a low wage.
- Affluent populace, which limits investment options.

While Ahmed and his colleagues (2006) conducted their research in Saudi Arabia, they discovered a slew of challenges that organisations may face when using digital platforms. There are many of these issues that are either organisational or consumer-related, such as a dependence on face-to-face contact, a lack of technical help, and older people who are unwilling to make use of information technologies. During a second study conducted in Saudi Arabia, Al-Hudhaif and Alkubeyver (2011) revealed that market e-readiness, awareness, human and technological resources, and market e-readiness are all factors that influence the performance of private sector enterprises in Saudi Arabia. As a result of their research, AlGhamdi et al. (2011) and AlGhamdi et al. (2011b) discovered several characteristics that influence the adoption of digital platforms in Saudi Arabia. There were a variety of factors considered, including selling and purchasing habits, delivery issues, online payment, a lack of an adequate ICT infrastructure, unclear regulations, a lack of trust, a lack of government support, people's culture, suppliers' beliefs in their inability to offer online advantages to consumers, that certain products (such as food) are not suitable for digital platforms, a lack of digital platform experience among suppliers, resistance to change, and the high setup costs for digital platforms.

When it comes to purchasing decisions, negative feedback has a far bigger impact on customers' decisions than positive input (Zhou et al., 2009). Additionally, the reputation of a vendor has an impact on sales (Ye et al., 2009). Six hurdles to the formation of global digital platforms were identified by Farhoomand et al. (2000, p. 27). Several of these difficulties have already been addressed in the literature, while others are worthy of consideration for addition.

1. A legal stumbling block: In addition to user privacy and advertising regulations, copyright laws, the legitimacy of electronic signatures, the responsibility of Internet service providers, encryption and public-key encryption are also covered.
2. Cultural obstacles include things like ethnic, religious, and language barriers, to name a few.
3. Unfavourable attitudes, a lack of knowledge, a reluctance to change, and an absence of commitment on the part of top management are all examples of organisational impediments.
4. Government attitudes and interagency coordination, among other things, are a source of worry in the political sphere.

According to Rotchanakitumnuai and Speece (2003, p.316), there are nine obstacles to Internet banking, which they categorise as trust issues. These obstacles include security, confidence in the service provider, and transaction reliability, among others. There is a second group of challenges that involves legal assistance. These difficulties include privacy protection, equitable responsibility for bank clients for financial mistakes, and the court's ability to resolve Internet banking disputes on time. Finally, there are organisational hurdles, which include a negative attitude, a lack of information and communications technology resources, and a lack of experience in how to properly use Internet banking.

Another obstacle is that the majority of senior managers are above the age of 50, creating a generational divide between the leader and his or her workforce. Another group of researchers, such as Aguila-Obra and Padilla-MelUndez (2006), found that organisations were the most significant hurdle to the use of Internet technology, particularly when it came to digital platforms. There are two factors at play in this situation: technological resources and managerial skills. Other difficulties have been identified by Chircu and Kauffman (2000, p.66), including conversion (moving from an existing system to a new one), resources,

knowledge, and usage of the system. According to Barbon is and Laspita (2005, p.31), a majority of the difficulties previously described in the literature as barriers to the adoption of digital platforms are still present. These include security, privacy, the Internet's condition of anonymity, limited payment options, and a lack of human connection.

When Siala et al. (2004, p. 7) said that "religion has an impact on consumer purchasing decisions," they agreed with the literature. Similarly, Chau et al. (2002, p.139) voiced a similar point of view on culture, arguing that it influences consumers' perceptions of online platforms.

2.5. Consumer perspective towards digital platforms

User perception drives the acceptance and utilisation of any service. It creates a make-or-break situation for the service providers where the positive perception means more business opportunities, and negative perception leads to lesser usage of the services. Sharma et al. [30] investigated user perception of the effectiveness of performance management systems. They argued that the accuracy and fairness of these systems help develop positive user perception that leads to increased service usage. Bourgonjon et al. [31] investigated students' perceptions of video games in the classroom and argued that their preference is directly affected by the perceptions of usefulness, ease of use, learning opportunities, and personal experience with video games. Lui and Jamieson [27] investigated the trust and risk perception of e-commerce users. They argued that perceived risk is a direct antecedent of intention to transact, and various dimensions of attitude have a positive influence on perceived risk. Similarly, Ndubisi [28] investigated user perception and intention to adopt internet banking and argued that PU and PEU are strong determinants of behavioural intention to adopt internet banking. In the case of real estate and property sectors, Ullah et al. [22], Ullah et al. [32] and Ullah and Al-Turjman [33] discussed the usage of Big9 technologies, including drones, the internet of things (IoT), clouds, software as a service (SaaS), big data, 3D scanning, wearable technologies, virtual and augmented realities (VR and AR), and artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics for shaping positive user perception of adopting real estate technologies. Felli et al. [13] proposed using 360° videos and mobile laser measurement technologies for immersive visualisation of real estate to shape its positive perception and image. Ullah et al. [34] investigated the managerial perspective on barriers to the digitalisation of Australian Smart Real Estate. The authors argued that high costs and complex systems, lack of will to invest in digital technologies and government support, regulations, and standards lead to technology non-adoption in the presence of positive user perception. Similarly, Ullah et al. [11] reported that REOP design shape positive user perception. Further, lack of information on the REOPs such as property photos, neighbourhood insights, and delayed response from real estate agencies is responsible for the lesser utilisation of these platforms.

In terms of the theories used for modelling or assessing the user perception and acceptance of technologies, TAM, ISSM, Diffusion of Innovation (DOI), and Hedonic Demand (HDT) are evident from published literature. DOI deals with how, why, and what of the rate of new ideas and technology spread. It has five key categories: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. These refer to types of users accepting the innovation or technologies. Similarly, HDT deals with the value offered by a service or technology and explains that users are willing to pay for technology or service equivalent to its value offered. Thus, the price an individual is happy to pay for a technology reflects the users' perceived value or usefulness of the technology. TAM and ISSM are among the two most utilised theories for modelling and capturing user perceptions. Accordingly, these are utilised in the current study and explained subsequently.

Similarly, an examination of the growth of digital platforms reveals that client approval is essential, according to the study team, who believes that market penetration is decided by the acceptance and actual use of particular platform services. Nonetheless, this presents a substantial risk of failure in the process of changing the general attitude of platforms from one of rejection to one of acceptance and utilisation. a.

Considering that customers are primarily responsible for determining platform utilisation, the question of which factors have an impact on platform usage arises. The apparent point to make here is that merchants will comply with consumer requests for payment and paid content consumption procedures only if the benefits outweigh the expenses. This thesis is based on Davis's Technology Acceptance Model, which was first published in 1985 and revised in 1993.

2.6. ACCEPTANCE AND USE OF TECHNOLOGY EVALUATION MODELS

Here is a quick look at some of the ideas and models that have been used to predict, explain, and understand how people and businesses will use new technology and how it will affect them. These concepts have developed over many years as a consequence of the never-ending attempts at confirming and extending models that have occurred with the release of each model in the series of models. In the field of information systems, there is a substantial body of literature, which includes a large lot of research on the human and organisational

acceptance of technology advancements. To explain why end-users choose to adopt new technology, psychologically-based theories are necessary to be developed. Developed by Albert Bandura in 1986, SCT is a viewpoint on how people's decision-making processes are impacted that is used in psychological research.

On the contrary to many other sociologists, SCT believes that cognitive processes have a considerable impact on how people react to a variety of different situations and environments. New technologies' acceptability has been evaluated in recent research employing most of Bandura's principles, which are summarised here. Known as technology acceptance models, these studies have had the bulk of their constructs reduced to the 32 by Venkatesh et al (2003a), which are the most often used. The general overview and core concepts of these models are explained in the table below:

Table 1. Models and Theories of Individual Acceptance

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)	Core Constructs	Definitions
<p>Drawn from social psychology, TRA is one of the most fundamental and influential theories of human behavior. It has been used to predict a wide range of behaviors (see Sheppard et al. 1988 for a review). Davis et al. (1989) applied TRA to individual acceptance of technology and found that the variance explained was largely consistent with studies that had employed TRA in the context of other behaviors.</p>	Attitude Toward Behavior	"an individual's positive or negative feelings (evaluative affect) about performing the target behavior" (Fishbein and Ajzen 1975, p. 216).
	Subjective Norm	"the person's perception that most people who are important to him think he should or should not perform the behavior in question" (Fishbein and Ajzen 1975, p. 302).
Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)		
<p>TAM is tailored to IS contexts, and was designed to predict information technology acceptance and usage on the job. Unlike TRA, the final conceptualization of TAM excludes the attitude construct in order to better explain intention parsimoniously. TAM2 extended TAM by including subjective norm as an additional predictor of intention in the case of mandatory settings (Venkatesh and Davis 2000). TAM has been widely applied to a diverse set of technologies and users.</p>	Perceived Usefulness	"the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance" (Davis 1989, p. 320).
	Perceived Ease of Use	"the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort" (Davis 1989, p. 320).
	Subjective Norm	Adapted from TRA/TPB. Included in TAM2 only.
Motivational Model (MM)		
<p>A significant body of research in psychology has supported general motivation theory as an explanation for behavior. Several studies have examined motivational theory and adapted it for specific contexts. Vallerand (1997) presents an excellent review of the fundamental tenets of this theoretical base. Within the information systems domain, Davis et al. (1992) applied motivational theory to understand new technology adoption and use (see also Venkatesh and Speier 1999).</p>	Extrinsic Motivation	The perception that users will want to perform an activity "because it is perceived to be instrumental in achieving valued outcomes that are distinct from the activity itself, such as improved job performance, pay, or promotions" (Davis et al. 1992, p. 1112).
	Intrinsic Motivation	The perception that users will want to perform an activity "for no apparent reinforcement other than the process of performing the activity per se" (Davis et al. 1992, p. 1112).

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)	Core Constructs	Definitions
<p>TPB extended TRA by adding the construct of perceived behavioral control. In TPB, perceived behavioral control is theorized to be an additional determinant of intention and behavior. Ajzen (1991) presented a review of several studies that successfully used TPB to predict intention and behavior in a wide variety of settings. TPB has been successfully applied to the understanding of individual acceptance and usage of many different technologies (Harrison et al. 1997; Mathieson 1991; Taylor and Todd 1995b). A related model is the Decomposed Theory of Planned Behavior (DTPB). In terms of predicting intention, DTPB is identical to TPB. In contrast to TPB but similar to TAM, DTPB "decomposes" attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control into its the underlying belief structure within technology adoption contexts.</p>	Attitude Toward Behavior	Adapted from TRA.
	Subjective Norm	Adapted from TRA.
	Perceived Behavioral Control	"the perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behavior" (Ajzen 1991, p. 188). In the context of IS research, "perceptions of internal and external constraints on behavior" (Taylor and Todd 1995b, p. 149).
Combined TAM and TPB (C-TAM-TPB)		
<p>This model combines the predictors of TPB with perceived usefulness from TAM to provide a hybrid model (Taylor and Todd 1995a).</p>	Attitude Toward Behavior	Adapted from TRA/TPB.
	Subjective Norm	Adapted from TRA/TPB.
	Perceived Behavioral Control	Adapted from TRA/TPB.
	Perceived Usefulness	Adapted from TAM.

Model of PC Utilization (MPCU)	Core Constructs	Definitions
<p>Derived largely from Triandis' (1977) theory of human behavior, this model presents a competing perspective to that proposed by TRA and TPB. Thompson et al. (1991) adapted and refined Triandis' model for IS contexts and used the model to predict PC utilization. However, the nature of the model makes it particularly suited to predict individual acceptance and use of a range of information technologies. Thompson et al. (1991) sought to predict usage behavior rather than intention; however, in keeping with the theory's roots, the current research will examine the effect of these determinants on intention. Also, such an examination is important to ensure a fair comparison of the different models.</p>	Job-fit	"the extent to which an individual believes that using [a technology] can enhance the performance of his or her job" (Thompson et al. 1991, p. 129).
	Complexity	Based on Rogers and Shoemaker (1971), "the degree to which an innovation is perceived as relatively difficult to understand and use" (Thompson et al. 1991, p. 128).
	Long-term Consequences	"Outcomes that have a pay-off in the future" (Thompson et al. 1991, p. 129).
	Affect Towards Use	Based on Triandis, affect toward use is "feelings of joy, elation, or pleasure, or depression, disgust, displeasure, or hate associated by an individual with a particular act" (Thompson et al. 1991, p. 127).
	Social Factors	Derived from Triandis, social factors are "the individual's internalization of the reference group's subjective culture, and specific interpersonal agreements that the individual has made with others, in specific social situations" (Thompson et al. 1991, p. 126).
	Facilitating Conditions	Objective factors in the environment that observers agree make an act easy to accomplish. For example, returning items purchased online is facilitated when no fee is charged to return the item. In an IS context, "provision of support for users of PCs may be one type of facilitating condition that can influence system utilization" (Thompson et al. 1991, p. 129).

Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT)	Core Constructs	Definitions
<p>Grounded in sociology, IDT (Rogers 1995) has been used since the 1960s to study a variety of innovations, ranging from agricultural tools to organizational innovation (Tornatzky and Klein 1982). Within information systems, Moore and Benbasat (1991) adapted the characteristics of innovations presented in Rogers and refined a set of constructs that could be used to study individual technology acceptance. Moore and Benbasat (1996) found support for the predictive validity of these innovation characteristics (see also Agarwal and Prasad 1997, 1998; Karahanna et al. 1999; Plouffe et al. 2001).</p>	Relative Advantage	"the degree to which an innovation is perceived as being better than its precursor" (Moore and Benbasat 1991, p. 195).
	Ease of Use	"the degree to which an innovation is perceived as being difficult to use" (Moore and Benbasat 1991, p. 195).
	Image	"The degree to which use of an innovation is perceived to enhance one's image or status in one's social system" (Moore and Benbasat 1991, p. 195).
	Visibility	The degree to which one can see others using the system in the organization (adapted from Moore and Benbasat 1991).
	Compatibility	"the degree to which an innovation is perceived as being consistent with the existing values, needs, and past experiences of potential adopters" (Moore and Benbasat 1991, p. 195).
	Results Demonstrability	"the tangibility of the results of using the innovation, including their observability and communicability" (Moore and Benbasat 1991, p. 203).
	Voluntariness of Use	"the degree to which use of the innovation is perceived as being voluntary, or of free will" (Moore and Benbasat 1991, p. 195).

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT)	Core Constructs	Definitions
<p>One of the most powerful theories of human behavior is social cognitive theory (see Bandura 1986). Compeau and Higgins (1995b) applied and extended SCT to the context of computer utilization (see also Compeau et al. 1999); while Compeau and Higgins (1995a) also employed SCT, it was to study performance and thus is outside the goal of the current research. Compeau and Higgins' (1995b) model studied computer use but the nature of the model and the underlying theory allow it to be extended to acceptance and use of information technology in general. The original model of Compeau and Higgins (1995b) used usage as a dependent variable but in keeping with the spirit of predicting individual acceptance, we will examine the predictive validity of the model in the context of intention and usage to allow a fair comparison of the models.</p>	Outcome Expectations—Performance	The performance-related consequences of the behavior. Specifically, performance expectations deal with job-related outcomes (Compeau and Higgins 1995b).
	Outcome Expectations—Personal	The personal consequences of the behavior. Specifically, personal expectations deal with the individual esteem and sense of accomplishment (Compeau and Higgins 1995b).
	Self-efficacy	Judgment of one's ability to use a technology (e.g., computer) to accomplish a particular job or task.
	Affect	An individual's liking for a particular behavior (e.g., computer use).
	Anxiety	Evoking anxious or emotional reactions when it comes to performing a behavior (e.g., using a computer).

Table 1: Models and theories of Individual acceptance. Source: Author

2.6.1. Theory of Reasoned Action:

In the mid-1970s, Ajzen and Fishbein claimed that an individual's real behaviour may be addressed by assessing his or her goal in combination with the beliefs he or she would have for the behaviour under consideration (Davis, 1986). It is referred to as BI (Behavioural Desire) and it is an examination of the individual's intention to conduct the behaviour before engaging in it.

An individual's BI, according to Ajzen and Fishbein (1980), may be addressed by their attitude toward genuine BI in combination with the corresponding subjective norm. Human behaviour and relevant solutions were investigated using the models in the 1980s. However, the purpose elements of this model are not necessarily confined to the proposal factor, which is an essential consideration since it contributes to characterising and anticipating a person's behaviour and attitude (Werner, 2004).

Three components characterise consumer behaviour in this model: BI, individual attitude toward the behaviour, and a subjective norm. Individuals' actual behaviour, according to Ajzen and Fishbein (1980), is a product of their desire to demonstrate that behaviour, which is a result of the individual's attitude and subjective standards. They described behaviourism as a person's proclivity to engage in certain behaviours. The individual's perception of the consequences of engaging in this behaviour, together with the individual's judgement of the repercussions, is taken into consideration while forming an attitude. An Individual's evaluation of what other relevant individuals anticipate, as well as the individual's excitement to meet these expectations, is referred to as Subjective Norm (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980).

The TRA framework assumes that an individual's desire to participate in or refrain from engaging in a particular behaviour is conditional on the individual's want to engage in or refrain from engaging in a particular behaviour (ibid). Investigators have utilised the TRA framework to effectively analyse UB (Usage Behaviour) by presuming that their investigation of an individual's ideas, behaviour outcomes, and attitude predominates over their examination of their actual behaviour (Yousafzai et al. 2010). Aside from that, judgements regarding this model were formed as a result of the model's indistinct links between subjective norm and attitude and its presumption that BI resulted in unconstrained real behaviour (Truong, 2009).

Through the use of the TRA framework, researchers have uncovered a variety of incidental components that have been demonstrated to impact an individual's motivation to engage in a certain behaviour (Venkatesh & Davis 2003). This framework benefits from the identification of BI and the factors that influence it because it allows investigators to use this model to comprehend the cognitive areas of human behaviour and identify the aspects that can be targeted to affect willing behaviour, resulting in investigators such as Sheppard et al. (1998) lavishing praise on the model's predictive capabilities and concluding that it could be used in research outside of its intended sociological difficulties.

With the adoption of digital platforms as a necessary behaviour, this paradigm proposes that the desire to embrace the platform will naturally result in acceptance of the underlying technological infrastructure. Also shown by the study is that use is not only driven by the intents of the user and that demographic features have an impact on the intention to embrace the technology. According to Abbas and Nik (2010), the TRA theory is considered to be crucial when it comes to predicting behaviour. As a result, the segmentation of BI and actual behaviour into a series of ideas may be included in the model.

2.6.2. Motivational Model (MM):

As a consequence of psychological research, this product was conceived and created (Davis, et al., 1992). Numerous psychological studies have been conducted to establish the association between the MM model and behaviour. As established by Davis et al. (1992), a theory of motivation including intrinsic as well as extrinsic motivational aspects is required to explain the process of deciding on new technology in the area of information systems, implementing it, adopting it, and putting it into use.

2.6.3. Theory of Planned Behaviour:

In response to the limitations of TRA, Ajzen and Fishbein (1985) conceived and built TPB, which is still in use today. TPB has been utilised and validated in a wide range of research to predict people's intentions and behaviours in the context of technological adoption. In their critique of TPB and TRA, Taylor and Todd (1995b) point out that the assumption that users must be motivated to do certain behaviours may create issues when researching consumer adoption behaviour. According to the data, this theory accounts for anywhere between 21 per cent and 37 per cent of the variation in technology uptake and user behaviour seen in the research. When the TPB was developed, according to Eagle and Chairken (1993), it did not take into account the existence of extra structures capable of anticipating behaviour intention. TPB, according to the authors, did not illustrate how individuals should strategize or how strategizing is related to TPB in any way.

2.6.4. Decomposed Theory of Planned Behaviour (DTPB):

This theory is tested by two separate experiments. Because it incorporates components from an IDT perspective, DTPB improves on TRA (Taylor & Todd, 1995a). In DTPB, the factors PU, complexity, compatibility, subjective norm, SE, and FC are all considered. To test the appropriateness of the TRA, TPB, and DTPB as forecasting theories for consumer behavioural intentions, Taylor and Todd (1995a) experimented.

In the SEM study, it was discovered that, although TRA and TPB were both capable of predicting behaviour, the DTPB was the most effective in explaining it. This concept may explain anywhere between 21 per cent and 25 per cent of the variation in technology adoption and user behaviour seen across time.

A person's genuine behaviour, according to this concept, is a product of four components, which are discussed more below. The TPB's major goal is to predict and understand human behaviour via an investigation of the four elements' influence on human behaviour (Armitage & Christian, 2003). By including a fourth variable (PBC), TPB, in contrast to the TRA,

expands the predictability of its framework beyond complete knowledge of BI to encompass behaviour that is not totally within the control of the individual's free will (Bilic, 2005). Based on the idea that people would show a certain behaviour depending on the ease or difficulty of performing the behaviour and the presence of enhancing external circumstances, this fourth variable was developed (Ajzen, 1991). TPB also holds that if an objective is persistent, some behaviours become unavoidable (ibid). As a consequence of this assumption, TPB has some success in analytical applications, but it also faces the same limits as TRA in terms of computational efficiency. The adoption of the TPB has been effective in an investigation that has included health, technology, and social behaviour (Brown and Venkatesh, 2005). According to Armitage and Conner (2001) as well as Godin and Kok (1996), these three characteristics may account for 39–42 percent of the difference in intention to demonstrate behaviour in different situations. It's possible that PBC and BI together account for anywhere between 24 and 39 percent of the diversity in actual behaviour.

These researchers, notably Elliot (2003) and Sheeran (2001), were persuaded by several results to see this framework as a comprehensive model that could be utilised to analyse and understand individual behaviour. Also preserved is the concept that a desire to demonstrate a behaviour will result in the actual execution of that behaviour by the user. Following this assumption, the model was tested using inquiry findings, which revealed that real behaviour was not a direct outcome of BI (Bias Inquiry) (Taylor & Todd, 2001). TPB factors explained a significant percentage of the variation in both perceived and real behaviour, but they did not account for a significant portion of the variation in either perceived or actual behaviour. Individuals' responses to external conditions are not taken into consideration by the TPB, according to Sharma et al. (2007), and debates over the link between subjective norm and attitude continue. TPB's prediction is confined to four variables in the absence of external circumstances, which is inadequate for exploratory settings, which need anticipating an individual's behaviour utilising a more grounded collection of information than four variables (ibid).

Because it does not account for the effect of other external factors, such as demographic data, TPB cannot be used to evaluate consumer acceptance of digital marketplaces in the United Kingdom when these limits are taken into consideration (Knabe, 2012). Recent research revealed the importance of these components in the adoption of new technologies, and this

model's failure to include these structures excludes it from being employed in this study due to its limitations. An additional element of this technique, as highlighted by Taylor and Todd (2001), makes it inappropriate for application in this research on client adoption of digital platforms. The unusual nature of variables such as Attitude Towards Behaviour (ATB) makes it difficult to conduct a practical study of the variable, even though it is a qualitative variable that has been extensively researched.

2.6.5. Combined Technology Acceptance Model & Theory of Planned Behaviour (CTAM-TPB):

An integrated theory, which integrates the TPB and PU variables from the technology acceptance model, is presented in this section. PBC and subjective standards were both incorporated in Taylor and Todd's TAM to provide more full and important drivers of information technology utilisation, according to Taylor and Todd (1995a). While allowing for a degree of purpose and user behaviour variety, the authors believe that this technique allows for adequate usage by both expert and beginner users. The C-TAM model may be effective even if the person has no experience with the technology under research, meaning that the model may be used to estimate future use behaviour for people with or without prior experience with the technology being studied.

2.6.6. Model of PC Utilisation (MPCU):

To forecast the use of personal computers (PCs), Thompson and colleagues created the MPCU in 1991. Affective attitudes toward usage, complexity, FC, job fit, long-term ramifications for the organisation, and societal considerations are the major variables in MPCU theory.

2.6.7. Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT):

"Diffusion" is defined by Rogers (2005) as "the process by which a novelty is conveyed among members of a social system along specified routes and within a certain timeframe." Additionally, Rogers (1995) defined communication as the act of generating and transmitting information among individuals to promote a shared understanding among those involved. The simplicity with which an innovation may be used, and the novelty of the invention may be indicators of how a person will react to it. Certain features of novelty adoption have been found, including their difficulty, relative benefit, and compatibility with existing technologies.

In other words, when there is a relative gain, people are more likely to accept innovation since it is less complicated and compatible with their existing lifestyles. These ideas were not taken into account by Rogers (1993), who feels that relative advantage and compatibility are key aspects to evaluate when analysing innovation adoption trends (Zhao, 2008).

2.6.8. Social Cognitive Theory (SCT):

As indicated in the chapter's opening section, Bandura(1986) developed it for the goal of analysing human behaviour. It was used by Compeau and Higgins (1999) to research computer usage. It involves emotion, anxiety, performance and personal outcome expectations, as well as SE. SCT, which Bandura invented in 1986, is a psychometric research viewpoint on how people's decision-making process's function. The concept is crucial for analysing the area of technology adoption because it provides a framework for grasping human behaviour. According to the concept, three elements influence human behaviour: personal, behavioural, and environmental. To the contrary of some sociologists' claims, SCT holds that cognitive processes have an important role to play in how people react to diverse situations and contexts. The bulk of Bandura's theories has been used in recent research to assess the acceptability of new technologies.

2.6.9. Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

Model:

To build this theory, Venkatesh and colleagues(2003) combined eight (eight) distinct models, including the TRA (TAM), TRA (LUT), IDT (IDT), TTF (TPB), SCT (SCT), and MPCU (MPCU). New technology adoption and use are moderated by four moderators (gender, age, experience, and willingness to use) impacted by four components of the theory: PE, EE; SI; and FC. PE, EE; SI; and FC each have four components.

2.6.10. Technology Task Fit:

The TTF model was developed by Goodhue and Thompson (1995) and claims that new systems that address fundamental demands increase a person's performance. It can help you figure out whether people will use new technology in their jobs better if you look at three factors: how well they use their abilities, how well the technology works, and how well the job needs it.

2.6.11. Lazy User Theory (LUT):

Tetard & Collan (2009) provided a framework for interpreting a user's selection of given services/products. People pick the technology that meets their needs and are easy to use; this strategy is based on these two factors.

Figure 2.6.: TAM and other Technology acceptance Models source Author

2.6.12. Technology Acceptance Model:

As previously stated, there are a variety of technology acceptance models that can be used to explain and predict customer acceptance of new technology; however, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) has proven to be the most powerful and widely used framework for understanding and predicting customer acceptance of new technology in recent years. As perceptions of online technologies in the United Kingdom.

As seen in the image above, the TAM framework is an extension of the TRA framework. It postulates that users' desire to accept new technology is governed by their behavioural intention, which is impacted by their attitude toward adopting that technology. Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use are the two key beliefs that influence the user's attitude. It is the perception of a user that employing a certain technology or strategy would result in enhanced work performance that is referred to as perceived usefulness. In basic words, perceived utility refers to the ease with which a proposed technology may be adopted

and used. Although PU was first applied to organisational settings, it was subsequently expanded to include other typical activities and non-organizational situations. On the other hand, perceived ease of use (PEU) refers to the user's impression of how simple and painless it is to acquire and utilise a prospective technology.

PU and PEU are the primary criteria that have a direct effect on the user's decision to accept or reject new technology. Davis (1989) also posits a connection between PU and PEU (For instance, even if a new technology is useful, users will not adopt it if it is complicated to understand). According to Davis (1989), the PU and PEU are the two most critical factors of user adoption of technology in the TAM model. These two variables are impacted by a variety of external factors, including the system's design, service quality, training, documentation, and other technology-related support mechanisms (Davis, 1989).

The TAM model has been used in a broad range of studies examining user acceptability of technology (Rauniar et al., 2015; Sharif Abbasi et al., 2012; Abbasi et al., 2014). TAM was first created in 1989 to assess workers' attitudes regarding word processor technology. TAM has now been expanded to describe and forecast user behaviour in a variety of technological situations, including e-mail, graphics software, voice messaging, personal computer (Igarria and Livari, 1995), internet (Gefen and Straub, 2000), internet banking (Yousafzai, 2007), and online shopping. Davis (1989) examined TRA, TPB, and TAM while assessing user behaviour toward word processing application adoption. The results indicated that TAM was more effective in explaining user behaviour than TRA and TPB. TAM was shown to be capable of explaining up to 51% of the variation in behavioural intention. To summarise these findings: PU was a significant predictor of students' intention to utilise personal computers.

The study's objective was to ascertain workers' attitudes on utilising their company's intranet e-mail system. The research revealed that the TAM model was quite beneficial for forecasting user behaviour in USA and Switzerland, but not in Japan. Additionally, Gentry and Calantone analysed the TRA, TPB, and TAM to forecast user attitudes regarding web technology. All three models were shown to be useful; however, the TAM was found to be superior and stronger in explaining variation in behavioural intention. Burton and Hubona (2006) performed second research to anticipate and explain how individuals behave when it comes to online bidding. He examined the TPB and TAM models and found that both were successful at explaining variation in behavioural intentions to bid online ranging from 84 to 87 per cent; however, the TAM framework was more parsimonious than the TPB framework. Additionally, the researchers discovered that PU and PEU are the most significant elements of a user's desire to bid online.

The TAM model is said to be the most effective and widely used model of technological adoption for three primary reasons: (1) It is economical and IT-specific, having been developed expressly for the examination and forecasting of user attitudes about a broad variety of computer technology and information systems. According to Venkatesh (2000), during the last decade, TAM has shown to be the most potent and stable model of technological adoption. (2) It is based on a strong theoretical foundation that has been experimentally confirmed and validated by a large number of writers and researchers over the last two decades (3) It has exceptional explanatory power in comparison to other frameworks and models of technology adoption.

TAM was developed in the United States and has been extensively utilised and tested in a variety of contexts and nations throughout time. Philips et al. performed the first TAM investigation undertaken outside the United States (1994). He used and evaluated the TAM model in China and discovered that culture may significantly affect TAM's predictive ability. The TAM determinants (PU and PEU) will exhibit variable responses across nations and cultures. The following table summarises the number of TAM studies conducted by country categorization. The data was taken from a 2006 article and maybe regarded out of current; nonetheless, it offers an overview of TAM research done outside the United States.

The TAM model has been used to assist researchers and organisations in a variety of end-user technologies and information systems, including office applications, communication technologies, online applications, business-to-business services, and financial software, among others.

2.6.12.1. The Role of Attitude in TAM

As previously mentioned, users' behavioural intentions are intimately related to their attitude toward the system (Davis, 1989). In the original TAM model, the attitude was regarded to be the most important predictor of user adoption of technology. However, as additional research on TAM was undertaken, it was suggested that the attitude construct is unnecessary, and that the TAM's explanatory power stays unchanged in the absence of the mediating attitude aspect. Numerous studies on the TAM reveal that although the attitude construct, like many other behavioural factors, is important for predicting user adoption of technology, it is not sufficient. The attitude construct is said to be ineffective in the TAM model for these three primary reasons. To begin, perceived usefulness immediately influences behavioural intention to utilise technology, negating the necessity for an attitude construct. Second, a tenuous direct relationship exists between PEU and attitude. Third, TAM is self-contained. According to Davis (1989), when the TAM model is used to technologies that include additional elements such as PU and PEU, the attitude construct does not perform well as a predictor of intents. Numerous research has examined the TAM model in the absence of the attitude construct, and the model's predictive value remains robust (Yousafzai, 2007; Chaung, 2008; Gumussoy & Calisir, 2009 and Al-Mohammad, 2014). Taylor and Todd (1995) assert that in settings where technology performance is critical, intentions to utilise the technology are established based on performance concerns rather than user attitude. Several other scholars, however, argue that attitude is the primary mediator of behavioural intentions, which filter information and influence an individual's view of technology. Additionally, it is said that the attitude construct is excluded from the TAM model without enough theoretical foundation. Davis (1989) asserts that an individual's choice to adopt new technology is influenced by his or her PU and PEU and behavioural intents, with attitude

Several other scholars, however, argue that attitude is the primary mediator of behavioural intentions, which filter information and influence an individual's view of technology. Additionally, it is said that the attitude construct is excluded from the TAM model without enough theoretical foundation. Davis (1989) asserts that an individual's choice to adopt new technology is influenced by his or her PU and PEU and behavioural intents, with attitude serving as the best partial mediator.

2.6.12.2. Importance of PU and PEU in the TAM

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) proposes that two major determinants influence a user's intention to accept or reject new technology: (1) perceived usefulness (PU), which is defined as the degree to which a user believes that implementing a particular technology or technique will result in improved job performance, and (2) perceived ease of use (PEU), which is defined as the degree to which a user believes that implementing a particular technology or technique will result in improved job performance. However, research has shown that PU is a more essential component in technology adoption than PEU as the key determinant. In other words, PU is more important than PEU in terms of influencing consumers' choices about which technologies to embrace. According to Davis (1989), even if a system needs some effort but is beneficial to the intended user, adoption will be inhibited.

David (1989) discovered that perceived usefulness was more strongly and directly connected to how these systems were used in two trials involving 152 users and four applications. He continued by stating that although individuals are willing to make an effort to utilise technology that would enhance their work performance, even the simplest application will not be embraced if it does not provide helpful benefits to the prospective user. The majority of research has not shown a causal relationship between PEU and technology use. According to some authors, the PEU is a stepchild's determinant of the TAM.

However, the function of PEU in the technological adoption paradigm is hotly debated. Fareed and Mustafa (2002) and Al-Mohammad (2007) assert that PEU has a stronger, more direct, and comparable influence on technology adoption than PU. Similarly, unlike Davis (1989), Lim and Ting (2012) assert that there is a direct relationship between PEU and behavioural intention. Several studies have even shown a negative correlation between PU and the adoption of new technologies (Teo, et al, 2004).

Additionally, the findings of Aulamie's (2013) research indicate that PEU has a favourable effect on users' willingness to embrace new technologies. He discovered that users who participated in various training programmes said that PEU had a greater impact on their intention than PU. On the other hand, Igarria and Livari (1995) conducted a TAM experiment in Finland and discovered that PU alone is insufficient to alter people's behaviour. Additionally, researchers have advocated for the relevance of PU and PEU to be determined by experience, gender (Venkatesh and Morris, 2000), and task type (Moon and Kim, 2001). In conclusion, research indicates that the roles of PU and PEU vary according to technology kind, user demographic, and historical period. As a result, it is determined that the TAM literature has failed to adequately explain these contradictions.

Davis, (1986) examined technological adoption using 'real usage' as the dependent variable in the original TAM. However, more research on TAM reveals that the ultimate dependent variable, as opposed to actual usage, is 'behavioural intention.' After a thorough examination of TAM and consideration of the study's objectives, the researcher intends to utilise 'behavioural intention' as the dependent variable for two reasons. To begin, prior research indicates that users' actual behaviour is directly impacted by their behavioural intention (Davis, 1989; Khan Jan 2002). Second, the current research intends to examine customers' attitudes on internet banking in the United Kingdom. As a result, the researcher argues that using behavioural intention as the final dependent variable is both theoretically justified and pertinent to this investigation.

2.6.12.3. External Variables in the TAM

As previously mentioned, the TAM postulates that there are two primary predictors of intention: PU and PEU. The TAM, on the other hand, does not explain how perceptions (PU and PEU) are produced or how they might be changed to boost consumers' adoption of technology (Mathieson, 1991). The researchers discovered several potential predictors of perceived utility and ease of use when it comes to technology use. In other words, a variety of external circumstances have the potential to have a direct effect on PU and PEU. Venkatesh (2000), for example, performed three experiments in three distinct situations and discovered that control, intrinsic drive, and emotion all had a role in creating perceived ease of use. Stern et al. (2008), on the other hand, examined the antecedents of PU and PEU in the setting of an online auction system. The research discovered that computer affinity and risk tolerance had a substantial effect on PU and PEU.

Davis et al. (1992) contributed the first external variable to the TAM, which was output quality. Since then, the researchers have found several other external factors for PU and PEU. External factors were classified into four categories: organisational, system, user personal characteristics, and others.

2.6.12.4. Extension of Technology Acceptance Model (ETAM)

Davis's (1986) Technology Acceptance Model has been updated and expanded in several ways, with over 700 citations from various writers. Venkatesh and Davis (2000) suggested the first expansion to the TAM to explore the elements that impact a user's perception of the usefulness of the system. Consequently, they identified subjective norm, output quality, outcome demonstrability, image, and job relevance as the five main factors or drivers of perceived usefulness. The TAM 2 model was given this designation. The expanded model was shown to be more helpful, explaining between 40% and 60% of the variation in user judgments of usefulness. Venkatesh and Bala (2008) offered a second significant expansion to explore the determinants of perceived ease of use. The model was designated as the TAM 3. According to Venkatesh et al. (2003), the TAM's predictive potential was greatly enhanced once moderating factors were included. The figures below depict the TAM 2 and TAM 3 models:

Figure 2.6. 4.: TAM 2. Source: Author

Figure 2.6.5.: TAM 3. Source: Author

Apart from the TAM 2 and TAM 3, academics have developed several different extensions to the technology acceptance model. Gumussoy and Calisir (2009), for example, combined the TPB and IDT with the TAM to increase its predictive potential. The model was used to determine the characteristics that influence a customer's decision to utilise an auction in a business. The research discovered that when subjective norm, perceived behavioural control and perceived behavioural control were combined, they explained 76 per cent of the variation in workers' intention to use auctions. Similarly, Lee (2009) explained people's continuous usage of e-learning services by combining the TAM, TPB, and ECM models. The research discovered that these three models had more predictive and explanatory power than TAM alone. Gefeen et al. (2003) expanded the TAM by including the belief component of user adoption of electronic commerce. The study's objective was to determine the importance of the notion of trust to the client in the e-vendor sector.

The findings indicated that recurring customers had a higher level of confidence in the e-vendor than prospective customers, owing to the website's perceived usefulness website's ease of use. Additionally, Pikkarainen et al. (2004) indicated that although the TAM model is beneficial, other factors such as privacy and security, in addition to PU and PVC, are necessary to completely explain the adoption behaviour of online banking services. After combining the IDT and TAM models, Lei et al. (2005) concluded that the combined models had more predictive and explanatory power when it came to explaining consumer use of electronic banking in the United States of America. Most notably, academics have linked the problem of trust to TAM when it comes to online banking service uptake. Additionally, the researchers assert that consumer confidence in the services offered has a beneficial effect on their attitudes regarding online banking and other relevant distribution channels.

Additionally, research done by Lewis et al. (2010) indicates that compatibility, risk, and perceived utility all play a role in determining a user's inclination to use mobile banking. Ozdemir, Hoecht, and Trott (2008) examine the adoption of online banking in Turkey. The survey found that internet banking adopters saw the channel as beneficial, simple to use, and less hazardous than those who do not utilise the service. Yiu, Grant, and Edgar (2007) examined the relationship between PU and PVC and personal effectiveness and discovered that these factors significantly influence customer behavioural intentions toward online banking. On the other hand, Wessels and Drenman (2010) discovered that consumer adoption of mobile banking in Australia is influenced by PU, perceived risk, compatibility, and cost.

2.6.12.5. Extended TAM to Account for value creation:

Modern technology provides a platform for knowledge generation and sharing that is easily available via new marketing channels like smartphones and tablets, opening the door to value creation opportunities through consumer contact activities (Brode, 2011, Alexander, 2014).

There is a value creation component related to the increase of TAM, which is linked with the adoption of new technologies (Malhotra & Galletta, 1999). This aspect of the enlarged model proposes that the platform creates value via dynamic capabilities that have an effect on processes that influence behavioural intentions and attitudes toward technology, as well as user acceptance behaviour. The tactics of social influence developed by Kelman are included in this development of TAM (Malhotra & Galletta, 1999).

The major source of customer value generation is via the use of dynamic capabilities. They are "higher-level abilities that describe the platform's capacity to integrate, create, and reconfigure internal and external resources/competencies to meet, and perhaps influence, rapidly changing business environments," according to the White Paper (Teece, 2012, p. 1395). These characteristics may be crucial in a user's journey through digital transformation. Teece, Pisano, and Shuen (1997) defined a dynamic capability as a firm's ability to adapt to rapidly changing circumstances; as a result, the usage (and utility) of dynamic capabilities is stronger in lively contexts, such as those impacted by digital technology. Teece, Pisano, and Shuen (1997) defined a dynamic capability as a firm's ability to adapt to rapidly changing circumstances. Following the conceptualizations of Teece et al. (1997) and Teece (2007), according to Pavlov and El Sawwy (2011), the dynamic capabilities necessary for the reconfiguration process may be divided into four clusters of activities.

Sensing new opportunities and threats:

Identify, develop, cooperate on, and analyse technical trends and opportunities in connection to client needs. Customer value may be created by having the capacity to discover, analyse, and pursue digital technologies (for example, infrastructure, content, channels, services, and e-business applications) and then implementing such technologies. Using digital technology, which is an essential feature of sensing capabilities, marketers may more easily gather key marketing intelligence data. Businesses may have a full understanding of their customers'

motives and generate customer value that is unique to each customer by detecting and studying the consumer's new surroundings (Goerzig & Bauernhansl, 2018).

Seizing new opportunities:

Renewal of current skills by the application of fresh knowledge. Once an opportunity has been recognised, an organisation must reallocate and refocus existing resources while mobilising new ones via learning activities focused on problem-solving and knowledge creation. Consider the fact that a broad range of new competencies is required to aid the business in dealing with the problems of digitalization, and that learning processes are beneficial for responding to customer requests and capturing the new opportunities for value capture that arise because of digital transformation. The decoupling and disintermediation of present value chains have been encouraged by digitalization, according to Warner and Wager (2019).

Integrating & Coordinating:

New information is assimilated "into a collective system capable of launching new operational capability configurations," as the phrase goes (Pavvlou & El Sawy, 2011). A business unit's knowledge must be communicated across the organisation because the bulk of redeployed and fresh information is held by individuals and that skills are shared between them.

It is possible to build new shared capabilities by coordinating and deploying various tasks, resources and activities via the use of "orchestration" of coordinating assets. Structures, strategies, and processes are all used in the reconfiguration of capabilities. Strategic transformation cannot be realised to its full potential without the presence of such transformative abilities (Teace & Lindan, 2017). Leadership, in our perspective, develops dedication, and creative techniques of resource allocation are a result of the firm's ability to coordinate its resources and activities. The integration of the four dimensions and the differentiation of dynamic capabilities for customers are the domains of any company's strategy.

Involvement in new technology use adds to the psychological connection that users have with the device. Internalisation, identification, and compliance of the user are all affected by these procedures. As a result, this component of value generation has an impact on both behavioural intentions for real use and attitudes about actual usage.

2.7. The rationale for choosing TAM as a research model:

Technology Acceptability and Utilization Measures (TAM) performs research on the acceptance and usage of technology at a personal and individual level. A range of concepts and disciplines, including user participation and psychological theories such as the theory of planned behaviour, TAM, user satisfaction, and human-computer interaction have been explored in the past, as has the relationship between users and computers.

The nature of our study necessitates that the model we use be capable of predicting user intention while also being extendable enough to include aspects from rival hypotheses. A key reason for selecting TAM was that it is capable of discerning the precise relationship between consumers' perceptions of and benefits derived from the use of digital platform technologies. Consumers' perceptions of technology are improved as a result of a better knowledge of the external variables whose causal links influence their perceptions of technology (Wang 2004). In addition, as compared to other models, TAM is fairly simple to apply (Davis, 1999). The effectiveness of TAM has also been shown in several other studies and across a wide range of technology contexts. A prior version of this technique was used to analyse users' intentions for word processing programmes such as WordPerfect and Lotus 1-2-3 (Adams 2000), internet applications such as remote patient monitoring technologies (Chau & Hu, 2002), and consumer electronic commerce websites (Adams et al., 2002). (2010). (Ha and Stoel, 2009). Furthermore, it has been used in a range of fields, including manufacturing, financial services, healthcare, and education.

2.8. TAM Validation:

The literature analysis shows that multiple successful TAM studies and forecasts of user adoption of new technology and applications have been made, and this is confirmed by the outcomes of this research. The author (Davis, 1989) describes the process of creating a synthesis of two or more sources of information. (2013); (Liu and colleagues, 2013): In 1989, Davis and colleagues utilised TAM to analyse user behaviour in universities, and they discovered that the model was predictive of the behaviour seen there. Additional applications include the industries of industry, finance, healthcare, and education, among other fields. In addition to serving as a well-established model for understanding information technology adoption behaviour, it serves as a framework for investigating the impact of external influences on people's intentions to use IT (Darsono & Mada, 2007). Davis's original TAM, on the other hand, has been updated by several studies to incorporate other important aspects. As will be discussed later in this chapter, this was done to get around some of the flaws of TAM.

2.9. Technology Acceptance Model Limitations:

Even though TAM has been effective in predicting consumers' attitudes about new technologies, others argue it has its limitations. There are many issues with the model, the first being that it is very simple, which restricts its capacity to quantify intentions. A total of just two factors are capable of accurately capturing a person's behavioural purpose. The simplicity of TAM, on the other hand, is considered a strength by the vast majority of researchers. Additionally, saw it as a limitation since current use cannot be utilised to predict future or sustained usage in the same manner. May (2001) hypothesised that short-term consumption may be used to anticipate future consumption (May 2001). In 1997, Straub and colleagues assessed TAM in three different countries: Japan, Switzerland, and the United States of America. A variety of results were discovered throughout their inquiry, including success in the United States of America and Switzerland, but failure in the Japanese market. This might be seen as evidence that TAM is not effective in all cultures. However, in their observations of TAM in different cultures, (Khalifa & Cheng, 2002) did not find this to be

true. The following section is a comparison of the most important models of technology adoption today.

2.10. COMPARISON OF MAJOR TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODELS

According to the findings of the study, significant similarities exist in the idea of one's perceptions in choosing IT/IS acceptance and use, notably in the models of TRA, TAM, DTPB, C-TAM-TPB, and UTAUT (Traditional and Technological Acceptance and Usage). TAM is simple to use and may be tailored to a range of different study environments (Davis 1999). TAM is more comprehensive than TRA and TPD (Han, 2004). Mathieson and colleagues (2002) performed a comparison between TAM and TPD and came to the conclusion that TAM sufficiently provides for the concept of purpose. When compared to TPB, which examines and exhibits the reasons why technology may not be adopted, TAM offers a safe method of obtaining information on an individual's attitude toward technology. It is more effective than TAM when it comes to applying theories because it not only recognises particular decisions that may affect how information technology is utilised, like TAM does, but it also incorporates extra subjective norms and PBC, which TAM does not (Ajzen & Breown, 1991). The inclusion of seven new variables into TAM boosted the predictive power of behavioural intent by 2 per cent, according to the DTPB study.

TAM, on the other hand, beats DTPB when it comes to anticipating information technology consumption. The use of TAM is beneficial in system design efforts. It is important to note that the DTPB theory considers design efforts as well as the distinction between control and standard efforts. TAM, TPD, and DTPB are evaluated by Chau and Hu (2001) to gain a better understanding of personal doctors' use of telemedicine technology." Their findings indicate that TAM justified 45% of the variation in physicians' use of the technology, whereas TPB interpreted 30% and DTPB interpreted 25% of the variation. The TAM and DTPB theories found that PU was connected with attitude and BI; however, PEOU found that it did not influence either PU or attitude in any of the three models. Therefore, approaches developed for longitudinal research involving customers and managers in corporate settings may be unsuitable for examining persons working in a professional context, such as doctors. Specifically, Bagozzi (1992) claims that when all statistical analysis and interpretation techniques are equivalent, the best acceptance and use model is the most straightforward to

implement. According to some authors, compactness is not required, but rather desirable in terms of easing the mastery of a phenomenon, rather than a requirement (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Users' intentions to utilise a system varied from 17 per cent to 37 per cent depending on the eight sample models analysed by (Ibid.) The variance as assessed by TAM2 was included, as was the initial gender of the participants. TAM has a greater range of applications than TPB and TRA. (Davis and colleagues.) Researchers observed that it performed much better than the Theory of Reasoned Action in predicting software usage intention. TAM was shown to be a more accurate predictor of intention to use spreadsheet software than TRA in predicting intention to use spreadsheet software. (2000) Venketash and Daves (Venketash & Daves) It was emphasised that using TAM to predict consumer acceptance of new technology is a dependable and cost-effective strategy for predicting consumer adoption.

It was discussed in this chapter how research on technology adoption has progressed and the relevance of the independent variables, as well as numerous theoretical assumptions about customer demographics and acceptable acceptance behaviour. Also included were models of behaviour theory with a focus on consumer behaviour as well as numerous models of consumer behaviour, which were emphasised.

Being that this research will employ TAM to analyse the acceptance and use of new technology, it will incorporate components from TAM2, the Theory of Planned Behavior, and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), in addition to those from the field of electronic commerce (E-commerce).

3. CHAPTER 3

Research Framework and Hypothesis Development

The next sections define the model's variables, beginning with the independent (external) variables and progressing through the intermediate and dependent variables, system utilisation. All variables will be discussed using evidence from the literature and their relationships to one another and the base TAM will be demonstrated. While one may anticipate certain factors to be more significant than others, this model assumes they are all equally weighted.

3.1. Intention to use

Specifically, according to Venkateesh and Daves (2000), the major dependent variable is the intention to use, which may be defined as a person's likelihood of using information technology in the future. In well-established user acceptability studies, the intention to use is a crucial element in user acceptance (Daves 1989; Taylor and Toodd, 1995; Venkateesh and Daves, 2000). However, there is little information accessible on the intention to use digital media to achieve this goal. In the study's outcome variable, it is stated that a consumer's ultimate adoption of online business platforms is mostly controlled by their willingness to utilise them. The goal of this study is to get a better knowledge of use as a dependent variable, as well as the role of intention as a predictor of behaviour, namely actual use.

3.2. Attitude towards the use

Attitude refers to several detectable behavioural thoughts that may be seen (Carter and Yeo, 2017). Many studies have found that people who are more likely to use technology are more likely to have a positive attitude about it (Daves, 1993). There has been a plethora of research that have shown positive relationships between one's attitude about technology use and one's proclivity to use it (Daves, 1993). TAM was created to anticipate information system utilisation; however, the variable attitude toward technology use may be utilised to gauge client acceptance. Because of the adaptability of the attitude toward using an information

system, this research employs a structure similar to that of the original research framework and expands it to include the investigation of digital platforms. Consequently, it is proposed that an individual's attitude toward digital platforms is a significant mediator of their motivation to make use of these platforms: "

H1: There is a correlation between Attitudes regarding digital platforms and the intention to use them.

3.3. Perceived usefulness

Technology is seen as useful by consumers depending on their assessments of the system's perceived usefulness (Davis 1999). A person's perceived usefulness is described as "the extent to which a person believes that a certain system will aid them in doing a specific task" (Bruner and Kumar, 2004). For users to participate with the system, they must think that online digital platforms are advantageous for their requirements. The choice to participate in transactions is based on a fair and deliberate assessment of the benefits connected with the services in consideration of their costs (Gao et al., 2012). Perceived usefulness was shown to be a strong predictor of user acceptance in prior TAM analyses conducted in consumer adoption situations. Earlier platform studies incorporated perceived usefulness in their research components as well as other components of the investigation (Anthony and Mutalemwa, 2014). Specifically, the researchers think that the perceived usefulness of digital platforms for doing business and collecting information has a direct influence on their attitude toward digital platforms to preserve consistency with their past results. The researcher argues that perceived usefulness is a crucial determinant of an individual's attitude toward using digital platforms as a consequence.

H2: There is a correlation between Perceived usefulness and the attitudes toward the adoption of digital platforms.

3.4. Perceived Value Creation:

Organizations may create and extract value from innovation, according to Teece (2018), by building ecosystems and generating applicable business models. Additionally, Teece (2018)

asserts that complementary asset providers, following the original PFI model, may be able to extract considerable value from the PFI transaction. To be clear, Teece(2018) doesn't explain why platform executives need dynamic skills, what kinds of dynamic capabilities they should have, or how they may develop and capture value with dynamic capabilities. The following paper builds on Teece (2018) by providing an investigation into how dynamic abilities are essential for platform leaders to generate and capture value, with a specific focus on digital platform-based ecosystems. Because of this, the following hypothesis has been advanced:

H3: There is a correlation between Perceived value creation and the attitude toward the adaption of digital platforms.

3.5. System characteristics

When we speak of "system characteristics," we are referring to a collection of external factors that can impact a consumer's choice to adopt new technology (Davis, 1989). Several researchers, including Davis (1993) and Venkatesh (2000), have hypothesised that the objective design qualities of a system have a direct effect on perceived usefulness and perceived value creation. In previous TAM studies, researchers found a strong link between system features and users' attitudes about and actual behaviour while using information services (Davis, 1993; Venkatesh & Davis, 1996).

Too far, however, there hasn't been any experimental confirmation of the premise about how different system properties influence platform acceptance. Therefore, this study will add to the knowledge of system characteristics for adaptability to online platforms as TAM external influences as a consequence of the findings. The following sections give in-depth explanations of the system's properties and functionality.

3.5.1. Mobility

The ability to move about is a crucial feature of information technology, especially in light of the trend toward a more mobile environment. When people talk about mobility, they're talking about the ability to take a mobile device with them almost everywhere they go that is

inside the service area of a mobile network, such as a phone, a tablet, or even a laptop (Mallat 2007; Au and Kauffmann, 2008).

When opposed to the Internet, which is considered "heavyweight," consumer devices are considered "lightweight" infrastructures (cf. [Bygstad 2017](#)). However, smartphones are powerful computational and networking devices that may function as infrastructures if they achieve a critical mass of users. Just think about how important smartphones and GPS technology are in allowing Uber's operations. Because of the ubiquitous availability of digital technology, the speed of digital innovation, which is being built on top of digital infrastructures, has been accelerated. Indeed, readily available internet infrastructure is essential for the establishment and expansion of new digital businesses. Digital infrastructures provide the necessary computer and networking resources, like how platforms connect supply and demand (Baldwin and Clark 2000; [Gawer 2014](#)). As a result, digital infrastructures distinguish themselves from other types of infrastructures in that they are [capable of gathering](#), storing, and making digital data available across a wide range of systems and devices, as opposed to older types of infrastructures.

Digital sources' perceived usefulness and perceived value production are positively correlated with their mobility, according to the study.

H4: There is a correlation between Mobility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H5: There is a correlation between Mobility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

3.5.2. Compatibility

With the addition of factor compatibility to the original TAM model, it is expected that consumer acceptance of digital platforms for online content would skyrocket in the coming years. How compatible an invention is with existing values, previous experiences, and needs is called "the degree to which an invention is seen as being compatible with the receivers' existing values, previous experiences, and needs" (1971, Rogers and Shoemaker). Tornatzky and Klein (1982) assert that client acceptance is impacted by the degree to which two

products are compatible. Agarwal (1997) observed that there is a significant association between compatibility and the usage of the internet. The vast bulk of existing research on digital platforms has been undertaken from the viewpoint of consumers, which is not uncommon (Kim et al., 2010; Schierz et al., 2010). Digital platforms, which are still in the early stages of development, are critical to the development of consumer-facing systems. Because of this, according to the researcher, the TAM framework must include compatibility as a mandatory feature. In the context of online activity, prior research discovered positive relationships between perceived usefulness and perceived value creation (Mallat and Dahlberg, 2005). The researcher hypothesises that compatibility has an indirect effect on consumers' willingness to utilise digital platforms via perceived usefulness and perceived value creation.

H6: There is a correlation between compatibility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H7: There is a correlation between compatibility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

3.5.3. Convenience

Convenience has been described as providing clients with time and location utilities and has been studied in the context of online transactions and digital platforms (Srinesavan et al., 2002). (Clark III, 2001). It is supplied "exclusively to simplify people's lives and ease the pain connected with unpleasant jobs and activities" that this technological benefit is made available to them (Obu and Balogun, 2007). Consumer acceptance and use of digital markets have been investigated in connection to customer behaviour for online services (Bhatnagar et al., 2000), and several studies have demonstrated that payment ease is a factor in consumer acceptability and usage of digital markets (; Chan, 2006; Mallt, 2007). Among the elements that influence the adoption of digital platform activities such as online shopping, online banking, online investing, and online services, according to Eastin (2002), perceived ease and financial benefits are important. In a similar vein, Lee(2009) found that consumers' willingness to use e-platforms and, as a consequence, their preferences for an online business are strongly influenced by their perceptions of the benefits of doing business online.

While Gerrard and Cunningham (2003) investigated the economic benefits of adopting e-platforms, such as low transaction costs, they could not find any evidence to support the perception of online platforms concerning economic gains in their study. Low fixed costs and transaction fees, on the other hand, are important to the popularity and profitability of e-payment systems, since the vast majority of online payments are processed via digital platforms (Lopez-Catalan, 2013). A recent study has demonstrated several advantages of e-platforms, including a rise in the amount of money transacted (Chakravorti, 2003). Convenience has been a driving factor behind digital platforms' attempts to provide simple, web-based interfaces for services since the introduction of digital wallets and online payments in the early 2000s (Ray 2006).

The definition and characteristics of convenience previously mentioned are that it is a combination of time and location utilities. Because consumers may transact at any time and from any place as long as they have access to the internet, these are features of digital platforms that customers should consider. Additionally, digital platforms are intended to make the lives of customers who wish to access digital information without having to pay a high membership fee more convenient and stress-free. The researcher hypothesises that convenience will have a positive impact on the perceived utility and perceived value creation of digital platforms for use in the digital marketplace, given the importance of supplying clients with advantageous digital platforms:

H8: There is a correlation between Convenience and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H9: There is a correlation between Convenience and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

3.6. Individual differences

The original TAM model does not create a link between individual reactions to technology usage and future objectives in terms of technology. This occurs as a result of a severe error in the initial notion, and it is critical in understanding TAM's limitations (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The ensuing gap encouraged information systems researchers to broaden the scope of the original TAM framework to incorporate information on how and why people adopt new technologies, hence boosting the explanatory power of the model's core connections. According to Lu et al. (2003), individual variances in consumer research have been connected to wireless internet use as well as buying behaviour (Shavitt, 1989). According to a recent study, there are two key factors in information systems and online services: innovativeness and knowledge management (Bhatti, 2007; Chen et al., 2000). None of these human attributes, on the other hand, have been examined on digital platforms that are specifically geared toward the digital industry. This weakness will be addressed by our study, which will broaden the scope of TAM to include these two different individual qualities to better our understanding of digital platforms.

3.6.1. Innovativeness

Personal innovativeness is defined as “the willingness of an individual to try out any new information technology” (Agarwal & Prasad, 1998, p. 206). Some studies have found that personal innovativeness has a direct impact on user acceptance of technologies. Yi, Fiedler, and Park (2006) compared two alternative models: a first model in which personal innovativeness is a moderator of the effects of innovation characteristics (usefulness, ease of use) on intention to use, and a second model in which personal innovativeness has a direct effect on innovation characteristics and on intention to use. Their results suggest that personal innovativeness has a direct impact on usefulness, ease of use and compatibility. Similarly, Kim and Forsythe (2010) showed that personal innovativeness has a direct effect on perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and perceived value creation in the context of a platform technology.

Roehrich (2004) identifies four factors that contribute to consumers' high innovativeness: a need for stimulation, a want for novelty, independence from others' transmitted experiences,

and a desire for originality. Another study discovered that an individual's innovativeness has a significant influence on their online purchase choice (Yi et al., 2006).

With regards to digital platforms, Bokai and Mohammadi (2010) used simulation and mathematical methodologies to analyse aspects impacting platform adoption through the spread of innovation. The two researchers discovered that the spread of innovativeness — as measured by decreased wait times and cheap transaction costs — promotes customers to adopt new digital platforms. Because the majority of people are unfamiliar with digital platforms in connection to online consumption, innovativeness will be critical in facilitating the adoption of new business technology. With digital platforms still in their infancy in the sector, it is reasonable to associate personal innovativeness favourably with perceived usage of digital platforms in the research. Thus, if inventiveness is a factor in determining the usage of digital platforms, the following statement is confirmed:

H10: There is a correlation between innovativeness and the perceived Value creation of digital platforms by consumers.

3.6.2. Knowledge of digital platforms

The researcher's goal is to discover if there is a relationship between knowledge of digital platforms and the desire to use them, which is a difficult question to answer given the paucity of study on the subject. Consumers who have a reasonable degree of knowledge about the internet business should find it easier to use services than those who do not have such knowledge. The act of looking for information on the internet has evolved into an ingrained habit in contemporary society. The web skill and understanding of Internet users who are comfortable looking for information on the internet allows them to speed the processing of information and discern between important and irrelevant material (Rieah, 2004). It is vital to understand how consumers who now use services — or who are hesitant to pay high costs for things — would be exposed as a consequence of the use of digital platforms by businesses (Mei, 2016). Due to the lack of research on the topic, this study attempts to assess the impact of knowledge on perceived value generation by users of digital platforms. As an attempt to demonstrate the importance of knowledge concerning digital platform utilisation, the following hypothesis is developed:

H11: There is a correlation between Knowledge and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

3.7. Conceptual model:

This section will discuss how the antecedents were determined via the literature study. Additionally, it visualises the conceptual model that was originally constructed as a foundation for exploratory study.

3.7.1. Derivation of original antecedents and moderating variable

It was Davis' (1985) Technology Adoption Model that served as the inspiration for this research, which sought to explain the antecedents of technology adoption and user behaviour when it came to computer technologies. When presented with new technology, the model hypothesises how customers might embrace and use an information system to their advantage. Venkatesh et al. (2003) and Venkatesh and Davis (2000) show that the desire to use an information system is the most important factor impacting the actual utilisation of the system. The intention to use has been regularly mentioned as a fundamental element in user acceptance studies (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). Predicted utility and perceived ease of use are two ideas that, according to the original TAM model, impact technology adoption behaviour: perceived utility and perceived ease of use (Davis, 1985).

Several recent studies on mobile and e-payments have shown that perceived utility and perceived ease of use are important indicators of customer acceptance and behaviour (Kim et al., 2010; Gao et al., 2012; Ming-Yen Teoh et al., 2013). An earlier study by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) indicated that parameters akin to perceived utility and perceived ease of use were connected with attitudes and intentions to utilise the product. Their study discovered a significant relationship between an individual's attitude toward a certain behaviour (for example, online buying) and their usage of information technology. They concluded that The attitude toward technology use, therefore, serves as a mediating factor between the two essential predictors of intention to use, namely, the attitude toward technology and the attitude toward technology usage. According to the findings of the study on mobile devices, consumers have a positive attitude toward the perceived usability of mobile marketing (Gao et al., 2012).

According to research conducted in the context of mobile commerce technology, perceived ease of use is an indirect influencer of consumer access to digital news information, article downloads from publishers, and website content related to current and previous news themes, among other things (Bruner and Kumar, 2005). Although the research found that the pleasure associated with using a mobile device was a key factor in shaping attitudes toward use, it did not find that the item's usefulness had any direct impact on behavioural intention. For this research, the outcomes of these trials support the use of attitude toward an information system as a combining construct, as was done in the previous studies.

The linkages highlighted before have helped us understand user adoption of information systems and technological behaviour. For this research of digital platforms, mobile payment studies provide a considerable collection of consumer-driven criteria. It is also intrinsically tied to the study of digital platforms, and understanding of these platforms is often advised to aid in the facilitation of electronic commerce via these platforms. Because of the facts presented above, the following hypothesis has been developed:

Hypothesis 1

H0: Attitudes regarding digital platforms will not have a positive impact on the intention to use them.

H1: Attitudes regarding digital platforms will have a positive impact on the intention to use them.

Hypothesis 2

H0: Perceived usefulness will not have a positive impact on people's attitudes toward the adoption of digital platforms.

H1: Perceived usefulness will have a positive impact on people's attitudes toward the adoption of digital platforms.

Hypothesis 3

H0: Perceived value creation will not have a beneficial influence on the attitude toward the adaption of digital platforms.

H1: Perceived value creation will have a beneficial influence on the attitude toward the adaption of digital platforms.

3.8. Derivation of external variables

While the TAM, as created with its original and moderating antecedents, serves as the starting point for this research, the researcher expanded the model with external factors affecting consumer perceptions gleaned from the examined literature. In a previous study, two groups of factors were shown to have a substantial correlation with the desire to utilise information services: system features and person variations, which function as external variables in the TAM model (Davis, 1993; Venkatesh and Davis, 1996; Venkatesh, 2000).

3.8.1. Derivation of system characteristics

Kim et al. (2010) hypothesised a connection between several system characteristics and mobile payment use. With the growth of mobile traffic for online news and the rising purchase of content online, digital platforms, particularly for mobile commerce, are gaining increasing relevance (Huang et al., 2016; Mitchell et al., 2016). However, no obvious correlation between various system features and the approach or attitude of digital platforms has been established experimentally. In a mobile payment setting, the three system features of mobility, compatibility, and convenience have been identified as external factors in consumer perceptions of the usage of digital platforms based on the literature research conducted for this study.

To begin, mobility, as a critical component of information technology owing to its inherent pervasive nature, showed a strong correlation with perceived ease of use for early adopters in prior mobile payment research by Kim et al (2010). Schierz et al. (2010) established a link between an individual's mobility features and mobile payments, whereas Eisenmann et al. (2006) and Pousttchi (2008) propose digital platforms as case studies in this regard. As a result, the researcher came up with the following theories:

Hypothesis 4

H0: There is no correlation between Mobility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Mobility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 5

H0: There is no correlation between Mobility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Mobility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

Second, compatibility as a factor influencing consumers' perceptions of an innovative technology's consistency (Rogers and Shoemaker, 1971) is a critical predictor of consumer acceptability (Tornatzky and Klein, 1982). Agarwal and Prasad (1997) established a clear correlation between compatibility and internet usage. Mallat and Dahlberg (2005) hypothesised a link between compatibility and both perceived value creation and perceived utility in a mobile activity setting in their article regarding success determinants for e-business. Digital platforms are regarded to be a critical factor of innovation since they are expected to drive consumer adoption of online platform content (BCG, 2009; Time, 2009; Evangelista, 2010; Graybeal and Hayes, 2011; Salomon, 2012). As a result, compatibility is expected to have a favourable influence on consumers' views and attitudes regarding digital platforms, as well as their desire to utilise them:

Hypothesis 6

H0: There is no correlation between compatibility and the perceived utility of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between compatibility and the perceived utility of digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 7

H0: There is no correlation between compatibility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between compatibility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

Thirdly, convenience as a feature that benefits customers' time and location utilities (Clarke III, 2001) is a significant driver of consumer behaviour for online services (Bhatnagar et al., 2000) and mobile payments (Chou et al., 2004; Dewan and Chen, 2005; Chen, 2006; Mallat, 2007). Convenience has been identified as a critical aspect in determining the utility of platforms for late adopters (Kim et al., 2010). Additionally, research indicates that digital platforms are designed to give users easy, web-based interfaces (Roy et al., 2006), implying that this research study should demonstrate a positive correlation between perceived value creation and perceived usefulness for online platforms:

Hypothesis 8

H0: There is no correlation between Convenience and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Convenience and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 9

H0: There is no correlation between Convenience and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Convenience and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

3.8.2. Derivation of individual characteristics

Individual differences, the second major category of external factors, enhance the TAM model by including how and why people embrace new technology. Previously conducted consumer behavioural research on personal traits was mostly concerned with information systems (Agarwal and Prasad, 1999; Sun and Zhang, 2006; Bagozzi, 2007) and information technology (Igarria et al., 1997). Mobile payment studies have shown a favourable correlation between personal characteristics, attitudes toward mobile marketing, and the desire to utilise mobile payment (Kim et al., 2010; Gao et al., 2012). Two distinct aspects were isolated from the previously examined literature, neither of which had been previously investigated in the context of the digital platform.

To begin, innovativeness, defined as a customer's receptiveness to novel ideas (Midgley and Downing, 1978), has been a critical factor in consumer acceptance study (Roehrich, 2004) and online purchase choices (Yi et al., 2006). As Agarwal and Prasad demonstrate, innovativeness is a direct consequence of perceived utility (1998). Bokaj and Mohammadi (2010) found a link between the dissemination of innovativeness — as measured by reduced wait times and cheap transaction costs — and the use of digital platforms. Kim et al. (2010) observed that consumers with highly inventive features considered digital platforms to be simple to use via a test sample of late adopters. Given the unique nature of platforms in terms of online consumption, the following proposal is suitable:

Hypothesis 10

H0: There is no correlation between the innovativeness of digital platforms and their perceived utility.

H1: There is a correlation between the innovativeness of digital platforms and their perceived utility.

Second, only a few research have examined knowledge of digital platforms in the context of customer behaviour. For instance, Kim et al. (2010) discovered that mobile payment customers with strong platform expertise quickly acclimated to mobile payment services. Given the rise in consumer internet usage as a result of consumers seeking information online and using their expertise to enhance information processing (Rieh, 2004; Mai, 2016), it is projected that customers familiar with digital platforms will have no issue utilising them. To substantiate the positive association between perceived value generation by digital platforms and its perceived value, the following hypothesis is advanced:

Hypothesis 11

H0: There is no correlation between Knowledge and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Knowledge and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

3.9. Conceptual model

Figure 4.1.: Source: Author

3.10. Additional Hypothesis:

Due to the novelty of platforms research, particularly in terms of user acceptability of online digital platforms in the United Kingdom, the researcher seeks to uncover new external factors that complement the basic conceptual model. The researcher operationalized additional hypotheses based on the study goal addressing two consumer perceptions on their attitude and intention toward platform use. These additional external factors may be system- or individual-level features. As such, they may be regarded both independent factors impacting platform use intention and dependent variables on the original antecedent variables of perceived utility and perceived value generation. As a result, the following theories are advanced:

Additional Hypotheses 12-n

H0: There is no correlation between external variables describing system features and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between external variables describing system features and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H0: There is no correlation between external variables describing system features and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between external variables describing system features and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H0: There is no correlation between external variables describing individual features and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between external variables describing individual features and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H0: There is no correlation between external variables describing individual features and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between external variables describing individual features and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

Figure 3.2.: Summary: Source Author

Taking everything into consideration, this research indicated that there is a knowledge gap when it comes to consumer approval requirements for the use of digital platforms in general. The purpose of this research was to fill in the gaps by examining the elements that determine how digital platforms are utilised in practice. Past research has investigated the adoption characteristics that impact consumer use of new technologies in related subject domains, with the theoretical TAM model serving as a framework for the investigation. Several parallel research was conducted to examine the influence of external factors, antecedent variables, and a moderating variable on the willingness to make use of information systems, digital platforms, and mobile payment systems.

When the researcher started the study, he conducted a review of relevant literature in similar issue areas, finding both direct and indirect causes of the desire to use a new technological advancement. This led to the identification of a set of variables that influence user acceptance and use of new technology. These variables included mobility (including compatibility and convenience), innovativeness (including perceived ease of use and knowledge), two antecedent variables, perceived usefulness and perceived value creation, and one moderating variable attitude toward the intention to use new technology. Relationships between these aspects have also been explored in contemporary research on information systems, information technology, payment studies, and online platforms. These determinants, as well as their causal roles, were merged to provide the foundation for the first conceptual model developed in this study. Based on these connections within the structure, the researcher operationalized hypotheses and fitted them specifically to the use of digital platforms, among other things. According to the researchers, the goal of this study was to test operationalized hypotheses concerning digital platforms in the context of user perception in the United Kingdom.

To make the initial conceptual model easier to comprehend, the researcher categorised the factors and related outcomes into four categories, one of which was the use of digital platforms. External factors, antecedent factors, moderating factors, and implications for the previous category are the four categories to which we might refer. Using the example of innovativeness, we can see how the structure works: past consumer behavioural research on personal attributes (category 1) had a strong emphasis on information systems (Bagozzi, 2007). (Igbaria and colleagues, 1999). According to research on mobile payment services, there is a positive association between perceived personal traits (category2), attitudes toward

mobile marketing (category3), and the willingness to use mobile payment services (category 4). (Gao and colleagues, 2012). This procedure was used to build the related connections and diverging hypotheses for each variable in the original conceptual framework, just as it was used to create the innovativeness variable in the preceding example.

At the time of the initial conceptual model, there were a total of 11 operationalized hypotheses, eight of which were classified as external variables and antecedent variables, two of which were classified as antecedent variables and moderating variables, and one which was classified as moderating variables and implication factor, and one which was classified as antecedent variables and implication factor. Because the market relies on digital channels, this conceptual approach is crucial. At this time, there is no such conceptual model available. Furthermore, it demonstrates how a complex set of circumstances affects the concept.

This study's data was gathered and analysed utilising a mixed-methods technique that included both qualitative and quantitative procedures, according to the researcher. The research was divided into two parts, with each phase including the use of different techniques. The initial stage was to conduct qualitative interviews with companies to identify any new factors that could influence consumer use of digital platforms for online platforms in the future. To get in-depth and rich information regarding the research subject while also allowing for the emergence of extra phenomena, a unique technique using semi-structured interviews with open questions was adopted. By adding these newly found qualities into the study construct, the researcher was able to make improvements to the original conceptual model that had been developed. Because of the additional factors, the conceptual model has been enhanced, allowing for a better understanding of the main perception characteristics impacting the usage of digital platforms, which will benefit companies in the formulation and implementation of their strategies and procedures. The detailed conceptual model that resulted from this process — termed the Alpha model — served as the basis for the subsequent research phase.

Second, the complete set of parameters was empirically tested using a large quantitative online poll of platform users, which served as the second phase. The (SPSS) analytical technique was utilised in the original study, which has grown in popularity as the dominant multivariate analysis tool in strategic marketing research (Halland, 1999). Because of its methodological benefits, which allow researchers to model interactions with unprecedented

flexibility, according to Anderson and Swaminathan (2011), this analytic methodology is particularly well-suited for use in research on electronic markets (such as digital platforms) (Hair et al., 2013). According to Teo et al., the statistical package SPSS was utilised to examine causal relationships in consumer adoption factors for digital platforms (2015). Given the novelty of digital platforms and the concurrent perspectives on mobile payments, the purpose of this thesis is to use variance-based structural equation modelling to causal links in the UK. The present study thus extends beyond the usual covariance-based SEM (CBS-SEM), which is compatible with Reinartz's findings (2009). However, Hair et al. (2014) advise that instead of employing the CBS-SEM strategy, the PLS-SEM technique should be used for exploratory research or for expanding an existing theory. PLS-SEM was used in this study rather than CBS-SEM, as advised by Hair et al., due to the exploratory character of the inquiry (2014). It was because of the user interface's simplicity and clarity that the researcher picked SPSS software over AMOS software (Arbuckle, 2006) to create the model.

Final thoughts: The goal of the current research study is to contribute to the consumer's comprehension of how digital platforms are used. As a result of this study, a research gap will be filled, and the importance of different elements of online communities will be highlighted. For the benefit of their competitive advantage, platform owners may utilise the study's results to prioritise their efforts in online business with innovative business models and the integration of digital platforms. It follows that the repercussions for platform owners will be huge. The research approach and procedure by which these operational assumptions of the conceptual model are investigated are discussed in further detail in the next Chapter.

4. CHAPTER 4

Research Methodology:

4.1. Introduction

This chapter will provide an overview of the research technique used in this study. The study has previously demonstrated that this research issue of platform adaptation is now under investigation since just a few studies have studied the criteria surrounding this topic (Scheu, et al., 2009). The notion that the issue under discussion has received insufficient investigation led to the decision to do exploratory research as the first stage in this study, which was successful. It will take a step-by-step approach to first explore the three philosophical research paradigms and then go on to explain the reasoning behind the paradigm that has been selected. The Pragmatist approach adopted for this study will serve as the foundation for selecting a mixed-methods design, which will be modified from Plano Clark, 2011, as described above. It will be mentioned in this chapter about the many phases of this investigation, as well as about the research technique methods that will be outlined.

4.2. Philosophy and Interpretation

This research will discuss and compare the philosophies to assess the various methodological choices for this research and after the comparison the study will discuss the chosen Philosophies and methodologies for this research and discuss the reason for choice made. The philosophy of any research has a significant influence on the design of the study, and it is critical to understand the ideology behind the research design (Creswell, 2009). In many cases, the quality of research is largely reliant on philosophical questions and failing to consider these issues may result in a skewed study design (Jackson, 2008). According to Easterby (2008), it is critical to identify and address ideological difficulties during the research process. Therefore, this study of user's perception of digital platforms acceptance will also need to navigate through the possible research philosophies it could adopt to get a desired result, and to do so this study will follow the following steps.

In the first instance, the research philosophy helps to explain the various methodologies that may be applied in that research.

2. This will also reveal which designs are more likely to support the research argument and which designs are less likely to do so.

3. They will guide the researcher in the correct route, which the researcher could otherwise overlook because of inexperience.

When used effectively, research philosophy will aid a researcher in the development of a research framework that can be justified in the selection of any given decision. When selecting the appropriate philosophical stance, it is necessary to examine all the philosophical perspectives as well as the persons who belong to these philosophical positions in detail (Teshakkori, 2009). According to Creswell, careful attention is necessary to navigate through philosophical methods, and this might be accomplished by recognising and challenging the most fundamental ideological assumptions made by the study team.

The word "worldview" will be used in this research since it is consistent with the philosophical viewpoint that has been adopted. According to Teddlie and Teshakkori (2009a), this phrase is endorsed by a large number of scholars. It is important to grasp all sides of the issue when dealing with philosophical positions in the social sciences since research designs might be derived from more than one school depending on the study topic (Easterby 2008). So, this research will follow the work of social science studies (Teddlie and Teshakkori 2009) which states that it is also critical that the selected viewpoint be supported by evidence and that the decision not to pursue other perspectives be supported by logic and reasoned argument.

This research of user's perceptions regarding the acceptance of digital platforms will begin by discussing the rival worldviews and then go on to illustrate the possibilities of these philosophical positions concerning this study. This will make sure that all the possible avenues of research philosophies are reviewed before settling for the best match for this research. According to Creswell (2009), there are two primary worldviews: post-positivist and constructivist (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008), but nomenclature varies from country to country. It might be said that these two worldviews are at different ends of the spectrum and are at the boundaries of the metaphysical continuum that is being investigated by scientists. The ideas of ontology, epistemology, and axiology, which are ascribed to Guba and Lincoln

(1994), are used to distinguish various philosophical perspectives and are distinguished from one another.

Philosophy	Explanation
Ontology	Presuppositions concerning the nature of reality held by philosophers
Epistemology	A collection of general assumptions concerning the most effective methods of enquiring about the nature of the universe
Axiology	Within the research process, this refers to the importance of values and ethics in one's work.

Table 4.1.: Ontology, epistemology, Axiology. Source: Author

When seen as conflicting paradigmatic approaches in the metaphysical continuum, these viewpoints may be better comprehended, since these perspectives take a firm position between perspectives. This assists researchers in distinguishing between paradigms because, if they are operating inside one paradigm, they are compelled to reject the other paradigms as well. Morrigan (2007) defines formalised that the constructivist and post-positivist worldviews are the two most often debated paradigms in the social sciences.

4.2.1. Positivist and Constructivist Worldviews

Positivism is very important world view from this research point of view, when it comes to thinking about positivism, post-positivism is a good representation since it solves concerns with positivism such as "value-free" assertions, which are difficult to support in social sciences with human beings (Tashakkori, 2009). In the 19th century, the comet represented pure positivism, which asserted that the physical world exists outside and can be assessed using objective means, and which was initially epitomised by the comet (Easterby 2009). To put it another way, the reality is external, and knowledge is not valuable unless it is received from external reality, which is what we mean by ontological terminology (Gill & Johnson, 2010) In social sciences, this paradigm was very dominant during the greater part of the twentieth century. This study can use this world view to address the issues of validity and reliability of the collected data.

Similarly, Post-positivist philosophy is deterministic since it strives to discover the source of every given result rather than just accepting it (Creswell, 2009). The observation of numerical

measures as well as the behaviour of persons is thus critical for the positivist paradigm to function properly. Post positivists, as a result, often use deductive reasoning to construct a theory, which is founded on a set of particular assumptions, and then produce hypotheses, which are tested using statistical analytic methods (Creswell, 2003; Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009).

An alternate world view evolved in the late twentieth century, which was utilised as an alternative to the post-positivist point of view (Easterby-Smith 2010).

This worldview is referred to as constructivism, which is also known as interpretivism in certain circles (Teddlie, 2009). The worldview proved to be a viable alternative to post-positivism in many ways (Creswell, 2009).

Researchers that adhere to this viewpoint believe that humans may get a better understanding of their environment by developing subjective interpretations for the phenomena that surround them (Creswell, 2009). Contrary to the positivist point of view, constructivists want a polarity of perspectives in their discussions. The individual participants' points of view are the most important source of information about how reality is being interpreted (Creswell, 2009). Individuals discover their subjective meanings via their interactions with others. The investigation under the constructive viewpoint is carried out utilising inductive reasoning since patterns may be generated from meanings in this perspective. It is collected, analysed, interpreted, and presented thematically (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009, p. 6) the narratives of the people.

Research Assumption(s)	Post-Positivism	Social constructivism
Ontology	Reality is objective and observed only by the investigator of the problem	Reality is objective and observed by the investigator
Epistemology	A researcher is not affiliated with the subject being researched	A researcher is associated with that being researched and is interactive
Human Interest	Should be unrelated	The primary motivators of research
Explanations	Must demonstrate connection	Attempt to broaden general understanding of the problem
Research progresses through	Hypotheses and deduction are used to progress through research	Using and gathering rich data from which ideas are induced
Concepts	It is necessary to operationalize concepts for them to be quantified	Should take into account the viewpoints of stakeholders
Units of analysis	Should be reduced to the smallest possible units of analysis.	It is possible to include the complexity of 'whole scenarios
Generalization through	The statistical probability is used to generalise a concept	Abstraction from reality on the theoretical level
Sampling requires	A high number of people was chosen at random	A limited number of examples were selected for specific reasons

Table 4.2. – Comparison of Approaches. Source: Author

It was Thomas Kuhn (1970) who popularised the concept of these two paradigms contending against one another; in his work, he proved how supporters of these two worldviews differ about the merits of the opposing party's point of view (Tashakkori, 2009). It was determined that there was disagreement on the grounds of ontology, axiology, and epistemology; these

are the terminology used to describe the differences between the stances of both worldviews (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009).

The incompatibility thesis, which asserts that these two world perspectives are fundamentally incompatible and hence cannot be combined, played a significant role in the battle. The thesis also states that the research paradigm serves as the foundation for the research technique and that if one is distinct from the other, the two cannot be related to one another (see Figure 1). (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009, p. 15). As social science research methods advance, an increasing number of researchers believe that these two opposed worldviews can be used as a complement to one another, and some researchers such as Smith (1988) believe that it is not possible to say that these two approaches can never be reconciled with one another.

Experts have expressed worry about studies that continue to follow the same mentality, such as marketing research, which has been criticised by researchers for failing to integrate different approaches when researching the topic (Davis, Goliicic, & Boirstler, 2011). When a single approach is chosen for investigations, the breadth of the study is restricted, and it is more susceptible to bias (Deshpande 1938). Stewart (2009) observed that the findings obtained through the use of numerous methodologies may be more persuasive than the results obtained through the use of a single way of study.

Mixed method research is a relatively recent approach, having emerged after the two well-known world perspectives of the twentieth century (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009, p. 7). The compatibility thesis was developed to oppose the incompatibility thesis and to promote the use of a combination of techniques. According to Brewer (2006), "The pragmatism of adopting numerous research methodologies to examine the same general issue by presenting diverse particular questions has certain pragmatic consequences for social theory." It is preferable to mix approaches that promote or even necessitate the integration of diverse theoretical viewpoints to understand the data rather than being committed to a specific theoretical style...and it is the most compatible way.

It is because of this that pragmatism has emerged, and scholars have begun to use pragmatism to oppose the incompatibility thesis (Tashakkori, 2009). Additionally, this research utilised the same pragmatism stance, which will be described further in this research later.

4.2.2. Pragmatist Worldview:

This study will also discuss the pragmatist worldview as this will assist this research to provide a medium method of obtaining desired outcomes it could provide an alternative mix of methods to get better understanding of the research area. because pragmatism is described as follows by Immanuel Kant: 'Because our limited human efforts at inquiry can never achieve totality, we must settle for sufficiency, which is ultimately a practical matter rather than a theoretical one, so that prioritising practical reason over theoretical reason is an inescapable part of the human condition.' (Honderich, 2005, p. 747) (Honderich, 2005, p. 747), Which in this research case will be an important aspect due to inheriting restrains of this type of study.

Kant criticises pure reason, claiming that it contains a fundamental error since the whole metaphysics is predicated on the erroneous assumption that persons may have real knowledge of the world outside of its existence. He went on to say that all claims of reality are false and that what we experience as reality is indeed reality (Honderich, 2007).

A pioneer of contemporary pragmatism in the form of American philosopher C.S. Pierce, who holds that beliefs are habits of acting upon things rather than representations or descriptions of reality, was born in the early 1900s (Mautner, 2007). The pragmatic viewpoint gradually evolved into a theory of meaning, with the interpretation of every belief that has an application in the actual world happening in connection to the observable consequences becoming more important. Even though for Fort Pierce, tangible outcomes meant practical application. Another well-known researcher, William James, holds to the concept that real belief should be followed by action (or inaction) (Mautner, 2005). In addition to Jhon Dewey, another advocate of Pragmatism, Darwin held the Darwinian perspective that there is no obvious distinction between practical and theoretical knowledge. It was dualism (theory and practice) that Dewey and James considered was the primary issue with pragmatism, and both of them believed that dualism was out of date and was taken for granted. Efficacy is the cornerstone of pragmatism; pragmatism takes the premise that what works and what doesn't is the most effective in practice and applies it. Perspectives that are optimistic and progressive might be related to pragmatism (Honderich, 2005). In pragmatism, the reality of the world is examined and exploited to the greatest extent possible.

Instead of focusing on making things perfect, which is the primary emphasis of dualistic research philosophies, pragmatic approaches present an alternative (Cherryholmes, 1992, p. 13). Because it does not focus on following rigid norms of ontology and epistemology, it differs from conventional philosophies in that it aims to clarify meanings rather than preserving theories and explanations, as traditional philosophies do (Cherryholmes, 1992). In Pragmatic philosophy, knowledge is utilised as a tool to make sense of our experiences, and our actions are dictated by the conceptions that have developed as a result of those experiences (Audi, 1999; Cherryholmes, 1992).

Because the purposes of the researcher and the values of the researcher cannot be distinguished using epistemological criteria, the truth cannot be determined using these criteria in pragmatic methodology, and vice versa. The ideals that are shown to be effective in solving difficulties are considered worthy of preservation (Audi, 2000). Researchers in the pragmatic world must understand the results of their study because they are utilised to explain the practical ramifications of their research and because they form the foundation of future experiences. When considering the concept of pragmatism, it is helpful to think along the lines of (what may happen if I do X) since this will lead to a deeper understanding of the consequence of that action and the ability to apply that knowledge to other outcomes (Johnson & Onwueigbuzie, 2004).

When doing pragmatic research, the researcher plays an important role; as a result, any study based on an experienced interpretation of the situation is inherently flawed and vulnerable to a correction. Since the pragmatist researcher does not pretend to know the reality of their research when asked about the reality of their research, they typically respond with another question, "Is there any way we could know?" because the pragmatist researcher recognises and understands how frequently the understanding of the reality is the understanding of one's self (Cherryholmes, 1992, p. 14).

Teddlie and Takahashi, 2009 found a stronger connection between pragmatism and mixed-method research, defining it as follows: "A deconstructive paradigm that debunks concepts such as 'truth' and reality and focuses instead on 'what works' as the truth regarding the research question under investigation." According to Pragmatism, "either/or options are not

acceptable in research; mixed approaches are encouraged, and the researcher's views play a significant influence in the interpretation of study findings."

The following section describes the work of researchers who use a pragmatic perspective as an alternative and who combine both qualitative and quantitative methodologies into their study findings. The pragmatist is frequently uncomfortable with making claims about the actuality of truth; as a result, they attempt to make sense of their experiences via the use of consequential and practical reasoning (Audi, 1999). Often, it is said, the pragmatist makes use of epistemological justification and values to create the most effective framework for a study topic. Creswell (2009, p. 10) claims that, in contrast to post-positivism, the world view of pragmatism is derived from acts and their consequences. Specifically, Morgan (2008) contends that: **Outside of beginning textbooks, the only time we pretend that research may be either completely inductive or completely deductive is when we write up our work to submit it for publication. Although neither an exclusive theory-driven nor a data-driven approach can be used during the actual design, collection, and analysis of data, it is conceivable to do so during the actual data collection and analysis.**

Because pragmatists do not preach about truth, the heart of their philosophy of knowledge is based on their attitude toward the philosophy of knowledge. Instead, they simply recognise the practical effects of a particular activity. It is necessary for a researcher to exercise some discretion in this regard since this technique constantly reminds us that a researcher's personality has an impact on the organization's policies and ideals (Morgan, 2008). Caracelli (1997) and Morgan (2008) define pragmatism as a basic concept about how to conduct research in the social sciences that also serves as a basis for combining qualitative and quantitative methodologies in research (Caracelli, 1997).

	Qualitative Approach	Quantitative Approach	Pragmatic Approach
Connection of theory and data	Induction	Deduction	Abduction
Relationship to the research process	Subjectivity	Objectivity	Intersubjectivity
Inference from data	Context	Generality	Transferability

Table 4.3. – Alternative to pragmatic view. Source: Author

As in the theory to data abductive strategy converts observation to theory and then assesses it via action (Morrigan, 2008), this study employs the same research approach as in the pragmatic approach since this reasoning technique changes between inductive and deductive approaches. A further point made by Morrigan (2008) is that rather than relying on subjective or objective techniques, an intersubjective approach is preferable since it may use a variety of methodological approaches. Because the pragmatist does not conclude that the outcomes are context-dependent or generalizable, they have adapted the word transferability to fit their needs. The pragmatist should constantly inquire as to how much of one's previous knowledge may be used in the current situation (Morgan, 2007, p.72). They should constantly ask questions that are relevant to knowledge, and they should do it in a manner that may be used in other situations.

According to Johnson and Onwuegbozie (2004), pragmatism is not the conclusion of the debate in the social sciences, but rather a means of navigating a more alternative path through the field. It provides an immediate and useful philosophical and methodological middle position; it provides a practical and outcome-oriented method of inquiry that is based on action and leads, iteratively, to further action and the elimination of doubt; and it provides a method for selecting methodological mixes that can help researchers better answer many of their research questions.

As it makes use of both numerical and narrative forms of data for extracting conclusions, this technique enables researchers to combine the best aspects of both qualitative and quantitative

approaches (Tashakeori, 2009). This strategy of obtaining research findings enables researchers to concentrate on the research topic and utilise whatever method necessary to get information about the research subject in question (Creswell, 2009)

Following is a summary of the three worldviews that were explored before in this section.

The pragmatic perspective used for this research led to the selection of a mixed-method technique for data collecting.

<p>Post-Positivist World View</p>	<p>Knowledge is conjectural. Post-positivists do not claim absolute truth. In this approach, a researcher fails to reject a hypothesis rather than establish one. Post-positivistic arguments are improved or abandoned and typically require theory testing.</p> <p>Knowledge is formed by facts, evidence, and logic.</p> <p>Researchers strive to show causation or explain circumstances by investigating the link between variables.</p> <p>Objectivity is vital — researchers must address questions of validity, reliability, and bias.</p>
<p>Pragmatist World View</p>	<p>Pragmatism does not adhere to any one ideology or point of view. Researchers are involved in both qualitative and quantitative research projects.</p> <p>Researchers can pick procedures that best match the goals of the research because they have the flexibility to do so.</p>

	<p>Pragmatists do not regard the world as a monolithic whole and instead use a variety of ways to make sense of a given research challenge or question.</p> <p>The truth, in the eyes of pragmatists, is whatever works at the moment and is not dependent on the objective or subjective <u>viewpoint</u></p> <p>Researchers that are pragmatic in their approach are concerned with what and how to investigate.</p> <p>Practising pragmatism in research allows researchers to experiment with many approaches, worldviews, and assumptions at the same time.</p>
<p>Social Constructivist World View</p>	<p>Individuals generate meanings in a phenomenological manner, which they then investigate via open-ended questioning.</p> <p>Face-to-face engagement with others and visits to research facilities are two ways in which social constructivists make sense of their environment from a social standpoint.</p> <p>The understanding gained via study is taken through social interaction and created using inductive methodologies.</p>

Table 4.4.- Philosophical Worldviews Source: Author

4.3. Research Design:

This research could use the quantitative or qualitative design or both to get the required answers but to better understand the research designs and if possible chose the best design which will serve this users behaviour study we need to discuss and asses all the possible options. One method of distinguishing between quantitative and qualitative approaches may be to employ numerical and non-numerical data to make a distinction between the two. The term "quantitative" is often used in conjunction with any approach or operation that relies on numerical data, such as questionnaires. In contrast, the term "qualitative approach" is used to refer to any narrative data collecting technique, such as interviews, that collects narrative data. In most cases, qualitative approaches do not include numerical data collecting and analysis methodologies, but quantitative approaches do. Even though this is a very essential point of demarcation between quantitative and qualitative approaches, this explanation is problematic and limited in its application.

The fundamental flaw in this line of thinking is that not all research designs are likely to include both quantitative and qualitative parts of the study. For example, instead of merely checking boxes, a questionnaire can invite respondents to answer a question in their own words, which would be considered open-ended. As an example, the study design may call for a researcher to conduct follow-up interviews with respondents following the questionnaire to get an explanation for their responses. Similarly, Additionally, certain qualitative research designs need data to be analysed numerically, while other qualitative research designs are used to inform quantitative research designs, such as questionnaires, which are used to collect quantitative data. Research designs may be thought of as a continuum of qualitative and quantitative designs that are often blended. A discussion of the mixed-method research design will be included in this study at a later time.

The distinction made previously between qualitative and quantitative designs is too limited, and it does not adequately account for the differences between these two types of designs. The larger perspective on this problem may assist us in better understanding this discrepancy since typically, the researcher's prior preconceptions impact the technique of the study he is performing at the time of the interview. Because of this, this research have attempted to

understand the distinction between qualitative and quantitative designs and then choose how we will apply this interpretation to the study situation at hand. The next section will attempt to reinterpret research techniques by connecting them to assumptions, approaches, and tactics.

4.3.1. Quantitative research design:

Research philosophy

Quantitative research is associated with positivism, especially when it employs a highly organised data gathering approach. The data obtained, on the other hand, should always be differentiated since it might pertain to people's opinions or to the characteristics of those who participated in the survey. For example, when data requires a respondent's viewpoint, the quantitative technique might be connected with interpretivism; alternatively, it can be associated with pragmatic or realist ideologies, as in the case of mixed methods study design.

Approach to theory development

The quantitative method may be utilised in both deductive and inductive approaches, where data is used to test theory and theory is generated using data, however, the quantitative approach is more often linked with the deductive approach since it is more accurate.

Characteristics

A variety of statistical tests are employed to analyse numerical data in quantitative research, and these tests are utilised to explore the correlations between variables in the selected research subject. Controls are often used in quantitative approaches to assure the validity of the results. Ensuring that questions are stated properly and that participants understand them in the same way that data collecting in quantitative research is done in a standardised manner is very essential. Because the researcher is acting as an impartial observer of the respondents, this approach often uses the probability sampling technique to gather information.

The design of quantitative research may be classified into many types. There are two types of quantitative techniques: monomethod quantitative technique and multimethod quantitative technique. Researchers often use questionnaires and analytical procedures to conclude the monomethod quantitative analysis, whereas, in multimethod quantitative analysis, researchers use more than one data collection technique and then apply corresponding analytical methods to conclude. For example, a researcher might want to collect data using structured observation as well as questionnaires before applying quantitative methods to conduct data analysis. It is possible to use various ways to collect quantitative or qualitative data using a multimethod of quantitative and qualitative approach, however, it is not possible to combine both types of data collecting methods.

Bryman (2006) advocated for the use of multiple data collection methods rather than a single data collection method to obtain more rich data. He did so because multiple data collection methods help to reduce the likelihood of error and overcome the shortcomings of the single data collection method.

Research strategies

Survey tactics and experimental strategies are two strategies that are often associated with quantitative research. To collect data for quantitative research, researchers often use organised observation or questionnaires to get the information.

4.3.2. Qualitative research design

Research philosophy

The term "interpretive philosophy" is often used in conjunction with qualitative research (Denzin and Lincoln 2011). When doing qualitative research, the researcher must make sense of the social construct, and interpretative philosophy may assist the researcher in better understanding the meaning of the phenomena under investigation.

The word "naturalistic" is often used to describe this form of study since the researcher must operate in a natural setting to build confidence among the participants and therefore get a better understanding of the phenomena. Qualitative research may be conducted using pragmatist or realist philosophical approaches.

Approach to theory development

In qualitative research, the inductive method to theory is often utilised because the naturalistic research design is used to construct a theory to get a more complete knowledge of the theoretical point of view. In certain situations, a deductive approach may be used in qualitative research to test an existing theory, which is when qualitative methodologies are used to examine an existing theory (Yin 2014). Similar to this, an abductive technique may be used in many qualitative investigations, where the researcher first develops inductive assumptions, which are then verified by using the deductive approach throughout the study.

Characteristics

When doing qualitative research, many data gathering approaches are used to better grasp the meaning and connection of the study subject at hand. These procedures are subsequently evaluated, and the results of the evaluation are utilised to construct a theoretical framework. Despite the wide range of methods used in data collection and analysis, the most important thing in qualitative research is to demonstrate the rigour of the methodological choices made and the theoretical contributions made as a result of these choices, which is particularly difficult in quantitative research.

When it comes to qualitative data collecting, nonprobability sampling may be used, since, unlike quantitative research, qualitative data collection is non-standardized, and questions can be amended or even completely new questions might develop during the data gathering stage. This realistic and engaging procedure is also dependent on the researcher's capacity to get not just physical access to the participants, but also cognitive access via questioning and discussion.

Research strategies

A variety of techniques may be used in conjunction with qualitative research. The fundamental notions of ontological and epistemological assumptions are the same across all of these different tactics, but the scope and emphasis placed on the scope differ. Among the methodologies that may be employed in qualitative research are case study, grounded theory, narrative research, and action research, all of which have common assumptions but range in scope and can be applied in various ways. A few of these tactics may also be used in mixed methods research designs as well as quantitative research designs such as case studies, among other things. The Mixed Methods Research Design will be discussed in further detail in the next section.

4.3.3. Mixed methods research design

Research philosophy

Mixed method research is the closest research philosophy to this study as the it is the outcome of two opposing philosophical viewpoints. Mixed method could provide the window to the researcher to collect and analysed data from multiple sources using multiple methods, this will provide the current study a unique advantage of doing a data triangulation which will robust this research results and help the author to explain its results with more clarity. Mixed method research methodology incorporates both qualitative and quantitative research techniques, and as a result, mixed-method research methodology is usually referred to as the multimethod branch of the research methods. This branch has its origins in the philosophy of realism, and more especially in critical realism. Even if reality exists in the world in which we live, the advocates of mixed approaches think that how this objective reality is viewed and understood may influence social situations. The researchers begin with quantitative data analysis and then go on to qualitative research methodologies to investigate perceptions and attitudes (Tashakkori and Teddlie 2010).

Pragmatic approaches to research, such as mixed-method research, may also influence the methodology since pragmatists believe that choosing just one philosophical perspective is

less beneficial and instead prefer to employ many or mixed techniques to better comprehend the research topic (Teddlie 2010). When doing pragmatism research, the nature of the research issue and the study setting are the primary motivators, and the pragmatic will choose a qualitative, quantitative, or mixed research methodology to get the desired knowledge of the situation.

Approach to theory development

There are many methods to the theory that is suitable for mixed-method study design, including deductive, inductive, and abductive techniques. The researcher may use qualitative or quantitative techniques to test the theoretical claim, and then follow up with quantitative or qualitative research to get a more complete picture of the theoretical knowledge in mixed methods. In the case of mixed-method study design, the theory may also influence the scope of the investigation (Teddlie 2010).

Characteristics

To get a better understanding of the study topic, qualitative and quantitative methodologies are blended in a variety of ways. This spectrum of approaches includes techniques in basic, concurrent, and sequential forms, among others. As a consequence, mixed methods may be classified into a variety of approaches depending on the amount to which qualitative and quantitative techniques are combined to produce the desired results (Nasstasi et al. 2010). **When using mixed methods, data is collected using both quantitative and qualitative approaches at the same time, and the findings of both techniques are interpreted later on to provide a more complete picture of the results, the results are richer. This approach is referred to as a contemporaneous mixed-method since it employs a single-phase study design to determine how the data acquired from both phases complement one another and how they work together. This strategy delivers a more complete view than the traditional single-method data collecting method. The researcher may save time by using this approach rather than the sequential mixed methods to gather data from the respondent since it is more practicable to do so.**

In contrast to the sequential mixed method, which is a more complicated kind of mixed methods study design, the sequential mixed method incorporates more than one step of data gathering. In a sequential mixed approach, data is gathered at the beginning of the process, and at a later point, the data acquired is utilised to expand on the next round of data gathering.

In addition, sequential exploratory and sequential explanatory research designs are subdivided into two strategies: sequential exploratory and sequential explanatory research designs. While there are some similarities between these two branches, the primary difference is that in sequential exploratory research design, qualitative data collection techniques are applied first, followed by quantitative data collection techniques, whereas in sequential explanatory research design, quantitative data collection techniques are applied first, followed by qualitative data collection techniques. There are a few rare instances when the sequential mixed approach is used in a more intricate structure, such as in one phase the explanatory technique will be applied and tested, followed by the exploratory research methodology being used and examined in a later stage. The use of a two-phased research design like this helps to reinforce the study findings while also highlighting the dynamic character of the mixed methods approach.

It is important to note that when a researcher employs the fully integrated mixed-method research design, he does so at every step of the research process, from data collection through data analysis and outcomes interpretation. However, when just one phase of a research project is using a mixed approach, incomplete mixed methods might be employed to complete the research project successfully (Tashakkori, 2011).

Furthermore, qualitative and quantitative methods can be used in conjunction, as in some cases qualitative data is coded and converted into numerical numbers to conduct quantitative analysis, and similarly, quantitative data can be converted into text or other forms of qualitative data to conduct and interpretation, but these cases are very rare as there is always the risk that the data form will be diluted, such as if a researcher quantifies all of the qualitative data, it may result in losses.

Because a mixed-methods researcher may employ both sides equally or unequally in a mixed-methods research project, the emphasis of weighting in quantitative or qualitative research may vary (Clark 2011). Depending on the goal of the study, either qualitative or quantitative approaches may play a more dominating role in mixed methods research than the other. This function might also be a reflection of the researcher and the supervisory team who were responsible for commissioning the study. Depending on whether the research is exploratory or explanatory, the qualitative techniques may play a more dominant role while the quantitative techniques play a supporting role; conversely, if the research is explanatory, the quantitative techniques may play a more dominant role while the qualitative techniques only play a supporting role.

Additionally, the research methodology may have a significant impact in determining which technique to use. For example, theoretical conceptions may be developed using an inductive approach, while theory can be built utilising qualitative approaches. The focus placed on certain study topics varies depending on the research technique used.

The mixed method approach may have techniques that are integrated inside it. The phrase embedded mixed methods research is often used to describe situations in which several approaches are used, with one methodology serving to assist the other (Clark 2011). During the data collecting phase, certain quantitative questions may be included in an interview, while on the other side, some qualitative questions may be incorporated into a questionnaire or survey. This is possible in single-phase research design, and it is referred to as concurrent embedded design in certain circles. Furthermore, a study may use both qualitative and quantitative approaches at the same time, but gather the data in two consecutive phases, with one portion of the data being analysed to support the other portion of the data. However, just one side of the data will be examined, with the other serving as a support for the other.

Mixed methods research design qualities may be utilised to obtain a result using both quantitative and qualitative approaches; however, the importance of each feature in a research project will rely on the breadth of the study challenge and the researcher's judgement. There are several reasons for using a mixed methods research design, but only the specific reason for selecting this design will compel the researcher to include this design in their investigation.

Research design

The study design is determined by a mix of features of the research methodologies used in the investigation. It has already been mentioned previously in this chapter how the primary research design would be implemented. Among the most common mixed methods research designs are the concurrent research design, embedded research design, exploratory research design in sequential mixed methods, and explanatory research design in mixed methods (to name a few).

4.4. Chosen Research Design:

4.4.1. Mixed Methods:

This research will choose Mixed method research design as in this design both qualitative and quantitative techniques can be utilised and based on the structure of this study this approach will assist this research in obtaining the required outcomes. The questionnaires designed for this research could become a quantitative technique and the interviews could be conducted to serve the qualitative side of research technique. After the two existing research communities (qualitative research community and quantitative research community), several writers from other disciplines, such as education, management, sociology, and others, proposed the concept of a third research community (Plano 2011). Later, these concepts were more fully integrated, and study designs and classifications began to develop (Bryman, 2006). Mixed method research, according to the findings of Johnson (2007), is characterised as:

When a researcher or team of researchers employs elements of both qualitative and quantitative research approaches (e.g., the use of both qualitative and quantitative viewpoints, data collection techniques, and analysis inference techniques) for the broad purposes of understanding and corroboration, they are said to be conducting mixed methods research.

The phrase "multi-trait multi mixed-method matrix" was invented by the author Campbell, who advocated for a more rigorous validation procedure for qualitative research. As a result, the development of mixed methods study design may be dated back to the mid-20th century. Campbell and Fisk were concerned that if a researcher used only one method in a quantitative technique, it would be difficult to distinguish between trait variance and method variance;

therefore, using multiple methods (measuring the same trait and then using a matrix of the trait) can ensure that the enhanced validation is achieved (Campbell & Fisk, 1959).

In later years, Jick (1979) recognised the limitations of single data collecting approaches and attempted to combine both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods. This sparked the idea of using mixing techniques for not just quantitative approaches, such as those developed by Campbell and Fisk, but also for other purposes. According to Jick, rather than seeing these two methodologies as opposed to one another, researchers should consider them to be complementary to one another. Better data triangulation was achieved via the use of the mixed approach, which led to a better comprehension of the study topic and a deeper knowledge of the phenomena.

The researcher, according to Jick, will be able to compare the data from these two methodologies, which may be utilised for cross-validation in the study to confirm the validity of the findings. Not only will this increase trust in the research's findings, but it will also push the researchers to come up with more innovative techniques for data collecting in the future. Other writers agreed with the concept and used a multimethod approach to data collecting. [page number] (Denzin, 1978). Cronbach (1975) attempted to include more qualitative methodologies into experimental research and was successful in doing so.

The rise of qualitative research in the 1970s played a significant role in convincing researchers that new approaches could be used in addition to quantitative research. This notion aided mixed methods research from positivist tradition researchers, who believed that using a variety of methodologies could improve the validity of the research. Plano and Creswell (2011) described the different phases of development of mixed methodologies research projects:

Over the last several years, the mixed-method approach has progressed beyond a straightforward data triangulation strategy. The mixed methods research methodology has been supported by several publications and journals, and it has evolved into an inquiry strategy that incorporates philosophical assumptions as well as integrated qualitative and quantitative approaches.

The task includes much more than just collecting and analysing both sorts of data. Also included is the practice of integrating both approaches in such a way that the overall strength of the study is greater than the strength of either qualitative or quantitative research alone. It is necessary to first grasp the pros and cons of mixed methods research design to better comprehend the mixed methods research design itself. A summary of the advantages and disadvantages of the selected study design is provided in the table below:

Benefits

- Combining several sources of information, it produces more conclusive conclusions.
- Numbers may be given more meaning via the use of words, visuals, and storey.
- Numbers may be utilised to give accuracy to written text, visual images, and narrative narratives.
- Ability to deliver both quantitative and qualitative advantages.
- A grounded theory may be developed and tested by researchers.
- Research problems may be answered more comprehensively and comprehensively because the researcher is not constrained by the use of one particular technique or strategy.
- By using both methods in a research study, a researcher may make use of the strengths of one approach while compensating for the flaws of another.

Challenges

- Performing both qualitative and quantitative research may be challenging for a single researcher, particularly if two or more methodologies are planned to be employed at the same time; this may necessitate the formation of a research team.
- The researcher must get familiar with a variety of methodologies and approaches, as well as how to combine them most effectively.
- Some methodological purists believe that one should always operate within one of two paradigms: a qualitative or a quantitative framework.
- It's going to cost more.
- It will take more time to complete.
- Some philosophical questions remain unanswered (analyzing mixed results, problems of paradigm mixing)

- Through the convergence and confirmation of results, it is possible to give greater evidence for a conclusion.
- When more than one approach is employed, it is possible to get additional insights and knowledge that might otherwise be overlooked.
- It is possible to apply this technique to improve the generalizability of the findings.
- It allows for a more comprehensive knowledge of occurrences.
- It is possible to run into complications throughout the review procedure.
- The reporting of findings within the constraints of a journal may be difficult.

Table 4.6.-Strengths and Weaknesses of Mixed Methods Research. Source: Author

It would be more practicable to use a pragmatic mixed-method research technique for this investigation. As a result, in this doctorate thesis, the mixed-method research approach will be used to gather information. According to Creswell (2009), a mixed-method research strategy may be split into two categories: sequential and concurrent. These two categories are further broken into a total of six categories. The sequential mixed methods, as their name suggests, would employ a series of data gathering techniques, where one data collection method would be completed first, followed by an analysis of that data, and then a final analysis of the data would be completed. Concurrent designs, on the other hand, imply that both data collecting techniques will be used simultaneously in a single study phase and that both outcomes will be analysed in the same session. This study will use sequential mixed techniques for data collection and interpretation since the primary goal of the research will be to understand the nature of value creation and the utility of a platform, as well as to analyse the notion in more detail.

4.5. Chosen Research Design Philosophy:

The rationale for using pragmatism for this investigation is because this viewpoint employs a variety of methodologies to ensure that the researcher obtains a comprehensive picture. Because the research topic for this study does not provide any explicit guidance on which research techniques should be used, pragmatism is the approach of choice for this investigation.

Additionally, this study applies pragmatic perspectives since it starts with a problem and seeks to give conclusions that are practical and can be utilised not only by companies but also by future researchers to make a positive contribution. The research question serves as the primary driving force for the investigation.

The other three main philosophical schools are interpretivism, postmodernism, and positivism, in addition to critical realism and pragmatism. When it comes to mixed methods research design, there are two main research philosophies to consider: pragmatism and critical realism. Critical realism allows for the application of quantitative analysis of previously collected data, followed by qualitative methods for the exploration of additional objectives.

The reality of things is determined by the practical effect of ideas, but truth can only be determined if it permits actions to be taken in the first place. If a notion can only be used to promote action, it may be accepted in pragmatism as a concept (Kelemen and Rumens 2008). To do this, it is necessary to conduct qualitative and quantitative research.

4.6. Chosen Research Design Purpose:

The mixed methods research strategy will be used in this study to attain more than one research goal. This study will make use of a combination of descriptive, explanatory, and investigative techniques. It will be studied utilising open-ended questions as well as other books and journals to get a better understanding of the topics that need further investigation. In addition, descriptive questions will be included in the study design as an alternative. This use of descriptive research design will aid in the discovery of the events' description as well

as the development of a more complete comprehension of the occurrences. The survey, which includes a descriptive questionnaire, will be sufficient to get the descriptive cover.

Explanatory research will be conducted on the data to better understand the co-relationship between the variables of the phenomenon. This explanation will aid in the establishment of explanatory research, which is essential for a better understanding of the variables and their relationship with one another. In a similar vein, evaluation design will be used to examine the success of business strategies for implementing platform-based solutions. Because this design contributes to knowledge by not only analysing the efficacy but also by offering a comparison with the findings and current theory, it will aid in the comparison and assessment of performance.

Even though the exploratory design will be preferable, the descriptive and explanatory research designs will also be included in the study. While the exploratory design will be preferable, the other designs will aid the researcher in better understanding the phenomena and answering the research question. To gain a better understanding of users' perception factors and their experiences with platform adaptation, this study will include semi-structured interviews, which will allow respondents to articulate their answers following their perceptions and will allow the researcher to discuss the results with the respondents, which will later assist the study in conducting a more in-depth analysis of the phenomenon.

To find more significant contributing aspects, this study will compare the theory with the themes that emerged from the data throughout the data analysis stage of the research. Additionally, the relationship between those elements will be investigated, as well as the efficiency of those factors, and the findings will be compared with the existing theories from the literature.

4.7. Chosen approach to theory development:

Though in mixed methods research, a researcher can choose between deductive and inductive approaches, this research will use abductive report because it will gather primary data from

interviews and a questionnaire to assess the research's main objectives and goals, rather than deductive or inductive.

Because the data will be acquired from a primary source and both interviews and questionnaires will be used to gather information throughout the data collection process, the information gathered will be rich and thorough in this study. Using an abductive technique, the rich data will be analysed, allowing the researcher to better grasp the themes that emerge from the data, and these patterns will be incorporated into the theoretical framework. A deeper understanding of the phenomena will be gained, as will knowledge of platform adaptability; in addition, this idea will be tested using additional data in the future.

4.8. Time horizon

Cross-sectional and longitudinal research are two phrases that are used to describe the temporal span of the study (Saunders 2011). The time frame for the study is dictated by the research subject itself. Longitudinal study design comprises observations of variables over a long period, as well as a set of studies that are performed in succession. These studies in longitudinal design may take decades to complete. On the other hand, with a cross-section study design, the variables are observed just once at a certain moment in time.

The cross-sectional research design is used in this study to answer the research question. First and foremost, the research on this issue has a strong focus on cross-sectional studies rather than longitudinal studies (Hussey, 2013). Second, customer tastes do not alter much over a short time. As a result, it is critical to capture the impressions and motivations of customers that impact their choice to use digital platforms in a short time. Because this research is concerned with understanding the correlation between variables rather than changing the research concept, a cross-sectional study is the only suitable alternative for this investigation.

A cross-sectional temporal frame is employed in this research, and surveys are used to gather data for it (Robson, 2002; Saunders, 2011). In a similar vein, cross-sectional temporal horizon research is often required for construct modelling. Finally, due to the limited time and resources available for this study, cross-sectional time horizons are the only realistic choice for this research, since longitudinal research may take years and would be more expensive than cross-sectional time horizons.

4.9. Data Collection:

4.9.1. Qualitative and quantitative techniques

Qualitative research is often carried out in the context of complicated societal concerns (Robson, 2002). Because the primary goal of this study is to get a more in-depth knowledge of respondents' thoughts and perspectives, it is not possible to grasp these difficulties immediately by converting them into statistics and variables. Qualitative research aids in the interpretation of people's viewpoints, and as a result, this kind of research is critical in understanding people's ideas and behaviours concerning a given situation. The researcher has the freedom to ask questions and explain them to respondents, or to make changes to questions during interviews to gain a better understanding of candidates' points of view. This method is very useful for further investigating any specific problem for which there is little previous literature on the subject matter.

If there is no existing theory in the issue area, qualitative research may be quite beneficial for solving the study problem in question (Bryman 2015) Furthermore, qualitative research has the benefit of being applicable in the early stages of a project and of allowing for revisions to the conceptual model based on the results of qualitative research.

Qualitative research has some disadvantages as well, including the fact that the study's generalizability, validity, and relevance may all be questioned (Kilbourn 2006). An investigation's internal validity measures how well the research's theory under development matches up with the researcher's observations, while its external validity measures how generalizable the investigation is to other situations or people.

Because qualitative research employs small samples, generalisability is a concern in qualitative research; however, in cross-sectional time horizons, generalisability becomes a concern because the sample size and time horizon indicate that the findings may not be a genuine representation of the community (Bryman and Bell, 2015). As previously stated by Schmitt et al. (2001) and Ercikan et al. (2009), generalisability is extremely important in qualitative results, and it can be achieved by using data collection methods such as case studies, provided that the data collected in the case study is replicable to be used for

determining the realisability of the results. Nonetheless, the generalizability of qualitative research findings will continue to be a weakness for qualitative research studies, since the generalizability of qualitative methods will not be as excellent as that of quantitative research methods.

Quantitative research approaches are often used in projects that are more concerned with numbers and variables. Data in its raw form is meaningless; it must be processed and understood before it can be used as an instrument in any research project (Saunders, 2011). With the use of statistical and analytical approaches, quantitative research can turn data into valuable information. The data gathered by quantitative methods is highly objective and can be used to test hypotheses and establish correlations to reach the desired result. Positivism is the research paradigm that is most closely connected with quantitative research methodologies, even though quantitative research is also related to phenomenology (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

While the external validity of quantitative research is less robust than that of qualitative research design, it is a solid argument in favour of quantitative research techniques. As a consequence, if the study employs an adequate probability of sampling, the findings of the obtained sample data may be generalised and should be an accurate representation of the overall population. With the standard technique and high level of objectivity, quantitative researchers can duplicate the findings in a variety of different settings.

Beginning with the hypothesis and concluding with the findings, quantitative research is conducted (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Because quantitative research is based on proven theories, it is possible to test hypotheses and come to a conclusion using the results. There are some downsides to quantitative research as well. For example, in contrast to qualitative studies in which researchers are allowed to gain a rich understanding of the phenomenon and a deeper understanding of the research problem because they have the opportunity to explain and understand the data directly to primary sources (e.g., interviews), quantitative studies in which researchers are given limited access to respondents and therefore are unable to gain a rich understanding of the problem (Bryman and Bell, 2015). By combining qualitative and quantitative methodologies to eliminate concerns that arise from both approaches, this deficiency may be addressed and overcome completely.

4.9.2. Data collection techniques for this research

This research makes use of both qualitative and quantitative data gathering methodologies to gather information. The researcher scheduled a face-to-face appointment with the respondent to conduct interviews as part of the qualitative portion of the data collecting process. The primary goal of conducting the interviews was to get first-hand information about the digital platform from those who were already familiar with it. This technique of data collecting is also beneficial in other ways, such as when respondents do not understand the questions, they may ask for an explanation again, and when the researcher does not grasp the significance of their answer, he can ask for clarification as well . The selection of qualitative data collecting is also supported by the goals and objectives of the research project. Because the results were not intended to be generalised, the researcher chose a small sample of people to study. It was through the use of qualitative methods that the researcher gained a better understanding of the user's perception of digital platform adaptation, and it was from these findings that the researcher formulated a construct for the subsequent second stage of the study, where quantitative methods were used to test the hypothesis.

To begin with, the researcher employs the second stage of the study to test the variables and factors that were offered by the respondents in the qualitative stage of the study, as well as variables and factors collected from the subject's literature. These tests were carried out using quantitative research techniques, in which a bigger group of participants was given survey forms to fill out, in which they were asked about the factors and their significance in terms of the attitude toward the adoption of a digital platform. These tests assisted the researcher in removing concerns about the generalisability and validity of the qualitative findings, which were then evaluated using quantitative procedures, which have a considerably greater level of objectivity and a more conventional approach to data gathering than qualitative approaches.

The use of both qualitative and quantitative research methods was appropriate for this study because digital platform adaptation is a relatively new topic, and the interaction with the respondent helped to clarify any misunderstandings between the researcher and the respondents. In the second stage, the researcher maintained the causal relationship with the respondents while collecting the quantitative data, which was a new method for this study.

Data triangulation is a type of data collecting in which data is acquired through several different ways at the same time (Collis, 2013).

Data triangulation increases the quality of the study design while also assisting in the reduction of any research bias in the data. This eventually assists the researcher in interpreting the findings with confidence (Hussey, 2013).

It is possible to split triangulation into three further categories (Hussey, 2009). To begin, data triangulation is used, in which data is acquired from several sources and the researcher selects two sets of samples from which to collect his or her data. The second kind of triangulation is method triangulation, in which the researcher employs several ways to acquire the necessary data, and the third type of triangulation is investigator triangulation, in which data is collected by numerous researchers or investigators. Only investigator triangulation was employed in this study, although the other two branches of triangulation were used since the data was acquired from many sources and numerous techniques (survey and interviews) were used to gather all of the data.

4.9.3. Specific methods for data collection

It is necessary to split the data gathering part of the investigation into two sections. Semi-structured interviews are used to gather information during the first step. There are two primary reasons for choosing semi-structured interviews: first, interviews are the most effective method of understanding complex social phenomena such as people's intentions, attitudes, and behaviour toward social issues; second, interviews are the most cost-effective method of understanding complex social phenomena such as people's intentions, attitudes, and behaviour toward social issues (Barriball and While, 1994). As a result of this characteristic, the researcher may get a comprehensive grasp of complicated social problems, and the process of data collecting allows them to explain the information that the researcher requires (Barriball and While, 1994).

Second, since there is no set sequence or phrasing for the questions in semi-structured interviews, the researcher has the flexibility to vary the order or wording of the questions to extract additional information from the respondents about the subject of the study. In many

studies, researchers believe that the difference in question-wording is the primary cause of variation in responses (Gordon, 1975). However, some researchers believe that the underlying meaning of questions is more important and that if the respondent understands the question, it makes no difference how the question was phrased (Treece and Treece, 1986). Keeping in mind the variety of the applicants, who all came from diverse backgrounds, had varying levels of education and had varying amounts of work experience. The researcher employed a semi-structured interview with pre-planned questions that might be changed in language or sequence based on the needs of the interview and the research topic being investigated (Corbetta, 2003).

When developing research questions, the researcher followed the methodology of Patton (2005), who utilises the same procedure in which research questions are generated based on interaction with respondents and reworded to ensure that they are relevant to the selected study subject. Due to the open-ended questions in semi-structured interviews, they are more adaptable in terms of uncovering new concerns that may occur throughout the interview. This strategy also allows the investigator to ask for clarification if there is any misinterpretation of the data and to gather data from all respondents at a reasonable degree of accuracy. According to the subject matter of the literature and the responses received from the respondents, the survey stage of data collecting was designed.

Second, a structured quantitative research survey is developed to perform quantitative and statistical data analysis on the results of the quantitative research survey. In the social sciences, questionnaire-based web surveys are becoming increasingly popular as a means of collecting quantitative data (Llieva et al., 2001). Because of their ease of design and construction, they are frequently used in business, management, and consumer behaviour related research (Llieva et al., 2001). (Muttalemwa, 2014). It is possible to get a variety of benefits by conducting an online survey. These benefits include ease of creation and administration; rapid replies; cost efficiency; mass dissemination; control; and reduced researcher bias (Couper et al. 2011). Saunders (2011) went on to say that because of the quantitative aspect of the survey, it is simple to include the results into positive research. Surveys also have the advantage of being generalizable since they are simple to repeat in another situation (Creswell, 2013). To add strength to the findings of the research, the survey instrument that was utilised in this study was used for data triangulation and method

triangulation, which increased the strength of the findings of the research. Fourth, the internet media allows the researcher to have access to a huge number of respondents, hence increasing the sample size for a more accurate representation of the general population.

4.9.4. Design and construction of data collection methods

The need for a qualitative data collection instrument was identified to get fresh insights and examine responses from the selected candidates (Healey and Rawlinson, 1994). This data collection instrument will aid in the development of an initial framework for the investigation. As a result, a semi-structured interview framework was developed for this research, which was meticulously planned to gather data both in the pilot study phase and in the first stage of the main study, when data collection is done qualitatively.

When it came to designing the semi-structured interview questions, the researcher followed the recommendations of Hutchinson and Wilson (1992). The most significant questions were included, such as users' perceptions of platform adaption, the effect of different elements on their intention and attitude, and the least important questions were eliminated. Unnecessary questions that were not related to the topic were deleted. Initial icebreaker questions were used to ensure that the respondents felt comfortable, and the flow of the interview continued towards essential areas as the procedure was guided by a sequence. Due to the novelty of the issue, open-ended questions were inferred, which had a good influence on the richness of the data obtained throughout the whole process. Keeping the novelty of the topic in mind (Doody and Noonan, 2013).

Given the possibility that respondents would stray from the subject or speak for longer than usual, the researcher limited the number of questions to 26 and the total time allotted for the interview to one hour. According to Barriball and Whille (1944), the validity of data obtained during an interview is dependent on the participants' willingness to provide meaningful information that may be utilised to interpret the findings. A quality assurance procedure was followed to ensure that all participants completed the interview and that no questions were declined or that any interviewees left the interview before it was completed. The interviewer's performance influences the overall quality of the interview (Patton 1990). The researcher ensures that the interviews are conducted in a peaceful setting and that the interviewees do

not experience any discomfort or obligation while participating in the interviewees' responses.

All the interviews were scheduled with the respondent's convenience in mind, and all of the applicants were properly informed on the nature and scope of the interview before participating. Before beginning the interview, the responder was asked if there were any concerns or questions that needed to be addressed by the investigator. All of the interview questions were addressed, which helped to create a more pleasant atmosphere between the researcher and the applicants, which in turn helped to boost the validity of the information gathered. The interview was designed as a normal semi-structured interview and was broken into three key portions to allow for a more accurate assessment of the data when they were obtained.

Part one of the interview consisted of an introduction section in which the researcher defined the purpose of the study and explained the questions that will be asked throughout the interview. This section also includes questions designed to break the ice, such as questions about the candidate's background and job responsibilities. Interview confidentiality issues were also discussed and pre-agreed upon before the start of the interview so that everyone feels safe and comfortable once the interview begins.

In the second section, the researcher attempted to get answers to the most relevant issues raised throughout the interview. A discussion was held between the researcher and participants on the perspective of users, the variables that influence their actions, and the business model of digital platforms. All of these questions were derived from the current literature on the subject by the researcher. Furthermore, the researcher introduces the notion of the system and individual characteristics to the respondents to elicit their opinions on these factors and, if feasible, to get information on any other variables that the respondents consider to be significant to them. The researcher enabled the respondents to freely express their opinions and corrected any misunderstandings they may have had about the interview question during the interview.

Part three of the semi-structured interview was the last segment in which the researcher attempted to bring the session to a close by asking the interviewee about country-specific

open-ended questions and discussing any other issues that may have been overlooked throughout the interview. After the interview, the researcher thanked the participants and invited them to ask any questions they may have concerned the interview.

Immediately before conducting the first interview, the researcher explained the expected results from the interview questions in the context of a questionnaire for the online survey that would be used to gather data for the main study. To conduct a web-based survey with the target population, a questionnaire was developed to satisfy their needs. For this reason, the questionnaire was designed to be concise and straightforward to complete to maximise response rates, as mentioned by Couper et al. (2011) and Saunders (2011). (1) The survey instrument was created once appropriate metrics were identified via credible research. (2) The survey instrument was designed in the first portion utilising specific measurement scales to improve the scientific quality of this thesis, which was then presented in the second section.

Several sources in the related literature were used to develop these measurement scales for intention to use, attitude toward use, perceived usefulness, and perceived value creation, including information technology, information systems (IT), information systems (IS), and other studies by Teece (2007) and Bhattacharjee (2007). (2007). Several relevant pieces of literature on digital markets and consumer behaviour in connection to technology, including Schierz et al. (2010), Gao et al. (2012), and others, were used to develop the measuring scales for external variables such as system features and individual differences (2012). offers a thorough description of all measuring scales derived from the literature review and utilised in the main study questionnaire, as well as proof that they have been employed in other research studies in the past When it comes to the second phase of the survey instrument, the measurement constructs and scale items for the newly found variables were developed based on the information gathered during the qualitative interview stage of the main study.

The questionnaire was divided into sixteen sections, with Section A containing four introductory questions about the use of internet platforms in businesses, as well as questions about respondents' age, gender, and individual income level. Section B contained questions about the use of internet platforms in enterprises, as well as questions about the use of internet platforms in general. Section A served as a jumping-off point for the other parts of the report. Perceived utility and perceived value creation were evaluated as antecedent

variables in Sections B and C, which contained three questions in each section. A total of six items were included in Sections D and E, all of which assessed respondents' views toward and willingness to use digital platforms. The core of the questionnaire was comprised of Sections F to P, which included questions assessing the relevance of dependent and independent factors that may influence consumers' acceptance of digital platform adaptation. Sections F to P also included questions assessing the relevance of dependent and independent factors that may influence consumers' acceptance of digital platform adaptation. Q concluded the questionnaire by expressing appreciation to everyone who has taken the time to answer the questions. Respondents were asked to rate their level of agreement with a statement via an online questionnaire, as recommended by previous research (Davis, 1989; Dahlberg et al., 2003; Pousttchi, 2008). Previous research on consumer perceptions of platform adaptation (Mutalemwa, 2014) and willingness to use digital markets (Mutalemwa, 2014) informed the development of the Likert scale (Kuts, 2015).

As a bonus, the Likert scale is often used in quantitative research, especially in web-based surveys, to assess the feelings of participants (Weng and Cheng, 2000; Subedi, 2016).

Numerous scholars have pointed up differences in the literature on the optimal number of steps to take (Gulllone, 2000). Mattell and Jacaby (1972) concluded that "if the criteria is the percentage of scale employed, there is no a priori reason to choose one scale over another." (Jacoby, 1972). As Oliver (2015) and Saunders (2012) pointed out, the most often used rating scale, ranging from 1 to 5, with a mid-point of 5, was utilised in this study, which was the most commonly used rating scale. Respondents were given the option of selecting the intermediate group while still answering the questionnaire instrument as "uncertain," "neither...nor," or "doubtful" at the halfway point. Even though respondents may be tempted to choose the neutral option, the mid-point was preserved due to the peculiarity of the research issue. In addition, the 5-point Likert scale was utilised in line with previous research on platform utilisation surveys to collect data (Lewis; 2016). The survey was carried out among clients in the United Kingdom, and the results were prepared in English after an evaluation of the literature in the field.

Several revisions were made to the web-based survey in response to suggestions, to clarify metrics and cut down on the survey's length. After conducting a preliminary test with two participants, the initial version of the survey questionnaire was changed. Various survey-related criteria, such as the wording of scale items, the structure and design of the questionnaire, the readability and understanding of the questions, and the overall length of the survey, were solicited for input from individuals and experts. These suggestions have been included in the final version of the instrumentation. The instrument's several processes ensured a high degree of refinement and intentional reorganisation, resulting in the preliminary face and internal validity for the measures as a consequence of the refinement and careful reorganisation (Kim, 2010).

The results of this pilot test revealed that the metrics of validity and reliability were both good on the whole. It took 51 questions to complete the final survey, with the bulk of them focusing on perceived factors impacting digital platform usage and flexibility for users. The final poll included 51 questions. It should take no more than five minutes to complete the survey questions. The appendix comprises a copy of the questionnaire, which includes both components, the measuring scales from reputable research and the interview stage, as well as the questionnaire itself.

4.10. Sample strategy and size

Specifically, users of online platforms are the major subject of this research, as indicated at the opening of the thesis. The next section outlines numerous sampling procedures before getting into the sample approach and size that was used to conduct this thesis's research on the consumers in question.

It was not feasible to collect data from the whole population to answer the research questions addressed in this thesis. This necessitated the collection of a sample, which was essential for both the semi-structured interviews and the web-based survey. There are two types of sampling techniques: probability sampling, also known as representative sampling, and non-probability sampling, also known as judgement sampling (Saunders, 2012). Using some kind of random selection, probability sampling is a sampling approach that ensures that every unit in the population has an equal chance of being selected (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Probability sampling is thus often employed in combination with survey and experimental research approaches (Saunders, 2010). Probability techniques such as simple random, systematic random, stratified random, and cluster random are all instances of which include: (Saunders, 2011).

Probability sampling includes random selection; non-probability sampling, on the other hand, does not include random selection. Therefore, the probability of picking each unit from the population is unpredictable. Consequently, non-probability samples fall short of meeting research questions or objectives that depend on statistical inferences about the features of a larger population to be answered (Saunders, 2011). Generalization for non-probability samples, on the other hand, maybe achievable but statistically infeasible in certain cases. Non-probability sampling techniques include convenience sampling, self-selection sampling, purposive sampling, snowball sampling, and quota sampling, among others (Couper et al., 2011).

To choose a predefined number of participants based on their unique experience characteristics for the qualitative phase of the study, the researcher employed non-probability purposive sampling in the interview procedure (Kotharri, 2014). As a result, the interview participants were chosen by the researcher based on their areas of expertise. Expertise was described as a person's combination of knowledge, years of experience, and talents in a particular field of endeavour or activity (Germain and Ruiz, 2009; Nokes et al., 2010). An expert was described as a person who has the essential knowledge and skills for this particular inquiry.

A team of experts was assembled for the study, and they were picked for their expertise in online firm strategy and consumer behaviour in the digital economy. Everyone on the panel was either responsible for making decisions or involved in the strategic decision-making processes of their respective organisations. The researcher interviewed experts from a variety of organisations to ensure that the panel represented a diverse range of expertise.

The bulk of the respondents' contact information was obtained from private data, according to the researcher. The researcher first reached out to specialists by phone or email in April 2021, and then again in June and September 2021, as the study approached its conclusion, to conduct face-to-face interviews with them. The interviews took held in October and November of 2021.

The study's target point was described as customers or users of digital platforms in the United Kingdom by the researcher for the quantitative component of the study.

Customers of online platforms must be defined specifically, and this must be taken into consideration. According to Gonzalez-Felipe et al. (2010), a consumer is defined as a person who attempts to use his or her purchasing power or that of a company. This results in the consumer of online platforms taking into consideration the platform's utilisation and being willing to purchase from it, which is the word used in this study.

According to Schwarz and colleagues, a sample survey was conducted to offer a quantitative description of the survey population (1999). To get a representative sample from the whole population of 840,618 people, the basic random selection strategy in combination with a computer-generated selection was utilised in conjunction with a special probability sampling approach. The initial sample frame consisted of 8,000 clients who were selected at random from a pool of 80,000. The required sample size for this sample frame, with a 90 per cent confidence level and a 5 per cent margin of error, was calculated to be 264 contacts (Wallace and Pfab, 2012). Because of this, the sampling technique was painstakingly carried out to ensure that a wider sampling process could be conducted (Saunders, 2011). As part of the selection process, we removed duplicate and invalid contact information from the sample frame to ensure that each member was only contacted once and that the bounce rate was maintained to a bare minimum. As a result, the final sample frame was revised to contain 6000 email addresses instead of the original 7320.

The overall sample size for this study was 262, with the consumer sample consisting of people who sell their products on several different platforms. The five qualifying criteria that were used to compile the selection list were as follows: It was necessary to create a seller user account to get started. Second, those that were chosen did not have a current (paying) platform membership at the time of their selection. On the other hand, it was expected that online users with user accounts, but no active subscriptions would have some misgivings about paying full price for a subscription and therefore constitute potential buyers of digital platform adaptation. Third, to target persons who actively use digital platforms, a minimum of one visit to an e-commerce website in the six months before the survey's delivery was necessary for selection to target those who use digital platforms. The fourth group excluded from the study were persons who read online news or magazines, since magazines differ from selling platforms in several ways, and therefore are irrelevant to this research in the news context, as previously stated.

On top of that, neither Apple's iTunes Store nor Google's Play Store was included in the sample of persons who downloaded the digital platforms App from either of these stores. Because of Apple and Google's data availability constraints, the number of persons who may be chosen is quite restricted. Users who use digital sites that need registration but do not want to pay a membership fee were discovered via the use of the combination of these five qualifying criteria. They were considered to have the highest ability to embrace and use digital platforms since they were frequent internet users. The sample consumers for this study who were included and omitted from the selection list are summarised in the following table.

Because they are crucial to the future usage of platforms as well as the success of the study endeavour, this group was carefully chosen. Because there were no demographic data for the sampling frame accessible in the database, it was not possible to provide a thorough breakdown of the demographic features of the sample distribution in the database. To avoid this issue, the researcher included questions on gender, age, and monthly income in the survey. Considering that all database users were obliged to register their email addresses with the online platform, it was determined that the sample frame members were an appropriate selection for participation in the web survey. According to Roacch (2013), many strategies were used to attain high response rates. These included: An overview of the study's purpose was provided at the outset of the online questionnaire; the survey instrument was straightforward; the questions were written in perfect English and were free of semantic problems, and the email and web surveys were both visually appealing in their design and layout. Additionally, the survey featured repeated reminders to ensure that participants completed each item thoroughly, hence lowering the number of participants who submitted incomplete responses. It is anticipated that the normal response rate for email surveys addressed to customers of digital platforms is between 8 and 10%, resulting in a forecasted sample size of between 640 and 800 respondents, according to the email marketing expert.

4.11. Validity, reliability, and transferability

A measure of validity in semi-structured interviews often referred to as objectivity (Davis, 1980) or credibility (Lincoln and Guba, 1985), is a measure of how well the interview technique examines what the investigator sought to explore (Willson, 1992). Valid interview data were gathered using several approaches, which are explained in further detail later in this section.

It is difficult to apply the notion of dependability in qualitative research, and it is much more problematic when dealing with the concept of rigour in semi-structured interviews. A study conducted by Curry (2009) found that rigour is strongly associated with reliability in the qualitative research literature and that it is associated with "systematic data collection, organisation, and interpretation using rigorous and widely accepted techniques for research strategy and sampling as well as for data collection, analysis, and interpretation." Semi-structured interviews, which make use of probes, allow the interviewer to get reliable

information from the interviewee (Wilson, 1995). Because they explain both significant concerns mentioned by interviewers and discrepancies in respondents' replies, interviews are crucial tools in the research process (Wilson, 1992). The researcher needed to establish rapport to get precise information and to ensure that the data was reliable (Gordon, 1975). To improve the quality and reliability of semi-structured interview data, a variety of strategies are available. Beginning with the collection of data from expert interviews, the researcher is critical to the success of the project (Curry 2010). For this reason, he needed to become acquainted with the data collection method, which included paying close attention to the subject and reacting to any particularly interesting points raised by the interview subject, which were potentially important to the study and supplemented the data collected. Second, the researcher used audiotapes to ensure that the information gathered during the interviews was correct, which benefited the analysis (Curry et al., 2010). Audiotaping is a commonly utilised aid in semi-structured interviewing approaches since it gives insight into the performance of both the interviewer and the respondents (Barriball 1995). As an added benefit, it avoids the inconsistencies that are inherent in handwritten interview summaries. In the context of quantitative research, dependability refers to the consistency and precision with which measurements are made. However, validity refers to the degree to which a measurement correctly represents the reality of the situation being measured (Schündler, 2011). To be successful in this scientific study endeavour, reliability and validity must be high. A high Cronbach Alpha score indicated scale reliability, which was obtained by a) developing and testing a structured research instrument consisting of a web-based questionnaire with specific questions; and b) obtaining a high Cronbach Alpha score indicated dependability. Before conducting the survey, the instrument was tested and verified by a panel of academic and industry professionals before being used in the survey. According to transferability, the results of the DBA thesis's core research should be reflective of the study's geographic breadth, which is premised on the claim that Because there were only 262 usable respondents in this research, the sample size may nevertheless be considered statistically "large" and representative; hence, transferability to comparable scenarios should be done with caution.

4.12. Data analysis

This section describes the many kinds of data analysis techniques that were used during the research process. First, the researcher's ongoing comparison strategy to analysing semi-structured interviews performed at the beginning of the main study is described in detail in the first section of the paper. It is the second stage of the main inquiry that is used as the foundation for the empirical component of this DBA thesis. It is a cross-sectional web-based questionnaire that has been distributed to users of digital platforms in the United Kingdom to determine their use intentions for digital platform adaptation in the country. Data gathering is an essential component of scientific procedure, especially when advanced statistical techniques are utilised to analyse the information acquired. The Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) approach, which was used to analyse the quantitative data in this investigation, is discussed in further detail in the second section of this paper.

4.12.1. Constant comparative method

The continuous comparative procedure, which is a generally used and analytical methodology, was employed for stage 1 semi-structured interviews as part of the research design (Glaser and Strauss, 2009). Going through the transcribed interview material line by line and labelling significant words, phrases, or chunks of the transcript was part of this procedure. In the qualitative research literature, this process of labelling is also referred to as coding or categorization. During the inquiry, descriptive data were obtained and coded or labelled to provide units of meaning to the descriptive data gathered (Basit, 2003). When comparing and contrasting text segments, the researcher highlighted similarities and differences and classified instances that he considered noteworthy or relevant to the study. With the continual comparative strategy, the researcher adjusted existing codes discovered new codes via a back-and-forth process and then produced categories based on the most relevant codes utilising the results of the procedure. Later, the researcher classified and connected the categories, which resulted in the conclusion of the statistical investigation.

4.12.2. Structural Equation Modelling

Routine analysis (also known as route analysis) is a method for analysing multivariate data that allows the researcher to swiftly analyse functional connections between dependent and independent variables. Structural equation modelling is also known as route analysis. A structural equation model (SEM) was utilised to investigate the set of linkages hypothesised in this thesis's Alpha model. Because of a multitude of factors, the SEM approach is gaining more and more attention. Before beginning any study, it is necessary to raise awareness of a wide range of aspects to better understand complex social processes. SEM, on the other hand, places a greater emphasis on the validity and reliability of the survey instrument. Third, during the past 30 years, structural equation modelling has progressed to the point where it is possible to analyse complex phenomena, including interactions between variables and their interactions (Reinartz et al., 2009). Fourth, SEM software allows for the simulation of direct, mediating, and moderating effects, and it has progressed to a level of usability that is acceptable (Schmacker, 2004).

A large number of researchers do the covariance-based standard error of the mean (CB-SEM) investigations, which they conduct using software like AMOS, EQS, and LISREL. It is necessary to use CB-SEM when several different preconditions exist. CB-SEM is a good method to use when the goal of the investigation is to verify a hypothesis or if the study is confirmatory (as opposed to exploratory). Second, CB-SEM is the most appropriate approach when the research concerns a build with a limited number of components (one or two). Third, CB-SEM is predicated on assumptions about the distribution of information (Hair et al., 2011).

SEM offers an additional useful approach — Partial Least Squares SEM (PLS-SEM), which is unique from CB-SEM — that may be used in conjunction with other techniques. Several studies have concluded that CB-SEM and PLS-SEM are complementary rather than antagonistic approaches (Jöreskog, 1982) and that they should not be used in isolation. PLS-SEM analysis was used as the SEM technique for the quantitative main study. PLS-SEM analysis has earned substantial attention as the leading multivariate analytic tool in strategic marketing research, and it was used as the SEM approach for the quantitative main study (Halland, 1999). According to Anderson and Swaminathan (2011), PLS-SEM is

advantageous for studies in digital platform research, such as users of digital platforms for digital platform adaptation, primarily due to its methodological advantages, which allow researchers to model relationships with a high degree of flexibility. Anderson and Swaminathan (2011) also claim that PLS-SEM is advantageous for studies in digital platform research, such as users of digital platforms for digital platform adaptation, primarily due to its methodological advantages, which enable researchers to model relationships with a high degree (Hair et al., 2014).

Teo and colleagues (2016) and Andreev et al. (2012) employed PLS-SEM to investigate causal connections in consumer adoption characteristics for online payments, respectively. This thesis attempted to apply variance-based SEM to the causal relationships underpinning digital platform adaptation in the United Kingdom, using the unique topic of digital platform adaptation and related viewpoints on mobile payments. PLS-SEM, in addition, is recommended by Hair et al. (2014) for use in exploratory research or the extension of an existing hypothesis. SEM also provides researchers with the ability to study fresh predicted correlations, which may lead to the discovery of critical factor components (Hair et al., 2011). Because of the experimental character of this study, as well as the fact that it took an enlarged approach to the present TAM model, PLS-SEM was used rather than CB-SEM in this investigation. To develop the model, SPSS software was used because of its improvements in terms of a simple and intuitive user interface (SPSS, 2017).

4.13. Methodology process

The study technique was separated into several stages that were completed in succession. The research questions, as well as the study's objective and goals, were established at the commencement of the investigation. Following the end of the project, an evaluation of the literature was begun. The examination of the literature established the study's place in the context of academic literature and scholarly opinions on the subject matter. For this reason, and since digital platform adaptation is a fresh issue, the literature analysis focused mostly upon alternative viewpoints on mobile payments. This step collected information from the literature review and confirmed that the conceptual model included the right set of influencing components. The literature synthesis was completed after the evaluation of the literature.

Following the creation of the research hypotheses, the study was carried out in two stages: phase one and phase two. While the first stage involved semi-structured interviews with a targeted sample of industry executives and experts, the second stage — the most important stage — involved the collection of data from users of digital platforms across the country through an online survey conducted on a national scale. The initial phase included complementing the fundamental conceptual model with features proposed by industry experts who had been specifically tasked with adapting digital platforms to their needs.

The research approach used in the first phase was validated by a pilot study. The findings of the first stage were incorporated into the basic conceptual model, enabling the researcher to develop the entire Alpha model, which served as the basis for the major inquiry of the subsequent stage. To verify the Alpha model and to quantify the research hypotheses, the main study was carried out in a laboratory setting. After reviewing the results of the initial study, the researcher conducted more research, came to conclusions and offered recommendations to academics and industry leaders.

4.14. Pilot study

It was necessary to perform a pilot study to assess the feasibility of the original study design before moving forward with the full-scale interview research project. A pilot study is a trial run that is conducted in advance of the main study with the specific goal of pre-testing the research instrument before the main study begins (Watsson et al., 2007). Pilot studies have a long history of use in both qualitative and quantitative research, and they are still in use today (Teddje, 2010). In this research study, a pilot study was conducted primarily to validate the interview design and content validity, as well as identifying possible obstacles to participation.

The description of the primary study had a significant impact on the method used for the pilot research as well. The amount of information available in the literature on the sample size for pilot trials is limited (Hertzog, 2008). In contrast to probability studies, there are no constraints on the number of participants in non-probability research (Saunders, 2011). The sample size selected by the researcher should be relevant, meet the goals of the pilot study, and be feasible to undertake within the constraints of the available resources, according to Pattan (2002) and Paterrson and Cnam (2001). When doing survey research, Cyota and

Harrison (2006) advocate using a small pilot group, and Creswell (2012) emphasises that qualitative research studies with one or two participants are viable. As a result, the pilot test for this thesis was done with a small sample size of just two pilot participants.

Because of a combination of issues, the researcher was only able to conduct two appropriate pilot interviews: To begin, the first pilot interview yielded sufficient information for the selection of factor candidates. Second, the form, length, and, most importantly, the clarity and quality of the questions in both pilot interviews were suitable. Third, the pilot study generated satisfying results in terms of interviewing and transcription; fourth, both the data collection and analysis techniques were successfully evaluated; and fifth, the findings of the pilot research were published. Sixth, data saturation happened following the end of the two pilot trials, and no more data would have supplied any new insights into the situation. Seventh, there were only a few industry specialists in the United Kingdom who had substantial experience in digital platform adaptation due to time and resource limitations. A sample size of two persons was sufficient for the pilot study's aims since the researcher did not have access to a bigger sample of experts for the pilot study (unless samples from the main study were included; see the next paragraph for further information). For want of a better expression, the sample size was suitable for the job at hand. Two pilot interviews were undertaken as a last step, but only because of the limited resources available.

Because of the danger of contamination, it is generally discouraged in business research to incorporate pilot participants in the main study after the pilot phase (Hundley, 2001). In the case of a pilot study, contamination may arise from one of two sources: first, when data from the pilot study are included in the main findings; and second, when pilot participants are included in the main research, but fresh data are obtained from the same people.

Consequently, respondents to the pilot research were excluded from participation in the main study.

One of the three expert groups was used to choose a purposive sample from which the sample was drawn in a non-probabilistic way. They were both members of the same group of corporate strategy professionals and had been carefully picked by the researcher to be part of the study's pilot participants. The pilot study sample was selected based on the assumption that this expert group had the greatest expertise of the three expert groups in terms of

business models for digital platforms, and so was the best candidate for testing the interview method throughout the research process.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to acquire information for the primary study. A similar research approach was used in the pilot study and was carried over to the main study due to the advantages of eliciting detailed information from participants and clarifying meanings while also comprehending the phenomena of micropayment usage from the point of view of an individual participant (Bryman and Bell, 2014).

The initial interview framework was verified on a small number of pilot individuals. The feedback from the pilot participants was carefully evaluated to guarantee that any problems or inconsistencies with the interview framework were recognised and fixed before the main study could begin.

The pilot interview started with an explanation of the study topic and the informed consent form, followed by a question-and-answer session. Before any participant completed the informed consent form, the researcher answered any questions that the pilot volunteers had for him or her. Aside from that, the interviewees were notified that the session would be recorded on audiotape. Additionally, the researcher said that participation is entirely voluntary, and that the participant has the right to cancel the interview process at any point without giving a reason to the researcher.

Because of the modest sample size, the researcher was able to collect information in a timely and efficient manner. Several weeks before commencing the transcription process, the researcher produced a Microsoft Word template for inputting interview data, which comprised questions (Q), responses (A), and comments (C) in the form of bullet points (C). Following that, the following data collection methods were used for each pilot interview: Beginning with the interview, the researcher instantly transferred the digital audio recording of the interview to his or her computer when it was completed. Second, the researcher listened to the interviewee by playing the audiotape on a media player on his or her computer. Second, the researcher listened to the interviewee by playing the audiotape on a media player on his or her computer. Fifth, the researcher personally transcribed the interview content by listening to the audiotape word for word and then typing it out in an Excel spreadsheet.

Finally, the researcher manually transcribed the audio recorded interview, which was done using a Microsoft Word template. Seventh, the researcher double-checked the transcripts of the interviews to ensure that there were no omissions. Finally, the researcher examined and listened to the audiotape for errors and inconsistencies that could have occurred during the transcribed interviews (numbers eight and nine). The transcription was approved by the researcher on the ninth occasion since there were no omissions.

The perspectives and findings of the pilot group were used to modify the interview guide for the main study and to refine the original research design, which was then used to inform the final design. The four feasibility objectives served as the basis for the success criteria for the pilot project. These were the ones who determined whether or not the main research could be carried on (Thabane et al., 2010). In either case, the framework will be adjusted, or the framework will be used with greater supervision (as opposed to a modified framework).

c) There will be no change) Discontinue primary research owing to the impracticability of the approach

The following objectives were established by the researcher for the pilot interview, the template, and the content validity: (8) Evaluate the interviewer's data collection and analysis skills. (9) Evaluate the amount of tr that was used. (1) Evaluate the interviewer's data collection and analysis skills. (2) Evaluate the clarity of all questions. (3) Evaluate the respondents' refusal to answer any questions. (4) Evaluate omissions. If all of the objectives of the pilot research are accomplished well, the larger study may be restarted at a later date.

4.15. Accessibility:

Because the researcher works for a consulting (accounting firm) company that deals with a large number of organisations, the researcher has a large network of contacts. Moreover, the researcher personally requested access to data required for the study's execution, as well as addressed confidentiality issues and explained the need of maintaining anonymity.

4.16. Research ethics

The research was carried out independently by the author. When preparing the study, the author followed the research ethical rules established by the University of West of Scotland. The qualitative element of the study included conducting semi-structured interviews, documenting responses, and processing the data without the use of a research assistant or other helpers. By providing an informed consent form, the author ensured that participants were aware of the study's purpose and protected their rights. All participants signed the informed consent form once they had been briefed about it. Participants were informed that they had the option to refuse questions or exit from the interview at any moment without having to explain their decision. Additionally, respondents were informed that there were no benefits to taking part in the survey. The interviews were done solely at the participants' discretion. As part of the quantitative aspect of the inquiry, the researcher developed, administered, and processed a web-based survey questionnaire. The author made certain that all responses were kept anonymous. Because the data collection and processing methods lacked subject identities, it was impossible to relate the results to a specific survey question. There was no danger involved in taking part in the research since all that was asked of participants was to complete a questionnaire. The questionnaire was filled out willingly by the respondent. Following the study, the researcher only processed data that was legally obtained. The author kept his or her neutrality throughout the process. The researcher went to great lengths to demonstrate triangulation.

4.17. Conclusion of Chapter 4:

This chapter went into great length on the research approach and methods. The positivist paradigm was used in this research because the study's goal was to find factors impacting the adoption of online digital platforms by employing a conceptual model that comprised a predictive set of assumptions, and the positivist paradigm was the most appropriate choice. The researcher examined both inductive and deductive research approaches and argued for the use of a hybrid methodology. An explanation was provided for the qualitative data gathering method, which used semi-structured interviews. The quantitative data collection technique, which involved an online survey, was also explained in depth. Those who participated in the interviews were industry experts, while those who participated in the web survey were clients of online platforms. The literature was used to guide the design of both the interview framework and the survey. The triangulation of data and procedures was done using many samples and a variety of data collection approaches. The study's ethical considerations were addressed at every stage of the data collection and analysis process, including before, during, and after the research was completed.

The research will summarise the results from the project's first two phases, namely, the pilot research and the main study, in Chapter 6. The pilot study stage of the research project confirms the initial research concept and acts as a basis for the main study stage of this research project, which will take place later on.

5. CHAPTER 5

Findings

The findings of the pilot study are discussed in this chapter, as well as how they informed the whole inquiry. Following the completion of the cumulative study, findings and recommendations are developed, as well as a list of potential future research areas, which are covered in further depth later in the chapter.

5.1. Pilot study

The findings of the pilot study are discussed in this chapter, as well as how they informed the whole inquiry. Following the completion of the cumulative study, findings and recommendations are developed, as well as a list of potential future research areas, which are covered in further depth later in the chapter

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5.1.1. Introduction

To determine the suitability of the data collection approach, interview questions, and analysis, a pilot study was conducted. The pilot study also served as a simulation for the main study. Additional benefits of doing an exploratory study include determining if additional perceived elements impacting usage of digital platforms adaptability in the sector can be found and adding to the original conceptual model generated from the literature review. The questionnaire interview format employed in the pilot study was the same as that used in the main study.

5.1.2. Subject details

The pilot interviews were conducted with two industry experts who were hand-picked for their expertise. One interview took place on June 20th, while the other took place on June 23rd, both in the year 2021, respectively. When referring to pilot participants, pilot

participant 1 is referred to as PP1, and when referring to pilot participant 2, the term is referred to as PP2.

A single-subject was female and another was male, and just their genders were taken into consideration when it came to demographics. This resulted in a sample that did not accurately reflect the gender distribution seen in the initial study. Other demographic information was not obtained since it was deemed unnecessary for the trial study. Both people had full-time roles at companies that were heavily invested in digital media. Given that both parties were engaged in the strategy formulation process, they are both aware of anticipating customer behaviours and needs, which include the use of digital platforms. While one of the members worked in the online marketing department, the other was in charge of developing strategies for the company's shift to a digital-first environment. Both people had extensive experience with business model concepts, with one having six years of experience and the other having more than 10 years. As a result of the above, both interview subjects were highly regarded as industry experts inside their respective organisations.

5.1.3. Data collection process

The majority of the interviews were conducted in English unless otherwise stated. In addition, both pilot applicants were competent in English, which allowed the researcher to include problem terminology into the thesis and check the authenticity and trustworthiness of the information gathered. The researcher began the interview by stating the purpose and anticipated length of the interview, as well as seeking agreement to audiotape and transcribe the responses given by the participants. When all of the procedural obstacles had been resolved, the actual unstructured interview process could begin. Throughout the interview, the researcher made a few notes on prospective interview structure improvements, most of which were related to the issues — for instants, how to improve the transition from one subject to the next — and generally ignored the questions themselves. As a result, the researcher was reliant on the recording to obtain data and, as a result, concentrated on the replies given by the respondents. Following the conclusion of the interview, the researcher expressed appreciation to the pilot subjects for their time and participation, and the audiotaping of the interview was turned off.

In general, the pilot participants were able to grasp all of the questions. However, two exclusions were detected in which questions may have been better worded. The first two interconnected questions were written in pontification style and were much too long

The following question is posed: "What, in your view, are the encouraging characteristics that consumers of online platforms might use to support or accelerate their adoption of digital platforms?"

When it comes to using digital platforms, "What, in your view, are the disincentives that users of online platforms may encounter that may help or accelerate their use of digital platforms?"

During the second interview, the researcher refined these questions by using clearer wording and simplifying them to make them more understandable. During the second interview, there was no shortage of this kind of question.

"What elements, in your opinion, have a positive impact on customers' use of digital platforms?" says the interviewer.

"What elements, in your opinion, have a negative impact on customers' use of digital platforms?" says the interviewer.

For the second time, PP2 sought clarification on the meanings of the items specified in academic literature, as provided by the interviewer in one question:

"Academic study has shown that the following factors influence consumer acceptance of digital platforms: mobility, compatibility, convenience, innovativeness, and knowledge.

Is there a reason why one is more important than the others?"

However, although the interviewer was able to describe the factor definitions in his own words, he was unable to provide answers to queries concerning the subtleties of the external variables, which were believed to be self-explanatory. The interviewer instead covered each of the key study's features with him to ensure that his replies were consistent throughout the interview. Other than that, the researcher's interviewing skills were found to be adequate in the pilot study for the collection of the required data.

In the pilot interviews, none of the participants refused to answer a single question, and each participant had a response for each question. With the exception of a few adjusted transitional questions between the different segments of the interview and a modest alteration to the interview framework, the replies were well-organized. There were no recommendations or

additions to the discussion. Aside from the two instances mentioned above, no further omissions occurred during any pilot interview.

It took 35.13 minutes for the first interview to conclude, and 31 minutes for the second to conclude, both of which were well inside the allotted one-hour time limit. In order to facilitate transcription and data processing, all of the pilot interviews were audio-recorded. In order to manually transcribe the textual content from the interviews, the researcher used a template that had been developed in advance. In addition to providing room for the researcher's comments, this template was excellent for filling out each question and responding to them. A total of 15 pages of text were produced as a result of the pilot investigation.

5.1.4. Data analysis method

A quick manual data analysis was carried out in order to verify the research methodology and methodology and approach. The actual data analysis approach started with the first question of the interview, with any required follow-up questions thrown in for good measure. A Word Documents format was used to turn the interviews into textual data, which resulted in a thorough file that included all of the qualitative information gathered from each interview. The material was divided into sections based on the structure of the interview, with questions and answers included in each section of the document. The fast research confirmed that coding was an appropriate technique for data collection, which was achieved in Word by using different colours to highlight different sections of the text.

According to the results of both interviews, perceived aspects were detected that may or may not be related to the original conceptual model. PP1 provided four additional external variables during the interview: three system characteristics and one individual characteristic. Also emphasised by PP1 was the relevance of the pre-existing antecedent of value-generating in the context of adaptive solutions. Two more reasons were brought up during the discussion with PP2: one was system-related, and the other was personal. Additionally, PP2 stressed the relevance of value creation as well as the utility that it brings with it. The factors discovered in the two interviews were diverse from one another. Following the two pilot experiments, a total of six parameters were discovered, consisting of four system-level characteristics and two individual-level characteristics. The data analysis technique employed in the experiment

was declared suitable, and it was duplicated in the complete study for all interviews once it was shown to be effective.

5.1.5. Results: factor detection

Using the qualitative data collected during the pilot interview with one person (PP1), the results of the pilot interview were compiled and are presented in this section. Due to the fact that this part comprises just one pilot research sample, there have been no comparisons done to other pilot candidates in this area. While doing the main study, it was discovered that there were certain similarities and variations, patterns and trends among the interview participants. A variety of criteria might be identified as promoting consumers' adoption of platforms services in the United Kingdom, according to the results of the pilot interview conducted with PP1. As a result of their responses, the following perceptual inputs were inferred: (1) value creation, (2) universal payment system, (3) transparent communication, and (4) unique value. We will offer a brief evaluation of each of these inputs, followed by a judgement of whether the components qualify as supplementary variables that should be included in the conceptual model of the system.

The responder highlighted value creation as a positive component of adapting to digital platforms three times during the interview, starting with the opening statement.

For the sake of argument, let us assume that Amazon offers business market scanning capabilities. The potential for wealth creation offered by this alternative is important."

"I feel that value creation is vital." PP1: "I believe that value creation is critical."

Digital platforms cannot be designed for a single company or website since they must be flexible, as stated in PP1.

A technology is considered as more useful from the perspective of the client when it provides value, according to the available literature (Wang and Li, 2012). Consumers' faith in the capabilities of digital platforms, especially how digital platforms support them in obtaining information and business-related material, is referred to as perceived value creation in reference to the study's subject (Bruner and Kumar, 2003). As a result, prior to conducting the pilot interviews, the researcher revised the conceptual model to include value creation as

an antecedent variable for attitudes about use. In spite of the fact that the responder recognised this element, it did not qualify as a new variable and was thus excluded from consideration for inclusion in the initial conceptual model.

Another aspect that has been recommended to increase consumer adoption of platform services is the establishment of a universal payment system. In answer to the inquiry, the researcher reduced the interviewee's long circumscriptions into the following phrase: global payment platform:

"Assume I am an Amazon platform customer, but I come across something on E-bay, and if I could pay using my Amazon or any other single universal payment platform, where all of my payment information is already saved, I would easily pay." PP2: "Assume I am an Amazon platform customer, but I come across something on E-bay, and if I could pay using my Amazon or any other single universal payment platform, where all of my payment information is already saved," Alternatively, if I am compelled to pay via another site, I would think twice, if not three times, before handing my bank credentials to that platform." For lack of a better term, the participant presented a solution that is not connected to anyone firm selling channel and can be used by consumers to pay for things across a variety of platforms. PP1 responded to the researcher's inquiry concerning additional issues linked to the adaption of digital platforms that had not been addressed in the prior questions by stating, "I know I've said it before, but I think that every company will eventually migrate to a platform."

The universal payment platform has not yet been discovered by researchers in analogous studies or the context of digital platforms, as has been done by others. Therefore, the author intention was to test this avenue regarding digital platforms as well. The main reason for including this hypothesis even after one participant response is to assess the merits regarding the ability of this variable to impact the digital platforms adaptation. If this variable could be validated by main study than it would not only contribute to existing knowledge via this study but will also open a new avenue for users' acceptance of digital platforms therefore it qualifies as a newly found variable, and as such, it should be included in the fundamental conceptual model. As described by the study, system characteristics may be regarded as a collection of external features that have the ability to influence a consumer's willingness to use a new information system, such as a website or an application (Davis, 1993; Venkatesh,

2000). Customers may pay for goods and services via micropayment services, as the participant points out, thanks to the universal payment platform. As a result, this aspect may unquestionably be regarded as a characteristic of the system. As the last point, it should go without saying that the word "platform" is used in the context of technology or system, rather than a subjectively perceived feature. According to Venkatesh (2000), system qualities have a direct impact on the perceived usefulness and ease of use of a product or service. The responder related the global payment platform feature with perceived value creation ("extremely easy to use" and "would be the easiest approach") as well as perceived utility ("very easy to use" and "would be the simplest technique") ("I would pay soon" and "user would genuinely commit to paying").

Following are some more operational theories that have been proposed as a consequence of this research:

Hypothesis 12

H0: There is no correlation between universal payment platforms and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between universal payment platforms and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 13

H0: There is no correlation between universal payment platforms and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between universal payment platforms and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Third, according to the results of the pilot study, fair communication was shown to be an additional predictor of platform utilisation intention. As stated by the pilot candidate, PP1: "I also feel that communication fairness is vital."

Specifically, this element pertains to the platform's active and transparent presentation of an item's price information. This component should, without a doubt, be included in the fundamental conceptual model as a new variable. It was first unclear to which category this factor belonged, fair communication fits within the categories of system characteristics and personal characteristics. Although this factor provides a reasonable explanation of what to expect when approaching platform use, the researcher classified it as an individual characteristic because it is defined as the principles that govern how and why individuals adopt new technologies (Baggozzi, 2007) and because it provides a reasonable explanation of what to expect when approaching platform use. A number of additional operational hypotheses were created as a consequence of this process:

Hypothesis 14

H0: There is no correlation between Fair communication and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Fair communication and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 15

H0: There is no correlation between Fair communication and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Fair communication and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Additionally, during the pilot research interview, the respondent mentioned distinctive value as a factor influencing his or her attitude toward platform changes. The following is the statement made by PP1:

PP1: "I believe it is disappointing when the platform is not excellent enough, not necessarily because the material is awful, but because it is not distinctive enough for me to pay for it. [...] You create really unique material for people in order to entice them."

According to the interviewee, one method for platforms to provide distinct value to their consumers is via unique content and goods. This is a method through which the consumer may discover the depth and viewpoint of a product on the platform of his choosing. As a result, the following theory is advanced:

Hypothesis 16

H0: There is no correlation between Unique Value and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Unique Value and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

5.2. Pilot study synthesis

The findings suggest that three of the potentially four newly discovered perception aspects linked to the attitude and intention to use platforms have been classed as new variables, with one having been identified as an existing variable. Among the three new elements are one system feature, the universal payment platform, and two individual distinctions, fair communication and unique value, as well as one new system feature, the universal payment platform. The universal payment platform and equitable communication are both concerned with perception aspects, value production, and utility, while distinctive value is just concerned with usefulness and has no other considerations. As a consequence of the pilot investigation, the following additional hypotheses have been proposed:

Hypothesis 12

H0: There is no correlation between universal payment platforms and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between universal payment platforms and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 13

H0: There is no correlation between universal payment platforms and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between universal payment platforms and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 14

H0: There is no correlation between Fair communication and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Fair communication and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 15

H0: There is no correlation between Fair communication and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Fair communication and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 16

H0: There is no correlation between Unique Value and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Unique Value and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Consequently, these operational assumptions have been included in the first conceptual model and shown as the Alpha model (see Figure).

Figure: Alpha-model

Figure 5.1.: Source: Figure by author

The researcher included this additional variable in the conceptual model as a consequence of the pilot. However, it must be emphasised that these new hypotheses were included only in response to the pilot study's PP1 respondent's remarks. Stage one of the primary investigation evaluated this proposed concept in further detail. If confirmed by responders, this would next be tested in the main study's second stage.

Several adjustments to the Alpha model were made during the inquiry. It was decided to use the Alpha 1 model after taking into consideration the characteristics that were found during the main research interviews (stage one). In a second step, the hypothesised connections were tested on a larger primary sample (stage two), which resulted in the development of the Alpha 2 model. The structural research model was termed Beta 1 because it revealed t-values later in the statistical research process; the final research model, which displayed path coefficients, was labelled Beta 2 because it presented path coefficients. Beta 2 is the final version of the research model.

The use of semi-structured interviews as a research method has shown to be effective in achieving the objectives of this study. During the main research study, no difficulties were uncovered that may jeopardise the project. Pilot studies were considered successful if it was feasible to proceed with the major research in one of the following ways: a) with an entirely different context; b) with the same frame but with diligent management; c) with no modification; or by quitting the primary study due to its impracticality (Thabane et al., 2010).

Main study: interview stage one

5.3. Introduction

The results of the semi-structured pilot interviews were addressed in the section that preceded them. The pilot study assisted in the construction of the Alpha model as well as the determination of the applicability of the interview guide. This section will detail the findings of the main study, as well as an analysis of the research methods and a discussion of the hypotheses that were created as a consequence of the evaluation of the literature.

According to the main survey, attitudes toward and intentions to use digital platforms for business in the United Kingdom were examined to determine the elements that influenced such attitudes and intentions. In order to do this, a dual method was used: first, an evaluation of user perception aspects in a commercial context, followed by validation of these features among internet users. In order to offer a complete list of traits and features that serve as a strong basis for investigating the relational model, a two-step approach was developed and implemented. The effect of both phases — corporate and consumer views — on the actual usage of digital platform adaptation in the United Kingdom may be proven as a result of this investigation.

An external variable classification system features and individual factors are included in the holistic research model. These variables are also related to the antecedents of perceived value creation and perceived usefulness, the mediating factor attitude, and their impact on the adaptation to digital platform usage are also included in the holistic research. The primary goal of the core model was to identify the variables that impact consumer behaviour when it comes to digital platforms.

5.3.1. Subject details

As previously stated, nine experts (P1, P2, P3,... P9) from diverse industrial sectors participated in the primary study's semi-structured interviews. The experts were listed in Table. As advised by Lancaster et al., all experts were precluded from participation in the pilot project (2004). The interviews took conducted between the 17th of October and the 9th of November, 2021, in the applicants' respective places of employment or by video conference, depending on the conditions. Six males (67%) and three women (33%) were among the specialists that participated (33 per cent). Following the pilot research, no more demographic information was collected from participants, since this information was irrelevant at this stage of the main study. All specialists had long-term managerial positions, influencing strategic management choices, and demonstrating experience in their respective roles with digital platforms or industry-observing companies. Additionally, three experts (P3, P5, P6) worked directly with particular online digital platform firms in the United Kingdom, while two experts (P7, P8) worked indirectly with specific online digital platform businesses. P1 and P2 possessed extensive experience with technology acceptance strategies for businesses in general. Additionally, P4 has a demonstrated track record of transaction understanding in the digital platforms sector across many industrial sectors. Additionally, with over two decades of expertise in the electronic payments sector in the United Kingdom and Europe, P9 has been doing business online since 2000. As a consequence, each of the nine experts was uniquely suited to contribute significantly to the primary research.

5.3.2. Interview process

The data for the first stage of the primary research was gathered via the use of a semi-structured interview form. The same questionnaire interview guide that was utilised in the pilot study was employed in this study. The qualitative data analysis procedure was time-consuming and complex. Nine interview tapes ranged in length from 25 to 49 minutes, and a total of 5:48:42 hours of spoken information was transcribed from them. The transcripts were listened to multiple times before being read for themes and then coded and organised into categories, with citations to sources, and finally recorded in a comprehensive summary sheet. An enormous amount of information was gleaned from the interviews. In order to ensure data organisation and make sense of the textual content, this huge amount of text must be coded before it can be analysed (Bassit, 2004).

5.3.3. Quantifying the interview material

This section describes the method of quantifying the interview results via the use of coding before moving on to the qualitative analysis of the interviews. The frequency of individual and group data needs a plain presentation of the results in tables, which reflects the frequency of individual and group data. As a result, the frequency indicators provide a preliminary impression of the distributions within the data material and contribute to the transparency and verifiability of the qualitative interview research (Flick, 2004).

As a consequence of the nine interviews that were performed, eight criteria were identified. In regard to the fundamental conceptual model shown in Figure, four components that were previously existent were evoked, and one new determinant was discovered. Each set had two system-level characteristics as well as two individual-level differences. In the initial interview study, four out of five of the original conceptual model's five aspects were confirmed; just one element was found to be incorrect. The entire interview research also confirmed all three of the criteria that were discovered in the pilot interview study, so strengthening the Alpha model. The following table provides an overview of the recommended frequency as well as a visual representation of the balanced factor distribution.

Factors Overview

Category of external variables	Existing Factor	New Factor	Factors not Identified
System Characteristics	2	2	1
Individual Characteristics	2	2	0
SUM	4	4	1

Table 5.1.: Source Main study data.

A minimum of three and a maximum of six variables were discovered throughout the interviews. In each interview, an average of 4.33 variables were supplied by each participant. For example, in the interview, a value of 0 indicates that there was no identification, whereas a value of 1 shows that there was a successful identification.

Factors		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	SUM
1	Mobility	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	5
2	Compatibility	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	Convenience	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	6
4	Later Payment	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	4
5	Single Payment Platform	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	5
6	Innovativeness	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
7	Knowledge	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	4
8	Perceived Trust	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	7
9	Perceived Content relevance	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	7
SUM		5	4	5	4	3	6	5	3	4	
AVERAGE		4.33									

Table 5.2.: Factors identification

PTR perceived content relevancy, and innovativeness were the most often identified criteria in each interview, with a total of seven occurrences each, while the least frequently identified element was perceived trust (INN). Aspects of compatibility were the only ones that were not mentioned in any of the interview responses (COM).

Table: Factors Comparison

NO	Factor	Frequency of factor	Rank	Factor mentions per interview	Rank
1	Mobility (MOB)	5	3	19	5
2	Compatibility (COM)	0	0	0	9
3	Convenience (CON)	6	2	41	2
4	Later payment (LPM)	4	4	16	6
5	Single payment platform (SPP)	5	3	32	3
6	Innovativeness (INN)	1	5	1	8
7	Knowledge (KNO)	4	4	5	7
8	Perceived trust (PTR)	7	1	45	1
9	Perceived content relevance (PCR)	7	1	31	4
Total		39		190	

Table 5.3.: Factors Comparison

5.4. Analysis process

The textual analysis's major purpose was to discover codes and categories that were thought to be important in consumers' usage of digital platforms. Until the findings were given, the analytical procedure was repeated numerous times using the constant comparative method. This included going line by line through the prepared interview material, identifying patterns and themes, and then labelling pertinent words, phrases, or parts as codes for each interview. The following sections describe and explain the many processes of code creation that were

carried out manually to produce a cohesive collection of codes from the qualitative interviews. The three-step procedure is shown in Figure, along with an explanation of each stage.

Figure 6.2.: Coding

Figure 5.2.: Source: Researcher

Step 1: Initial category detection

After identifying parallels and contrasts in the textual content from each independent interview, the researcher next decided if relevant information belonged under a single topical heading. At this point, the researcher made a note of the titles of the summarised themes on the right-hand side of the transcribed interview sheet's codes box on the right-hand side of the interview sheet. Through a back-and-forth reading process of all interviews, themes that were similar or related were combined into a category family. Using this strategy, we were able to identify new themes while also refining categories that had already been identified earlier. Finally, the categories that were found were represented in a simple schematic map, as illustrated in Figure.

Figure: Initial detection

Figure 5.3.: Source: Author.

Step 2: Clustering categories and creating codes:

A refinement of the previously created initial categories was achieved by the identification of the characteristics that distinguish each unit from the others. Later, as shown in Figure, the researcher classified clusters by categorising units that had the same meaning or words that were joined together that were linked together. Three categories were identified: one for basic codes, another for more difficult codes, and a third for all codes. For example, group three was straightforward since speedy access to digital platforms is a need for convenience and, as a result, is directly related to a pleasant user experience in the study environment. As a consequence, the researcher merged the two categories and labelled the code after its primary objective, which was the ease of the user. However, cluster one is a more complex example, including the categories of relevance, value, extra value, and distinguishing value into a single unit of analysis.

After many cycles of analysing the textual material, the researcher was able to construct a consistent understanding of the relevance and the various sorts of worth, despite the fact that definitions of relevance and value are different. As stated by the responder, the relevancy of unique content results in monetary worth, additional financial value, or unique financial benefit for each consumer. Therefore, the fundamental issue is perceived content relevance by the particular user, which results in an incentive to achieve a given level of value. In Figure, all clustered categories that have been determined to code at this point of the analytic process are listed, with the primary code highlighted in boldface type.

Figure 5.4: Codes creation

Figure 5.4.: Source: Author.

Step 3: Developing final factors set

Finally, a particular name for each code was generated, together with a common name for the clusters, in order to arrive at a concrete expression. Additionally, the codes were categorised according to system features or individual variances. The final set of codes represents the variables found during stage one of the primary study's interviews. The figure depicts an overview of the components grouped according to their respective category.

Figure 5.5.: Final factors set from interviews.

Source: Author.

5.5. Descriptions of system characteristics

Four system features were identified during the primary study's interviews with nine experts, indicating a beneficial influence on consumer usage of platform services. The next sections discuss the function of each factor namely convenience (CON), mobility (MOB), and later payment (LPM). The next sections address the factors unique to the project and their links to the antecedent variables perceived utility and perceived value generation.

5.5.1. Mobility

To begin, mobility was identified as a perceived element in customer usage of Platforms services. According to the experts questioned a variety of distinct characteristics impact mobility in the context of the industry. The first and most crucial quality noted is the inherent mobile technology that enables consumers to access digital platforms at any time and from any location. The respondents commented on this feature using the following expressions:

P3: "The reluctance to purchase anything in the evening while sitting on the sofa with our cellphones is significantly reduced... we know that purchases are done in the evening and on mobile."

P6: "As a merchant, you offer a service to the user [...] at any time and from any location." The experts' views about the pervasive nature of mobile technology in connection to digital platform adaption are reminiscent of prior study results in relevant studies on mobile services (Wiedeman, 2009). Contrary to the importance placed on time and location freedom, the remarks reveal a fundamental issue: customers do not want to be concerned about whatever device or location they use to consume information. This problem is concerned with the concept of 'polarisation of mobile technology services,' as well as the function of portable devices in the consumption of news in the mobile age (Schnaueber, 2015). The findings suggest that not only are producers of material for digital platforms crucial to mobile internet users but their news content also dominates mobile information.

In addition, the influence of low-cost digital mobile service offers, according to one participant, is a consideration that should be considered in the context of digital platform adaptation. According to the expert, these products and services have led to a rise in the use of mobile devices:

P1: "With the rapid growth of mobile devices over the previous several years, mobile digital services [...] have emphasised low-cost offerings."

This trait associated with mobility was previously unknown in the literature and has not been explored in the main study's empirical section. However, two responders followed up on this point and increased consumer approval of digital platform adaption through mobile devices by emphasising the technical infrastructure feature directly. They noted that a mobile purchasing procedure should not just replicate the desktop checkout process, but rather adhere to mobile communication standards to alleviate the consumer's burden of supporting digital platform adaption. One expert substantiated this trait with the following statement:

P3: "I believe that a significant portion of digital platform adaption has occurred on mobile devices and that this trend will continue. I believe that your items must be really mobile-centric, as well as your payment method. [...] That, I believe, is a significant influence."

In summary, the semi-structured interviews revealed that mobility is a critical factor in the adoption of digital platforms and is driven by three factors: ubiquity, the allure of low-cost offerings, and technical infrastructure. Prior to the pilot and main interviews, the Mobile capability was included in the initial research model as an independent factor in the category of system characteristics that influence attitude to use. As a result, the results of the main research confirmed mobility as a significant characteristic, as well as its correlations with perceived value generation and perceived usefulness. As a consequence, the following assumptions from the fundamental research model were re-examined and confirmed:

H0: There is no correlation between Mobility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Mobility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H0: There is no correlation between Mobility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Mobility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

5.5.2. Convenience

According to six out of nine experts, ease is a key component in the adoption of digital platforms. Confirming findings from previous research (Obe and Balogu, 2007), all respondents identified convenience as a foundation for digital platforms, with the purpose of aiding customer adaptation to the online experience. As a result, the easiness factor was determined to be beneficial to a positive customer experience, which in turn helps to platform acceptance.

Among the first characteristics indicated by the vast majority of experts was simplicity, which is defined as the absence or lack of complexity in the process of customising the digital platform in question. People are goal-oriented because they know they can get what they want on the internet if they are focused on what they want (Nielsen and Levy, 1994). That is, internet clients, disregard any obstacles that stand in the way of their desire to use digital platform services. The experts made the following points, which are summarised below:

P2: "It has to be so simple that we aren't burdened with long and difficult registration, verification, and payment processes." P3: "It has to be so simple that we aren't burdened with lengthy and difficult registration, verification, and payment procedures."

P3: "The most significant hindrance to platforms is their complexity, which reduces the opportunity for value creation and the speed factor."

The two phrases above, "long... payment processes" and "speed factor," both pertain to the second component of platform services: quick access to information and resources. When customers think about using a platform, they want a simple and straightforward experience, according to the experts. Despite the fact that they did not comment on the phenomena of rapid access, it is reasonable to assume that it refers to instant access; otherwise, it is insignificant. User annoyance is increased by slow web services, according to one expert, since they reduce the immediacy of digital platform services online and increase user frustration:

The sharpness, quickness, and immediacy of a transaction are all factors that I feel should be taken into consideration by digital platforms in order for them to adapt.

A third participant highlighted the connection between these two related traits as a component of the convenience factor that contributes to ease of use:

"How come I have to pay for the content?" wonders P4. The use of online platforms is convenient. It ought to be easy, easily available, simple to use, and fast to respond."

The third dimension mentioned by interviewers is one-click shopping, which allows consumers to make online purchases with a single click after previously completing the payment information required to complete the transaction, according to the survey. According to the respondents, this attribute relates to customer information that has been predefined, such as their address or credit card information that has been used to make payments on digital platforms. In terms of adopting digital platforms, the experts came to the following conclusion:

P2: "We may be able to purchase things with a single click."

p3: "I feel that the effectiveness of one-click payment is due to the fact that it is really one-click."

The expert responses and relevant literature on mobile payments all employ the same wide definition of convenience, however, neither the expert answers nor the relevant literature on mobile payments uncovered any of the three qualities identified in the semi-structured interviews or vice versa. As a result, convenience is seen as a complex entity with a diverse set of characteristics and attributes. Briefly summarised, the statistics from the interviews reveal that convenience is a mix of simplicity, fast access, and one-click payment options, all of which are commonly considered to be characteristics of digital platform adaptation. Just like with mobility, the convenience variable was included in the initial research model as a system feature that was related to perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, attitude, and willingness to take advantage of digital platform adaptation.

As a consequence of the main study interviews, it has been established that convenience is an important component of the research model, and the following operational assumptions have been reinforced:

H0: There is no correlation between Convenience and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Convenience and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H0: There is no correlation between Convenience and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Convenience and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

5.5.3. Later payment

Nearly half of individuals who answered the survey's questions said that they used digital platforms, especially those that provide services, as a key motivation for doing so. In contrast to traditional upfront offers, respondents recommended that purchasers should first experience the items before making a purchase. The following statements serve to underline this idea further:

P5: The fifth point is that "[...] in which customers must first top-up [money] in order to progress, according to the report. What you're saying is utterly ineffective."

P6 (sixth): "In fact, if you visit the Spiegel Plus website, you will see that there is no registration cost to pay upfront. You are not here to establish a long-term connection with someone. You just have to pay when you reach the five-euro barrier."

According to the experts, the price should be established after the buyer's experience has been assessed. This gives the consumer the opportunity to view, test, and evaluate the items before deciding on a purchase price. Two respondents highlighted why the post-pricing procedure is vital, stating that platforms must reduce consumer risk or rejection of a digital platform's product upfront, as well as express the supplier's value and trustworthiness to customers and partners. Aim: Prioritize the client in order to convince consumers that the cost is reasonable and reasonable.

Throughout the analytic procedure, the researcher noticed a significant issue with the remarks on post-pricing, which he resolved. Due to the respondents' belief that consumers have the option of paying after reading, they believe that their kindness will not be monetized. To address this basic problem, one potential solution is allowing the consumer to choose their own price, which is referred to in the managerial business literature as 'personalised pricing'

(Reisman, 2017). The challenges that platforms face while attempting to handle this open subject, on the other hand, are not addressed in this research project since they are not the study's primary purpose. A direct remark on the billing issue was given by two additional respondents, who said that consumers should be taxed at the completion of the reading session:

P7: The seventh position is "When a firm shows trust in its customers, it should say, "You may continue purchasing; you may acquire everything you want." Following that, we'll send you an email with the bill attached. There should be as little pain and disturbance to the [shopping] flow as possible for the user."

P9: The ninth letter of the alphabet "The end of the month or the next day is the time when transactions are invoiced since clients loathe paying for items in advance. It is necessary for digital platforms to be treated as a service, with payment only required once you have used and are happy with them."

To conclude, all participants confirmed that post-pricing should be implemented. For the payment process, one interview group (P5, P6) was unsuccessful, whereas the other interview group (P7, P8) was specific about the billing option they preferred for a defined amount of time, as seen in Figure 1. In previous tests, either in the context of identical experiments or in the context of digital platform adaptation, researchers did not identify later payment. So the component discovered by interview specialists qualifies to be included as a new variable in the basic research model, which is what was done in this case.

In contrast to mobility and convenience, the semi-structured interviews indicated that there were no distinguishing characteristics or dimensions for future payment. In light of the fact that the respondents made no specific mention of value creation or utility, the researcher linked eventual payment to both perception factors and evaluated their relationship to attitudes and intentions to adapt to digital platforms. Later payment is a system feature rather than an individually experienced advantage since it refers to a technology or service rather than an individual's experience with it. Therefore, the following unique correlations are proposed for inclusion in the exploratory area of the main study, as a consequence of the findings:

H0: There is no correlation between Later payment and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Later payment and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 9

H0: There is no correlation between Later payment and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Later payment and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

5.5.4. Single payment platform

When asked why they use digital platforms, over half of those questioned said it was because of delayed payment. This was especially true of those who provided services. In contrast to traditional upfront offers, respondents recommended that purchasers should first taste the items before making a purchase. This is emphasised in the following sentences:

The fifth point is (P5) "Where customers must first deposit [money] before proceeding, this is referred to as a [...] What you're doing is utterly ineffective."

Number six, or P6, is the sixth letter of the Greek alphabet "The Spiegel Plus website indicates that there is no registration charge upfront, which is correct. You are not here to establish a long-term connection with another person or couple. After reaching the five-euro mark, you will be charged."

According to the experts, the price should be established after the buyer's experience has been evaluated. Customers may check, test, and evaluate the items before agreeing to a price because of this provision. Two respondents highlighted why the post-pricing procedure is vital, stating that platforms must reduce consumer risk or rejection of a digital platform's product upfront, as well as convey the supplier's value and trustworthiness to customers and prospects. Aim: Prioritize the client in order to convince users that the cost is fair and reasonable.

During the course of the analytic procedure, the researcher discovered a significant difficulty with the remarks on post-pricing. This problem originates from the interviewees' belief that consumers have the choice of paying after reading, and as a result, their kindness may not be monetized. This basic question may be addressed by allowing customers to choose their own price, which is referred to as 'personalised pricing' in the managerial business literature (Reisman, 2017). This research project, however, does not address the challenges that platforms face while attempting to handle this open subject, since this is not the study's primary goal. In response to the billing issue, two additional respondents said explicitly that clients should be taxed after the reading session has concluded, as follows:

The seventh point is (P7) "When a firm shows trust in its customers, it should say, "You may continue purchasing; you may purchase anything you want." A bill will be sent to you through email after that. Users' discomfort and disturbance of [shopping] flow should be minimised to the greatest extent possible."

P9: The ninth letter of the alphabet is "The end of the month or the next day is the time when transactions are billed since clients loathe paying for goods upfront. It is necessary for digital platforms to be treated as a service, with fees charged only after you have used and are happy with them."

All respondents agreed that post-pricing should be implemented. For the payment process, one interview group (P5, P6) was unsuccessful, whereas the other interview group (P7, P8) was specific about the billing option they preferred for a defined amount of time, as shown in the table. In previous trials, either in the context of identical experiments or in the context of digital platform adaptation, researchers were unable to identify later payment. So the component discovered by interview specialists qualifies to be included as a new variable in the basic research model, which will be implemented in the following manner: For future payment, there were no distinguishing characteristics or dimensions, in contrast to mobility and convenience, according to the semi-structured interviews.

Since the respondents made no specific mention of value creation or utility, the researcher linked eventual payment to both perception factors and investigated their relationship to attitudes and intentions to adapt to digital platforms. Later payment is a system feature instead of an individually experienced advantage since it is associated with a technology or service rather than a person. As a consequence, the inclusion of the following fresh connections in the exploratory phase of the main study is proposed:

H0: There is no correlation between Single payment platforms and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Single payment platforms and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 9

H0: There is no correlation between a Single payment platform and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Single payment platforms and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

5.6. Descriptions of individual differences

Apart from identifying system features, experts explored a variety of individual distinctions associated with four aspects affecting consumer usage of micropayment services: innovativeness (INN), micropayment knowledge (KNO), perceived risk (PR), and laws and regulations (LAW). The next sections describe these characteristics and their relationship to the antecedents — perceived value creation and perceived usefulness.

5.6.1. Innovativeness

Only one expert, out of nine, believed that innovativeness was critical in determining consumer acceptance of digital platform adaptation, which was already a significant component in previous online purchase studies (Yi et al., 2006). An individual's tendency for testing and experimenting with new methods, especially when it comes to online purchasing, was classified as innovativeness in the expert interview as follows: As an added bonus, the participant saw that these customers exhibited a penchant for embracing riskier technologies such as Amazon or Uber through their mobile devices. Additionally, despite the fact that the participant did not specify the characteristics of the aforementioned group of persons, the expert attributed innovativeness to a specific target audience:

P1: "Innovation is crucial, depending on the target audience [...] to correctly address that target audience." P2: "Innovation is critical, depending on the target audience [...] to properly address that target audience."

The most noteworthy feature of the above is that the expert advised innovativeness as an essential trait since the target audience for innovation expects new technologies to be introduced into the platforms of organisations. For platform owners to satisfy the expectations of a knowledgeable audience about innovation on websites, they must respond to their users' own innovativeness in order to influence their willingness to utilise digital platforms. It's safe to conclude, based on our discussion with P1, that the perceived usefulness of innovativeness will have a substantial influence on users' attitudes toward digital platform services. Innovation was added as a separate aspect in the initial research model in section 2.8.6.1 and was promptly confirmed via the main study interviews, which were conducted as part of the study.

The following are the relevant operational assumptions that have been formulated:

H0: There is no correlation between innovativeness and the perceived Value creation of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between innovativeness and the perceived Value creation of digital platforms by consumers.

5.6.2. Knowledge

On the topic of how platform knowledge should be conceptualised, experts expressed a variety of points of view. One of the first characteristics is being aware that a certain service is available via a digital platform, which is backed by the following statements:

P2: The second paragraph is a paraphrase of the first paragraph "Another important component, in my opinion, is understanding of the subject matter. Individuals must be aware of the existence of internet-based platforms."

P7: "Knowledge is the most important factor to consider."

The statistics also revealed another characteristic: clients with minimal awareness of online platforms and connected websites tend to concentrate on the most enticing parts, while users with higher web competence discern between new and less innovative offerings. Although this finding from the experts is tangential to the results of Rieh (2004)'s literature assessment,

it was revealed that experienced online users filter away irrelevant stuff on the internet as a result of their knowledge of the internet. Customers who have a thorough comprehension of digital platforms, according to the semi-structured interviews, would have an easier time adapting to digital platforms than customers who do not have this expertise.

According to the interviews, the third knowledge-related quality highlighted is time, as indicated by P5: "Doing business via digital platforms [...] demands some time to educate the user, to make them aware [that it exists and can be utilised]."

Clearly, the expert said, there is an adaptation and learning process that individuals must go through in order to get familiar with digital platforms, and this process will take time. The statement above is a fantastic instance of how technological advancements influence consumer behaviour. Consumers are changing and moulding their behaviour at a pace that is commensurate with technology improvements, such as the introduction of new payment mechanisms on news portals, among other things.

In summary, the replies to the interviews revealed that platform knowledge includes an individual's awareness of the existence of digital platforms, as well as their offerings, online experiences, and the passage of time between them. In keeping with the concept of innovation, the initial research model included the variable of platform knowledge as an individual difference relative to perceived ease of use, which was confirmed by an expert interview. It was discovered in the main study that platform knowledge is an important component of the research model:

H0: There is no correlation between Knowledge and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Knowledge and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

5.6.3. Perceived trust

Risk and trust were often highlighted in expert replies; in fact, they were referenced in seven out of the nine interviews conducted with experts (two experts, three industry observers). The opinions of the participants described trust as a consumer's faith that a platform would meet their expectations, especially when it comes to monetary transactions for purchases made on digital platforms. The term "perceived risk" was used in this study since trust is a subjective

view based on the consumer's past experiences, and the researcher referred to it as such. Trust was often mentioned by respondents, with phrases such as "it's all about trust," "a way of trusting," "Trust, yes!" "trust-based system," "risk transfer," "risk translation," and "no risk" are frequently used as examples. When it was observed that the last four assertions were all connected to a similar theme, it was determined that they represented the construct's first dimension. As mentioned in P6, the translation or transfer of perceived risk has a direct impact on user confidence in the payment infrastructure: "[platforms] will have to transform trust into a risk that is no longer in the user's possession."

Customers want confidence and security in processes and payment methods, which, according to experts, has a positive impact on customers' sentiments about the use of digital platform technologies. When it comes to financial transactions, one example that was brought up during the conversation was the uncertainty caused by fraudulent efforts, which had to be prevented by platform owners and positively translated into the privacy wanted by the consumer. Consequently, in the case of digital platform adaptation, this element is primarily driven by technology, whereas the second highlighted feature of a trust is tied to the brand of the platform offering the technology, as previously stated. Customers' confidence in the capabilities of the platform brand was shown to be the most important factor in determining trust in the provider of digital platforms. These characteristics were related to the platform's reputation, which increases over time and adds to the perception of trust in the firm by the customer.

Transparency was indicated as the third criterion of trust in the interviews as well. A superior service to users that generates perceived trust is described as encouraging consumers' adoption of digital platforms via the provision of superior service to users that foster perceived trust. This was validated by P1: "We observed that customers are prepared to pay a premium for a product that is obvious."

In accordance with one participant's observation, fairness is the fourth attribute highlighted as being crucial in influencing perceived trust: P7: "It's critical not to stifle someone's desire for fairness in their life."

In the opinion of the expert, "fairness" is defined as the capacity of consumers to exit the payment process at any time without paying any expenses, enabling the user to make an

independent decision about whether to continue or stop. Consequently, the customer is not exposed to the financial consequences of unmet expectations, which reduces the perceived risk of doing business with the company.

For the purposes of summarising the findings on perceived risk, four construct aspects were identified: trust in the payment's infrastructure, trust in the provider of digital platforms, transparency, and fairness. This variable was classified as an indication of individual differences since trust is dependent on customer perception and is seen differently by each person.

Following are some of the operational theories that have been presented as a consequence of this:

H0: There is no correlation between Perceived trust and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Perceived trust and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 7

H0: There is no correlation between Perceived trust and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Perceived trust and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

5.6.4. Perceived content relevance

Another aspect that has been identified as facilitating the adoption of digital platforms is the relevance of the material. Consumers consider online information to be relevant if they find it suitable in relation to the product they want to buy, according to the participants.

Consequently, the consumer's viewpoint and knowledge of the product dictate the relevance of material, and it is obvious that the consumer's perception of relevance overcomes objectivity in determining the relevance of content. As a result, the term 'perceived content relevance' was coined to describe the findings of this study. [A number of comments](#) from interviewees speak to the value of the concept, such as: "Without actual relevance, the buyer would not pay." P1: The relevance of a product is connected to the demand of the customer. In order for anything to be relevant, it must meet the needs of the client.

The fifth point is that "[relevance] requires presenting individuals with material that they really want to consume."

"Whether or not you are willing to pay for digital platforms is determined by the content."

P4:

A total of three perspectives on its conceptualization in connection to the adoption of digital platforms were offered by the experts questioned: the opinions on user-centricity, quality, and time, which are described in further depth below, According to the definition, user-centricity is a business strategy that places the needs of the customer first while still providing economic value:

P6: "Platforms that do not embrace user-centricity will be doomed to extinction."

"A transfer of ownership has happened from the platform's owner to the user," says P6.

User-centricity, on the other hand, is dependent on how platforms define the client, whether that client is a future or present news consumer, according to the study. Unfortunately, the experts were unable to specify what kind of customer they were referring to in their report. The only thing that can be predicted is that all consumer categories will need more attention in order to discover content that is both valuable and influential in their opinions about the use of digital platform adaptation. The experts advised that, in order to satisfy the specific focus, personalised information and an individualised experience be provided.

The second factor, which is related to perceived content relevance, is the level of quality. Participants expressed concern that a lower-quality product would reduce the perceived relevance of the information they were receiving.

P4 (fourth): "It's very difficult [for platforms] to sustain a high level of quality over long periods of time. In other words, a certain quality level is ultimately what acts as the basis [for the consumer]."

Others argued that a balance between high-quality and original content would be necessary to encourage people to pay for access to digital networks. According to the decision, an original and unique material that is not accessible on any other platform is exclusive and distinguishable from the competition. According to one respondent, there is a relationship between quality and the availability of specialised information. While respondents' definitions of quality varied, they all agreed on the need of maintaining a high-quality standard in general in order to maintain the perceived relevance of the material.

It is the third quality that determines whether the user considers the information to be relevant, and it is this characteristic that influences their attitude toward digital platform adaptation. P5 and P1 provided the following comments about this characteristic in response to the question:

In P5, he says, "It's really about giving people with anything they want to watch at any given moment."

P1: "Products are meaningful to the consumer [...] in terms of substance or length." P2: "Products are meaningful to the consumer [...] in terms of substance or duration."

To summarise the results from this section, three construct aspects are important in determining perceived content relevance: user-centricity, quality, and timeliness. Content relevance, like perceived trust in the previous section, is subjective in nature, and as such, it was classified as an individual feature. It was not previously discovered in the appropriate literature or platform research that the content was judged to be significant. It is a newly discovered variable that will be included in the initial research model to be developed. It is hypothesised to have a two-fold impact on perceived value creation and perceived usefulness. The following hypotheses have been put forward:

H0: There is no correlation between Perceived content relevance and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Perceived content relevance and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

Hypothesis 7

H0: There is no correlation between Perceived content relevance and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Perceived content relevance and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

5.7. Syntheses of findings

Eight external variables were discovered in nine semi-structured interviews, and they were divided into two categories. Specifically, in the domain of system characteristics and individual variances Expert interviews revealed that the construct of compatibility, which was identified as a system attribute in a study of similar mobile payment studies, had not been confirmed in the field. Overall, all three constructs from the pilot study interviews were confirmed in the main study interviews, supporting the initial correlations between the variables of single payment platform, perceived trust, and perceived content relevance in the research model that had been established earlier on. In a similar vein, the existing constructs of mobility, convenience, innovativeness, and expertise — all of which have been shown to influence perceived usefulness, perceived value creation, attitude toward, and intention to use digital platforms — were confirmed in the primary study interviews, confirming previous findings.

During the coding analysis, each notion was scrutinised for specific characteristics that ease adoption and, as a result, have an influence on the adaptation of digital platform architectures. It has been determined that mobility is constituted of three characteristics: ubiquity, cost-effectiveness, and technological infrastructure (or infrastructure). It was determined that ubiquity closely corresponded to the findings of the studies conducted by Newmaan et al. (2015) and Mitcihell et al. (2016). When it comes to the adoption of online digital platforms, convenience has been identified as a significant facilitator of adoption, notably in terms of simplicity, one-click payment processing, and quick access to the payment process. Later, it was determined that payment was solely reliant on the post-pricing aspect of the product. Single payment platforms, according to experts, are an essential external element that promotes the usage of digital platforms by providing a single content platform that also serves as a single payment platform, where users may pay using a range of payment methods. Perceived innovativeness has an impact on perceived competitiveness.

The development of value has an influence on the moderating variable and, as a result, has an effect on the proclivity to use platforms. It is particularly relevant to an audience that is motivated by creativity, which was the single feature that was highlighted throughout the interviews. Knowledge is influenced by three factors: familiarity with the payment method, quantity of online competence, and length of time. Generally speaking, perceived trust is a technologically driven quality that is impacted by factors such as trust in the payment infrastructure, confidence in the provider of the digital platform, as well as the transparency and fairness of the payment process. Perceived content relevance was proven to influence digital platform adaptation via the implementation of a user-centric business strategy, the provision of high-quality content, and the timing of product content presentation to the consumer.

In the study, it was observed that each of the newly discovered elements stated by interview participants had a positive correlation with the antecedent variables' perceived usefulness and perceived value generation, therefore altering attitudes toward and plans to utilise digital platforms. Because of these eight new connections made by the main research interviews, the Alpha model was transformed into the Alpha 1 model, which included operational hypotheses.

5.8. Alpha 1 model

In the above-mentioned interview analysis, several direct relationships were discovered, including those relating the system characteristics of later payment and single payment platform to individual differences in perceived trust and perceived content relevance, as well as perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and attitude toward digital platform adaptation, as well as intention to use digital platform adaptation, among others. Further, the features of delayed payment, a single payment platform, perceived trust, and perceived content relevance all contribute to the previously identified antecedents in the literature research, which are further defined below. As a consequence, the characteristics of the interview stage impacted the Alpha model, which resulted in the Alpha 1 model. It is depicted in Figure that the Alpha 1 model provides a more comprehensive representation of the components and their interrelationships discussed previously.

Figure: Alpha 1 model

Figure 5.6.: Source: Author

Main study: survey stage two

5.8.1. Revision of methodology

The method for the primary stage of the major inquiry was covered in the parts that came before it. According to the researcher, an email will be sent to 8000 persons who meet certain parameters, and an online survey will be conducted with them (Appendix C). During the selection process, the duplicate and invalid contact information was removed from the list in order to ensure that each member was only contacted once and that the bounce rate was maintained to a bare minimum. Consequently, a new contact list of 7,302 persons was created, which was then updated. The web-based query was sent out through email to the list's 7,291 clients, who responded to it. Two of the bounces were hard (emails did not leave the inbox), seven were soft (the inbox was full), and two were block bounces (emails were blocked from leaving the inbox) (spam). The fact that 99.85 per cent of the emails were sent illustrates the extraordinary quality of the selection process and of the particular emails. The consumer survey was sent out at 3 p.m. on November 6, 2021, which was a Wednesday. The day of the week and time of delivery were chosen in order to maximise the number of responses received for data collection.

A total of 48 questions were posed to consumers, including four at the outset concerning the adaption of digital platforms, 41 obligatory questions in the main portion, and three concluding optional questions about demographic data. To send the email to the consumer base, Salesforce.com's Marketing Cloud was utilised, while surveymonkey.com was used to build the survey and collect the information. During the design and execution of the questionnaire, there were no important or minor concerns that needed to be addressed. This conclusion was predicted since it had been tested with experts and users to verify that no critical errors were introduced throughout the deployment process, which had been done in advance. It took three weeks to gather all of the information for the online survey, which ended on December 27, 2021. Over the course of these 21 days, 775 people participated in the online survey in part, with 262 people completing the poll entirely by answering all 48 questions. Section 4.6 projected a response rate of 8-10 per cent, which was exceeded by the 775 responses, yielding a response rate of 10.63 per cent. At the completion of the data collection operation, the data from Surveymonkey.com was manually exported into a

Microsoft Excel file using Microsoft Excel. Following the collection of the data, it was checked for any evident flaws. There were no obvious errors that were detected. In order to do statistical analysis, the data must first be manually entered into (SPSS).

5.8.2. Respondents' profile

Females constituted 198 (76 per cent) of the 262 respondents, with males accounting for 64 (24 per cent). As a consequence, women formed the vast majority of the participants in the study. Additionally, the sample was skewed toward younger people, with 142 (54 per cent) of those who answered the survey being between the ages of 18 and 25 years old. There were 27 respondents aged 25-29 who represented the older adults (10 per cent), followed by 93 respondents aged 30-35 who represented the younger adults (36 per cent of the population). One-quarter of those who responded claimed a monthly income of fewer than 4000 thousand Pounds, with the remaining 26 (10 per cent) reporting a general income of 4000-6000 Pounds. Furthermore, 91 (35 per cent) of those surveyed earn between £6,000 and £8,000 each month.

Frequency Table

Table 5.4.: Main study (stage two) — demographic data

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25	142	54.2	54.2	54.2
	25-29	27	10.3	10.3	64.5
	30-35	93	35.5	35.5	100.0
	Total	262	100.0	100.0	

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	64	24.4	24.4	24.4
	Female	198	75.6	75.6	100.0
	Total	262	100.0	100.0	

		Income		Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
		Frequency	Percent		
Valid	Up to 4000	66	25.2	25.2	25.2
	4000 to 6000	26	9.9	9.9	35.1
	6000-8000	91	34.7	34.7	69.8
	8000 and above	79	30.2	30.2	100.0
	Total	262	100.0	100.0	

Source: Main study data.

5.9. Descriptive statistics

Starting with a description of the data collected in the main portion of the survey sample using descriptive statistics, the data is shown in Table, with the constructs and their indicators listed in the order in which they were asked in the online survey questions. The following table summarises the most relevant statistical metrics for each indicator (item) in the questionnaire, including sample size, the lowest and highest values on the five-point Likert scale, the mean and constructs mean, the median, and the standard deviation for each indicator.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimu m	Maximu m	Mean	Std. Deviation
PUN1	262	1.00	5.00	3.2366	1.38593
PUN2	262	1.00	5.00	2.8855	1.04783
PUN3	262	1.00	5.00	2.7595	1.09658
PVC1	262	1.00	5.00	3.3115	1.38593
PVC2	262	1.00	5.00	2.9133	1.04783
PVC3	262	1.00	5.00	2.8118	1.09658
ATT1	262	1.00	5.00	2.7328	1.09562

ATT2	262	1.00	5.00	2.8435	1.09437
ATT3	262	1.00	5.00	2.8397	1.08855
INT1	262	1.00	5.00	2.8588	1.02791
INT2	262	1.00	5.00	2.1565	1.01064
INT3	262	1.00	5.00	2.7214	1.10148
PVC 1	262	1.00	5.00	4.0191	1.01503
PVC 2	262	1.00	5.00	3.4809	.94160
PVC 3	262	1.00	5.00	3.7405	.95563
LPM1	262	1.00	5.00	3.8855	1.08024
LPM2	262	1.00	5.00	2.7634	1.19278
LPM3	262	1.00	5.00	3.1832	1.16987
SPP1	262	1.00	5.00	3.5840	1.17061
SPP2	262	1.00	5.00	3.8855	1.03310
SPP3	262	1.00	5.00	3.7634	1.11645
PCR1	262	1.00	5.00	3.0802	1.32659
PCR2	262	1.00	5.00	2.5763	1.27453
PCR3	262	1.00	5.00	3.5763	1.18737
MOB1	262	1.00	5.00	3.1603	1.11635
MOB2	262	1.00	5.00	3.1527	1.12426
MOB3	262	1.00	5.00	3.4504	.99588
COM1	262	1.00	5.00	3.9809	1.02255
COM2	262	1.00	5.00	2.7099	1.13454
COM3	262	1.00	5.00	2.5229	1.09223
CON1	262	1.00	5.00	3.1260	1.24236
CON2	262	1.00	5.00	3.2863	1.26177
CON3	262	1.00	5.00	2.8969	1.33938
INN1	262	1.00	5.00	3.5382	1.13313
INN2	262	1.00	5.00	3.0496	1.31650
INN3	262	1.00	5.00	3.2824	1.27020
KNO1	262	1.00	5.00	2.8435	1.01064
KNO2	262	1.00	5.00	3.7557	1.12847
KNO3	262	1.00	5.00	3.5802	1.16760
PTR1	262	1.00	5.00	3.0267	1.30254
PTR2	262	1.00	5.00	3.1107	1.23144
PTR3	262	1.00	5.00	3.0115	1.30276
Valid N (listwise)	262				

Table 5.5.: Descriptive statistics

PUN had a composite mean of 2.960, which was the third-lowest perception factor when compared to the other constructs ($x=2.812-3.749$), and it was also the least accurate.

Respondents, on the other hand, considered usefulness to be a somewhat advantageous consideration in deciding which online things to purchase (PUN 1, $x=3.240$). Those who responded felt that digital platforms were useful as flexible interfaces (PUN 2, $x=2.88$), while those who felt that they were easy to use (PUN 3, $x=2.75$) had poor evaluations of their usefulness as flexible interfaces.

It was found that the construct means for perceived value creation (PVC) was 2.96, which indicates that respondents considered the adaptation of digital platforms to be a value creation service. The findings revealed that the comment "learning to adapt to digital platforms is fulfilling" scored almost the same as the PUN indicator (PVC 1, $x=3.31$), followed by the comments "using digital platforms adaptation is gratifying" (PVC 3, $x=2.81$) and "using digital platforms adaptation is gratifying" (PVC 2, $x=2.91$), respectively.

It had the second-lowest value among the constructs, with an attitude toward digital platforms (ATT) having a construct mean of 2.805, the second-lowest value among the constructs studied. The indicator means indicated comparable outcomes: They "liked the idea of adapting digital platforms for online purchases" (ATT 1, $x=2.732$), "would like buying online via digital platform adaptation" (ATT 2, $x=2.843$), and "found it fascinating" (ATT 3, $x=2.839$) that digital platform adaptation might be used for online purchases.

It was the lowest perception factor, as shown by the composite mean of the intention to use digital platforms adaptation (INT) of 2.578, which indicated that participants did not have a substantial interest in digital platform services in general. But respondents feel that adopting digital platforms for online transactions is a feasible approach for conducting online transactions (INT 1, $x=2.859$), and they are confident in their capacity to use them in the next six months (INT 2, $x=2.156$), and in five years (INT 3, $x=2.839$) in the future.

The mean of the construct for perceived ease of use (PVC) was 3.407, indicating that respondents considered the adaptation of digital platforms to be very straightforward to use. "Learning to adapt to digital platforms is easy," according to the findings (PVC _1, $x=4.019$), followed by "using digital platforms is uncomplicated," (PVC _3, $x=3.480$), and "flexible to interact with," (PVC _2, $x=3.740$), which got the highest scores across all indicators.

Later payment (LPM) had a construct mean of 3.463, indicating that respondents considered digital platform adaptation to be a highly rewarding service to use in the future. "Learning to adapt to digital platforms is straightforward," according to the findings (LPM 1, $x=3.885$),

with "using digital platforms is easy," (LPM 3, $x=3.276$), and "flexible to interact with," (LPM 2, $x=3.183$) coming in second and third place, respectively.

This indicates that respondents considered the adoption of digital platforms to be a highly rewarding service to use. The construct mean for a single payment platform (SPP) was 3.550, indicating that respondents considered the use of digital platforms to be a highly rewarding service to use. Among all of the indicators tested, the highest score was obtained for "learning to adapt to digital platforms is straightforward" (SPP 1, $x=3.584$), followed by "using digital platforms is easy" (SPP 3, $x=3.885$), and "flexible to interact with" (SPP 2, $x=3.763$).

Respondents rated laws and regulations (LAW) as a very rewarding service, based on a construct mean of 2.944, indicating that they considered digital platform adaption to be a highly satisfying service to use. Following that, "using digital platforms is straightforward" (LAW 3, $x=2.763$) and "flexible to interact with" (LAW 2, $x=3.175$) received the greatest scores across all categories, with "learning to adapt to digital platforms" receiving the highest score across all categories (LAW 1, $x=3.080$).

In the construct mean of the variable Mobility (MOB), the construct mean was 3.296, showing that micropayment services are highly adaptable and may be used "at any time" (MOB 1, $x=3.160$), "anywhere" (MOB 2, $x=3.152$), or when "travelling" (MOB 3, $x=3.450$).

The composite compatibility score (COM) was 3.380, indicating that respondents are satisfied with the idea of paying a fee for information available via digital channels. It was the compatibility of "existing payment technologies" that received the greatest degree of confidence (COM 1, $x=3.980$), as opposed to the perception of compatibility with their online shopping behaviour (COM 2, $x=2.709$) and lifestyle (COM 3, $x=2.522$), which received the lowest level of trust.

Adapting digital platforms as a convenient service for online transactions that is especially beneficial in a variety of contexts (CON 1, $x=3.126$) received a construct score of 2.978, alluding to the adoption of digital platforms as a convenient service for online transactions that is especially beneficial in a variety of contexts (CON 1, $x=3.126$). On the other hand, respondents put the most value on the perception that they are just paying for the goods they consume (CON 2, $x=3.286$). It was the statement "read easily and swiftly" (CON 3, $x=2.896$) that received the lowest rating.

Digital platform adaption had a construct score of 3.161, indicating that people consider it to be a technologically inventive innovation. INN 1, $x=3.538$) found that users saw themselves as having the same level of expertise about new technology as other persons. Their trust in

their abilities to be among the first to investigate new technologies (INN 2, $x=3.049$) and in their ability to recommend them to others (INN 3, $x=3.282$) is, on the other hand, low. For micropayment knowledge (KNO), a composite mean of 3.29 was calculated. The statement "enjoy purchasing little amounts of things" had a poor grade (KNO 1, $x=2.843$), but the respondents said that they were confident in using credit cards, PayPal, and ApplePay as a result of digital platform adaptation (KNO 2, $x=3.755$) (KNO 3, $x=3.580$). Platform owners must show that platform adaptation is "not harmful" (PTR 1, $x=3.026$) and "uses trustworthy payment systems" (PTR 2, $x=3.110$), which also applies to other "media" (PTR 3, $x=3.011$).

The perceived relevance of the content (PCR) was rated at 3.127 out of 5 stars. According to the data, respondents are willing to pay for information that is considered as "useful" (PCR 3, $x=3.615$) and "relevant" (PCR 1, $x=3.080$), but not for content that is perceived as Important.

5.10. Normality analysis

To do the inferential statistical analysis, it was required to ascertain whether or not the data for each scale item was normal before proceeding. The absence of symmetry (skewness) and the presence or absence of peaks or valleys (kurtosis) in a continuous variable's distribution are two criteria that indicate whether or not the distribution deviates from normality. Each indication from the questionnaire was computed individually using SmartSPSS 3.2.7, as a result of which, The findings of the skewness and kurtosis tests are summarised in the following table: Table. In business research, skewness scores of zero and three indicate that the data has been totally normalised and is thus symmetric, which is not an optimal assumption to make (Pallant, 2013). In the words of Bulmer (1979), a distribution is considered highly skewed if the skewness is less than -1 or more than +1; moderately skewed if the skewness is in the range of -1 and -1/2 or in the range of +1/2 and +1; and typically symmetric if the skewness is in the range of -1/2 and +1/2. Western (2014) defines mesokurtic distribution as one in which the mean is three times the variance; platykurtic as one in which the mean is less than three times the variance; and leptokurtic as one in which the mean is more than three times the variance.

The outcomes of this study indicated varying degrees of negative skewness and kurtosis, but all were within acceptable ranges, with the exception of one scale item: PIC_, which was statistically substantially negative in the findings (-1.02). This value was kept since it was so close to the -1.0 requirement that it could not be changed. The data, on the other hand, was discovered to be regularly dispersed.

	N	Skewness		Kurtosis	
		Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
PUN1	262	-.208	.150	-.641	.300
PUN2	262	-.011	.150	-.609	.300
PUN3	262	.507	.150	-.265	.300
PVC1	262	-.208	.150	-.641	.300
PVC2	262	-.011	.150	-.609	.300
PVC3	262	.507	.150	-.265	.300
ATT1	262	.458	.150	-.512	.300
ATT2	262	.739	.150	-.351	.300
ATT3	262	.736	.150	-.338	.300
INT1	262	.841	.150	-.178	.300
INT2	262	.646	.150	.097	.300
INT3	262	.154	.150	-.266	.300
PVC 1	262	-.690	.150	-.199	.300
PVC 2	262	-.375	.150	.639	.300
PVC 3	262	-.442	.150	.213	.300
LPM1	262	-.648	.150	-.259	.300
LPM2	262	.426	.150	-.677	.300
LPM3	262	-.130	.150	-.629	.300
SPP1	262	-.269	.150	-.768	.300
SPP2	262	-.357	.150	-.731	.300
SPP3	262	-.387	.150	-.790	.300
PCR1	262	.090	.150	-.946	.300
PCR2	262	.712	.150	-.478	.300
PCR3	262	-.335	.150	-.684	.300
MOB1	262	-.171	.150	-.558	.300
MOB2	262	-.337	.150	-.489	.300
MOB3	262	-.507	.150	.281	.300
COM1	262	-.780	.150	-.186	.300

COM2	262	.303	.150	-.575	.300
COM3	262	.643	.150	-.097	.300
CON1	262	-.060	.150	-.843	.300
CON2	262	-.265	.150	-.781	.300
CON3	262	.132	.150	-.785	.300
INN1	262	-.262	.150	-.620	.300
INN2	262	.121	.150	-.920	.300
INN3	262	-.250	.150	-.823	.300
KNO1	262	.857	.150	-.084	.300
KNO2	262	-.410	.150	-.755	.300
KNO3	262	-.268	.150	-.756	.300
PTR1	262	.149	.150	-.861	.300
PTR2	262	-.051	.150	-.810	.300
PTR3	262	.167	.150	-.870	.300
Valid N (listwise)	262				

Table 5.6.: Data normality analysis

Source: Main study data.

The Alpha 1 model was first described in full, with a duplicate of the model shown in Figure to serve as a basis for empirical hypothesis testing once it was refined. It is a condensed collection of hypothesised correlations between variables and constructs indicators for each variable, developed from the literature review and an additional qualitative approach employed in the main study and shown in the replica.

In this DBA study, the route model used is reflective, as shown by the arrows linking the latent variable to the measured indicator variables in the table. We choose to utilise the reflective route model because the indicators represent a collection of components, each of which reflects the latent variable that was assessed (Garzson, 2017).

Figure: Alpha 1

Figure 5.7.: Source: Author

The whole set of hypotheses is repeated many times in order to begin the statistical hypothesis testing process.

H1: Attitudes regarding digital platforms will have a positive impact on the intention to use them.

H2: Perceived usefulness will have a positive impact on people's attitudes toward the adoption of digital platforms.

H3: Perceived value creation will have a beneficial influence on the attitude toward the adaption of digital platforms.

H4: There is a correlation between Mobility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers

H5: There is a correlation between Mobility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H6: There is a correlation between compatibility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H7: There is a correlation between compatibility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H8: There is a correlation between Convenience and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H9: There is a correlation between Convenience and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H10: There is a correlation between innovativeness and the perceived value creation of digital platforms by consumers.

H11: There is a correlation between Knowledge and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H12: There is a correlation between Later payment and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H13: There is a correlation between Later payment and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H14: There is a correlation between Single payment platforms and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H15: There is a correlation between Single payment platforms and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H16: There is a correlation between Perceived trust and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H17: There is a correlation between Perceived trust and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H18: There is a correlation between Perceived content relevance and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H19: There is a correlation between Perceived content relevance and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

5.11. Validity and reliability of scale items

5.11.1. Confirmatory factor analysis

However, despite the fact that the rising usage of statistical software programmes has made data analysis easier and more accessible, maintaining statistical expertise is not always straightforward (Williams 2010). "With the emergence of powerful computers and their frightening statistical programmes, factor analysis and other multivariate methodologies are now available to persons who have never been trained to comprehend them," Klene (1995), as stated in Pettl (2003), continues.

As a consequence, component analysis has previously been used to confirm that scale data is correct on the building level. In contrast to exploratory factor analysis (EFA), which is used to uncover dimensions from which a theory may be created from a large number of constructs, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is used to assess how well measured scales match the number of constructs in a proposed model (Williams et al., 2010). The validity of the constructs in the whole conceptual model was determined by the application of CFA in this DBA investigation.

The route loadings connecting the components to the indicator variables should be more than 0.7 to have a well-fitting reflecting model and high reliability of the indication. (Heinseler and colleagues, 2012).

According to Table, the loadings for each component in the appropriate build are as follows: Due to the fact that their values exceeded 0.7, 45 components were successfully combined

into a single factor. Six components, which are shown in bold, have loadings ranging between -0.102 and 0.532, and as a result, do not fulfil the minimum measurement loading requirement of 0.7. These items should be eliminated as a consequence, and since the indications are reflective, the latent variable will keep their significance even after they are eliminated (Garsson, 2016). Consequently, these six loads on the Alpha 1 model's structural elements were removed in order to improve the dependability of the indications.

Indicator	ATT	COM	CON	INN	INT	KNO	LPM	MOB	PCR	PEU	PTR	PUN	SPP
ATT_1	0.873												
ATT_2	0.941												
ATT_3	0.939												
COM_1	0.316												
COM_2	0.925												
COM_3	0.922												
CON_1			0.887										
CON_2			0.881										
CON_3			0.915										
INN_1				0.837									
INN_2				0.904									
INN_3				0.907									
INT_1					0.878								
INT_2					0.855								
INT_3					0.907								
INT_4					0.856								
KNO_1						0.477							
KNO_2						0.854							
KNO_3						0.856							
LPM_1							0.770						
LPM_2							-0.102						
LPM_3							-0.682						
MOB_1								0.952					
MOB_2								0.960					
MOB_3								0.861					
PCR_1									0.841				
PCR_2									0.872				
PCR_3									0.829				
PEU_1										0.442			
PEU_2										0.897			
PEU_3										0.532			
PTR_1											0.815		
PTR_2											0.784		
PTR_3											0.800		
PTR_4											0.703		
PUN_1												0.898	
PUN_2												0.895	
PUN_3												0.881	
SPP_1													0.880
SPP_2													0.826
SPP_3													0.788

Note. N= 262.

le: Outer factor loadings — initial set

Table 5.7.: Source: Main study data.

Following the SPSS recalculation, PTR 4 was identified as a significant outlier, with its value dropping from 0.703 to 0.696. Considering how close the value is to the 0.7 thresholds and how this influence is limited to a single item, it was determined that this was the best item to keep.

When LPM 3 and PVC 2 have loadings of 1.000, this indicates that the latent variable makes an absolute contribution to the reflective model. Despite the fact that values of one are rare, the absolute maximum of one is allowed in SPSS because the bigger the loadings, the more reliable the measurement model is considered to be (Garson, 2016). However, there were no omissions detected throughout the research for the 1 value. The LMP 3 and PVC 2 data, as a consequence, are considered to be very robust measures in the model.

The final factor loadings — which are listed in alphabetical order — that were used for additional statistical analysis are summarised in the following table.

Indicator	ATT	COM	CON	INN	INT	KNO	LPM	MOB	PCR	PEU	PTR	PUN	SPP
ATT_1	0.873												
ATT_2	0.941												
ATT_3	0.939												
COM_2		0.932											
COM_3		0.945											
CON_1			0.885										
CON_2			0.884										
CON_3			0.914										
INN_1				0.835									
INN_2				0.896									
INN_3				0.915									
INT_1					0.878								
INT_2					0.855								
INT_3					0.907								
INT_4					0.856								
KNO_2						0.866							
KNO_3						0.879							
LPM_3							1.000						
MOB_1								0.952					
MOB_2								0.960					
MOB_3								0.860					
PCR_1									0.842				
PCR_2									0.875				
PCR_3									0.825				
PEU_2										1.000			
PTR_1											0.826		
PTR_2											0.775		
PTR_3											0.797		
PTR_4											0.696		
PUN_1												0.899	
PUN_2												0.895	
PUN_3												0.881	
SPP_1													0.886
SPP_2													0.815
SPP_3													0.791

Note. N= 262.

le: Outer factor loadings — initial set

Source: Main study data.

Table 5.8.: Alpha 2 model with indicators

Figure 5.8.: Source: Author.

5.11.2. Cronbach's coefficient alpha

In order to ensure that the constructs contained in measurement models are reliable, it is necessary to conduct a reliability assessment. Cronbach's coefficient alpha (Cronbach, 1951) is widely recognised as the most accurate method of establishing internal consistency in stated reliability coefficients, and it is almost usually used in consumer research studies (Chao and Kem, 2015). When doing this study, the Cronbach's alpha values for each construct were calculated using SPSS and are shown in Table 1. Model fit is regarded as satisfactory when the degree of fit is more than 0.60 (Streineer, 2003), with a proposed threshold of greater than 0.7 (Peterson, 1994; Fornell and Larcker, 1981) (Peterson, 1994; Fornell and Larcker, 1981).

Table: Cronbach's alpha

Construct label	Full name of construct	Cronbach's alpha	Number of items
ATT	Attitude to use micropayments	0.907	3
COM	Compatibility	0.865	2
CON	Convenience	0.875	3
INN	Innovativeness	0.862	3
INT	Intention to use micropayments	0.897	4
KNO	Knowledge of micropayments	0.686	2
LPM	Later payment	1.000	1
MOB	Mobility	0.915	3
PCR	Perceived content relevance	0.804	3
PEU	Perceived ease of use	1.000	1
PTR	Perceived trust	0.788	3
PUN	Perceived usefulness	0.871	3
SPP	Single payment platform	0.782	3

Source: Main study data.

Table 5.9.: Source: Main study data.

Cronbach's alpha values for all 13 items ranged between 0.686 and 1.000, which was higher than the recommended limit of 0.6 for this test. Twelve measurements surpassed the acceptable limit of 0.7, with 10 readings above the necessary limit of 0.8. LPM and PVC displayed the greatest degree of reliability at the highest level, with just a small number of exceptions (1.000). It was discovered as a consequence of this that the constructs were dependable and internally consistent. Based on the results, it was determined that the measured item scales were reliable and valid.

5.12. Evaluation of measurement model

5.12.1. Convergent validity

The average variance extracted (AVE) approach, which examines the average communality of latent components, is used to assess the convergent validity of reflective measurement models (Garsson, 2016). In this validity test, the bare minimum criteria are 0.5 (Hairtl 2010), which indicates that a concept with an AVE larger than 0.5 sufficiently accounts for the variance of the model's relevant indicators. The AVE values for all of the constructs included

in the measurement model are listed in the following table. As a result, the values range from 0.69 to 1.000 — with the LPM and PVC repeatedly abutting the remarkable maximum (1.000) — and are therefore significantly greater than the permitted limit of 0.5, indicating that the model's convergence validity is completely compatible with the stipulated standard.

Construct label	Full name of construct	AVE
ATT	Attitude to use micropayments	0.843
COM	Compatibility	0.881
CON	Convenience	0.800
INN	Innovativeness	0.779
INT	Intention to use micropayments	0.764
KNO	Knowledge of micropayments	0.761
LPM	Later payment	1.000
MOB	Mobility	0.856
PCR	Perceived content relevance	0.718
PEU	Perceived ease of use	1.000
PTR	Perceived trust	0.601
PUN	Perceived usefulness	0.795
SPP	Single payment platform	0.691

Source: Main study data.

Table 5.9.: AVE

5.12.2. Discriminant validity

If two conceptions are not intended to be linked, discriminant validity is employed to assess whether or not the two constructs are, in fact, unconnected. When used in conjunction with the Fornell–Larcker criterion, AVE may also be used to establish discriminant validity in a sample of data (Fornell and Larcker, 1982). This illustrates that the square roots of any idea's AVE values must be greater than the correlation between that concept and any other concept (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Garsson, 2016). When stated inside its bundle of indicators, the variance of any construct may be bigger than the variance of any other construct in the SPSS output table.

The loading amounts for each construction are summarised in the table below. Avg. root squares (AVE) are presented in bold in the diagonal cells, and as can be seen, any construct column is much larger than the correlations below. As a consequence, the discriminant validity of the model is established. Given the negative cross-loadings, it is reasonable to conclude that the correlation between opposed variables did not sufficiently represent the

antagonism between these concepts. It was our intention to find contamination between the values, and no loadings were determined to be invariant across constructions, which was our aim.

Table: Cross-loadings

Construct	ATT	COM	CON	INN	INT	KNO	LPM	MOB	PCR	PEU	PTR	PUN	SPP
ATT	0.918												
COM	0.740	0.939											
CON	0.731	0.654	0.895										
INN	0.146	0.246	0.179	0.880									
INT	0.868	0.824	0.728	0.178	0.874								
KNO	0.492	0.524	0.510	0.336	0.526	0.872							
LPM	-0.455	-0.412	-0.368	-0.070	-0.456	-0.303	1.000						
MOB	0.664	0.576	0.750	0.177	0.670	0.477	-0.320	0.925					
PCR	0.699	0.663	0.788	0.119	0.697	0.480	-0.363	0.598	0.848				
PEU	0.641	0.522	0.655	0.123	0.617	0.392	-0.301	0.635	0.527	1.000			
PTR	0.665	0.653	0.742	0.267	0.678	0.581	-0.337	0.656	0.647	0.548	0.775		
PUN	0.823	0.713	0.740	0.123	0.818	0.497	-0.414	0.651	0.680	0.648	0.654	0.892	
SPP	0.577	0.549	0.602	0.173	0.611	0.545	-0.215	0.541	0.586	0.470	0.618	0.594	0.832

Note. ATT = Attitude towards use; COM = Compatibility; CON = Convenience; INN =Innovativeness; INT = Intention to use micropayments; KNO = Micropayment knowledge; LPM = Later payment; MOB = Mobility; PCR = Perceived content relevance; PEU = Perceived ease of use; PTR = Perceived trust; PUN = Perceived usefulness; SPP = Single payment platform.

Table 5.10.: Source: Main study data.

5.13. Testing the structural model

The SPSS analysis is used to verify the research model (as seen in Figure). The SPSS analysis generates t-values and path coefficients for each of the hypotheses that have been provided.

5.13.1. t-Value

Hair et al. (2010) emphasised the importance of t-tests in identifying the relevance of characteristics in a structural model, stating that they are particularly beneficial for this purpose. The relevant t-values are shown in Figure and correspond to each joint link hypothesised in the research model, as given in the table. Figure 1 shows the second to the final step of the research model, which corresponds to the Beta 1 model, as seen in this figure. In addition, the graphic displays the repercussions of the elements' interaction with one another.

In order to evaluate whether or not there are statistically significant correlations between the model's components, the one-tailed t-test was utilised. These were determined at the 1% and 5% levels of statistical significance, respectively, and are shown in the table.

Figure 5.9.: Beta 1 model with t-Values

Figure Source: Main study data.

Because their t-values surpass 1.65, seven of the 19 direct joint connections are statistically significant at the 5 per cent level of significance, as seen in the figure. With t-values of more than 2.33, four of the seven direct connections are statistically significant at the one per cent level. These include the correlations between compatibility and perceived usefulness, convenience and perceived value creation, and mobility and perceived value creation, among others. Furthermore, the figure reveals that all three indirect correlations are statistically significant at the one per cent level (t-values > 2.33), as shown by the t-values in the figure. The last stage of the research model referred to as the Beta 2 model, is discussed in the next section. This model depicts the individual route coefficients.

5.13.2. Path coefficients

As ~~Hair~~ Hair et al. (2010) point out, route coefficients are weights that help in identifying the contribution of each path to the overall fit of the structural model, and they are calculated using the route coefficients. In other words, path coefficients are used to evaluate the validity of the important links in the structural model. Weighing vary between -1 and +1, with the highest value around -1 and +1 and the least value near 0. Gardner (2017). A significant positive relationship between attitude and intention to use digital platforms is shown by the Beta 2 model, which has relative path coefficients of 0.954 between the two variables, indicating an extremely high positive link. Furthermore, there is a significant positive relationship between perceived usefulness and attitude toward use (0.879). It was revealed that there is a somewhat positive relationship between perceived value creation and attitude toward use (0.058).

Figure 5.10.: Beta 2 model with path coefficients

Source: Main study data.

5.14. Assessment of hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

H0: Attitudes regarding digital platforms will not have a positive impact on the intention to use them.

H1: Attitudes regarding digital platforms will have a positive impact on the intention to use them.

The relationship between attitude toward adapting to digital platforms (ATT) and intention to adapt to digital platforms (INT) was statistically significant, with a t-value of 61.021 indicating a significant relationship. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected at the one percent level of significance, and the alternative hypothesis, H1, is accepted. This link has a significant influence on it because of the route coefficient of 0.954 that it possesses. It may also be concluded that consumer sentiments about digital platform adoption have a substantial influence on their intentions to make online transactions using digital platforms.

Hypothesis 2

H0: Perceived usefulness will not have a positive impact on people's attitudes toward the adoption of digital platforms.

H1: Perceived usefulness will have a positive impact on people's attitudes toward the adoption of digital platforms.

There is a significant relationship between perceived utility (PUN) and attitude toward adapting to digital platforms (ATT). The t-values for this relationship are 16.897. In this case, the null hypotheses can be rejected at the 1 percent level of significance since there is a significant relationship between the two conceptual frameworks, therefore the alternative hypothesis is accepted (i.e. H1 accepted). As shown by the path coefficient of 0.879, the relationship between perceived usefulness and attitude toward adapting to digital platforms has a significant impact.

Hypothesis 3

H0: Perceived value creation will not have a beneficial influence on the attitude toward the adaption of digital platforms.

H1: Perceived value creation will have a beneficial influence on the attitude toward the adaption of digital platforms.

A positive link between perceived value creation (PVC) and attitude toward adapting to digital platforms (ATT) is demonstrated by the SPSS result with a t-value of 3.804, which was obtained by using SPSS statistical software (1 percent significance level). Therefore, it is concluded to reject the null hypothesis and accept Hypothesis 1. With a path coefficient of 0.058 between the two variables, it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship between perceived value production through digital platform adaptation and consumers' attitudes regarding their usage of digital platforms.

Hypothesis 4

H0: There is no correlation between Mobility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Mobility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

There is a significant relationship between platform mobility (MOB) and perceived usefulness (PUN), with a t-value of 2.053. As a result, at the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and H1 is accepted. It might be claimed that mobility has a positive impact on how useful digital platforms are perceived to be by their users.

Hypothesis 5

H0: There is no correlation between Mobility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Mobility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers

A significant correlation between mobility (MOB) and perceived value generation by platforms can be seen in the PLS output due to the t-value of 3.220 in the PLS output (PVC). As a result, at the 1% level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and H1 is accepted.

It is possible to demonstrate that mobility has a major positive impact on how platforms view their perceived value creation capabilities.

Hypothesis 6

H0: There is no correlation between compatibility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between compatibility and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

It was found that the relationship between platform compatibility (COM) and customer perceived utility (PUN) was 5.421 when using the t-test. As a result, at the 1% level of significance, the null hypothesis can be rejected and H1 is accepted. According to the findings, users' impressions of the usability of a platform are significantly influenced by compatibility issues.

Hypothesis 7

H0: There is no correlation between compatibility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between compatibility and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

At the 5 percent level, the relationship between compatibility (COM) and consumer perceptions of platform value creation (PVC) has a t-value of 1.625, indicating a positive relationship. As a consequence, the null hypothesis is not rejected, and the alternative hypothesis, H1, is not accepted. It is possible to argue that there is insufficient data to support the claim that compatibility increases consumer views of platform value creation.

Hypothesis 8

H0: There is no correlation between Convenience and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Convenience and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

According to the PLS result, which has a t-value of 3.282, there is a statistically significant link between convenience (CON) and the perceived usefulness of platforms (PUN). As a result, at the 1% level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and hypothesis (H1) is accepted. It might be claimed that there is a significant link between customer perceptions of the usefulness of digital platforms and their perceived level of convenience.

Hypothesis 9

H0: There is no correlation between Convenience and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Convenience and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

It was found that the relationship between convenience (CON) and perceived value creation (PVC) of digital platforms had a t-value of 3.129 when considered at the 1% level of significance. Consequently, at the 1 percent level, the null hypothesis is rejected, and alternative hypothesis is accepted (i.e., H1 accepted), showing that there is a strong association between convenience and consumers' perceived value creation via digital platforms.

Hypothesis 10

H0: There is no correlation between innovativeness and the perceived Value creation of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between innovativeness and the perceived Value creation of digital platforms by consumers.

The results of the PLS computations revealed that there was a relationship between innovativeness (INN) and perceived value creation by digital platforms, with a t-value of 0.618. (PVC). Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected, while hypotheses H1 rejected at a 5 percent level. To put it another way, the research does not support the proposition that innovation increases consumers' views of the value generated by digital platforms.

Hypothesis 11

H0: There is no correlation between Knowledge and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Knowledge and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

The relationship between micropayments knowledge (KNO) and perceived value creation by digital platforms (PVC) has a t-value of 0.039, according to the study. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected, and hypotheses H1 is not accepted at the 5 percent confidence level. To be more specific, it may be said that there is insufficient evidence to refute the assumption that digital platform knowledge increases consumers' views of the value generated by digital platforms.

Hypothesis 12

H0: There is no correlation between Later payment and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers platforms.

H1: There is a correlation between Later payment and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers

At the 5% level, the connection between later payment (LPM) and perceived utility of digital platforms (PUN) has a t-value of 1.941. Thus, at the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected (i.e. H1 accepted). It may be inferred that deferred payment improves customers' perceptions of the utility of digital platforms.

Hypothesis 13

H0: There is no correlation between Later payment and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Later payment and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

According to the PLS results, the relationship between later payment (LPM) and perceived value creation by digital platforms had a t-value of 0.748 at the 5 percent level, indicating a positive relationship (PVC). As a result, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected (H1 fails to be accepted). For the reasons stated earlier, the theory that postponing payment boosts customers' perceptions of the value created by digital platform transactions is not completely excluded.

Hypothesis 14

H0: There is no correlation between Single payment platforms and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers

H1: There is a correlation between Single payment platforms and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

In order to assess the relationship between the single payment platform (SPP) and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms, a t-value of 1.940 was calculated (PUN). As a result, at the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis, H1, accepted. According to some, a single payment platform has a positive impact on the perceived usability of a service.

Hypothesis 15

H0: There is no correlation between a Single payment platform and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers

H1: There is a correlation between Single payment platforms and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

It was shown that the correlation between a single payment platform (SPP) and perceived value creation by digital platforms (PVC) was 0.913 when the two variables were combined. Consequently, the null hypothesis is not rejected and therefore H1 is not accepted. As previously mentioned, there is little evidence to debunk the concept that a single payment platform increases users' views of the value generated by a digital platform.

Hypothesis 16

H1: There is no correlation between Perceived trust and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Perceived trust and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

In the study of the relationship between perceived trust (PTR) and consumers' perceived utility of digital platforms (PUN), the t-value was calculated as 0.373. (5 percent level). Consequently, the null hypothesis is not rejected hence, H1 is not accepted. It is possible to say that there is inadequate data to refute the assumption that consumers' perceived confidence in platforms influences their perceived utility of platforms.

Hypothesis 17

H0: There is no correlation between Perceived trust and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers

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H1: There is a correlation between Perceived trust and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

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The correlation between perceived trust (PTR) and consumers' views of digital platform value creation (PVC) was found to be 0.274, indicating a significant relationship (5 percent). As a consequence, neither the null hypothesis nor the alternative hypothesis H1 is rejected. The outcome is that the hypothesis that perceived trust in digital platforms has a beneficial impact on consumers' views of the value generated by digital platforms is not supported by substantial data.

Hypothesis 18

H0: There is no correlation between Perceived content relevance and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Perceived content relevance and the perceived usefulness of digital platforms by consumers.

According to the PLS findings, the relationship between perceived content relevance (PCR) and consumers' perceived utility of digital platforms (PUN) was significant at the 5 percent level of significance, yielding a t-value of 1.234. As a consequence, the null hypothesis is not rejected, and the alternative hypothesis, H1, is ruled out. Customers' opinions of the usefulness of digital platforms are favourably influenced by perceived content relevancy to platforms, and there is little evidence to deny this concept.

Hypothesis 19

H0: There is no correlation between Perceived content relevance and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

H1: There is a correlation between Perceived content relevance and the perceived value created by digital platforms by consumers.

The relationship between perceived content relevance (PCR) and consumers' perceived value creation through digital platforms (PVC) exhibited a t-value of 0.619 when measured at the 5 percent level of significance. As a consequence, neither the null hypothesis nor the alternative hypothesis H1 is rejected. Customers' views of digital platform value creation are favourably influenced by perceived content relevance toward platforms, according to the assumption that there is insufficient evidence to invalidate this claim.

5.15. Summary of the findings

Following the main research interviews conducted in stage one, external variables were added to the basic conceptual model with the purpose of experimentally examining the relationships between all of the comprehensive study model aspects in stage two's primary study survey. When it came to quantitative analysis of the interview material, the first stage involved quantifying the data to determine the frequency of individual and group data: eight variables were identified from nine semi-structured interviews, four of which were already known from the literature synthesis and four which were discovered during the research process; there were two system characteristics and two individual differences in each group. A single factor (compatibility) was not confirmed throughout the interviews. Following the qualitative inquiry technique and the application of coding analysis, four newly discovered items were removed from the conceptual research model. It was the opinion of the experts that later payment, a unified payment platform for all users, perceived trust, and perceived content relevance would all have an impact on perceived usefulness, perceived ease-of-use in online news, attitude toward the use of digital platforms adaptation, and intention to use digital platforms adaptation in Switzerland. A set of eight newly found connections was developed as a result of this process, and these associations were then incorporated into the Alpha 1 research model, providing a final set of 19 joint relations between all constructs, which served as the focal point of the second stage of the main study.

The results of the main research are quite similar to those of the pilot interview study, indicating that the findings are related. Three external features were recognised as being constant throughout both studies, including the use of a single payment platform, the perception of trust, and the perceived relevancy of the material. When describing the same construct in the pilot study, the researcher used a different term: universal payment platform

rather than single payment platform, fair communication rather than perceived trust, and unique value rather than perceived content relevancy, among other things.

When we first started working on the empirical element of stage two, we constructed a sample of 262 valid responses from the web-based survey, using demographic data such as gender, age, and income. When Structural Equation Modelling is used to quantitative data, it is possible to investigate the relationships between the various constructs. Adaptive digital platforms were shown to have a significant positive link with the willingness to use adaptive digital platforms for online news in the United Kingdom, according to the findings of this study. The route coefficient analysis was used to discover which associations were the strongest within the structural model.

In this study, it was discovered that perceived usefulness and perceived value creation both had statistically significant positive relationships with attitudes toward the use of digital platforms, with perceived usefulness exerting a strong positive influence on the moderating variable of attitude and perceived value creation exerting a moderate positive influence. Customers' opinions of digital platforms are expected to be influenced in a similar way by increased perceived utility, resulting in an improved attitude toward platform use. In a similar vein, increasing the perception of value creation will increase user awareness of the advantages of digital platforms. Consumer adoption of digital markets was influenced more by perceived utility than by perceived value generation, according to the findings. Prior study on mobile payments and e-commerce has shown that the results are consistent with one another (Ming-Yen Teoh et al., 2013). Due to the use of one-tailed t-tests in this study, it was not possible to investigate any negative effects.

It was discovered that the effect of all five system characteristics on perceived usefulness was positive and significant. Mobility, compatibility, ease, later payment, and a single payment platform were some of the reasons considered. Two of the constructs, namely mobility and compatibility, as well as convenience, showed statistically significant relationships with the antecedent variable. Additionally, the SPSS output demonstrated that two system features, namely convenience and mobility, had a positive and significant influence on perceived value creation. Both of these system features were shown to have highly significant associations with consumer perceptions of digital platform value creation. As a result, physical platform-related components impact customers' impressions of using digital platforms, in the same

way, that newly discovered criteria such as the necessity for delayed payment and the need for a unified payment platform are crucial for acquiring news content at affordable costs. Neither individual differences in innovativeness nor individual variations in knowledge, perceived trust, or perceived content relevance had a positive impact on any of the antecedent variables. Despite the fact that experts found that these aspects are crucial when customers consider paying for users' digital platforms, survey respondents rejected the hypothesised linkages that resulted as a consequence of their findings.

The majority of consumers did not believe that having knowledge of digital platforms had a positive impact on their views toward and usage of digital platforms, which was surprising. Based on the experts' idea that if customers are aware of the relationship, they would be more likely to utilise the platform efficiently, this connection was conceptualised. Various variables might be contributing to this. As a consequence of the inherent difficulties of digital transactions, many customers have psychological barriers that may be increased by repeated purchases.

The fact that, despite the fact that innovativeness was identified to have an influence on the antecedent elements in the literature research, it was not demonstrated to have a positive effect on perceived value creation in the empirical analysis is also unexpected. Therefore, it does not seem to be a substantial source of worry for clients who shop via digital platforms. This finding might be the result of a lot of circumstances coming together. Beginning with the music industry and app purchases, digital platform adaptation has been advantageous despite the fact that consumers see digital content, such as news or video, as non-innovative, particularly in light of the United Kingdom's number one ranking in the 2017 global innovation index . Second, the outcome is suggestive of a converging economy, since the United Kingdom has maintained its position as the global leader in innovation for the seventh consecutive year. Because the population of a high-income nation, such as the United Kingdom, has better access to technological alternatives than the population of other countries, the population of the United Kingdom has a larger desire for developing technology services.

When examining the Beta model, it was revealed that the relationships between perceived trust and perceived content relevance with the antecedent variables were inconsequential.

Customers may thus ignore the utility and value creation opportunities presented by digital platform adaptation, even if they have faith in a brand. Perhaps this is because faith in financial transactions implies a certain amount of risk, which might explain the phenomenon. Customers' expectations for satisfying their news consumption demands have raised as a result of the purchase of digital platforms, and trust is thus essential for consumers' behaviour on news platforms. No promise can be given, however, that the publisher will refrain from unethical practices such as unjustifiable pricing, the unauthorised use of personal information, or the use of insecure payment methods in the future (Zhosu, 2013). Considering that all online payments include some level of risk, it is reasonable to conclude that risk avoidance exceeds the trustworthiness of using micropayment services.

The findings of the empirical investigation did not support the notion that perceived content relevance had a beneficial impact on the antecedent variables. When applied to the adoption of digital platforms, the findings do not support the consumer's perceptions of unique and crucial characteristics of adoption factors, according to the researchers. Because of this, the impact of consumers' perceived content relevance in driving trends associated with their propensity to make small payments for users' digital platforms has not been shown to be significant.

The results presented above, which were experimentally validated using the Beta 1 and Beta 2 models and their associated associations, are summarised in Table. Please note that the (+) means the alternate hypothesis is accepted and null hypothesis is rejected, similarly (−) means that the alternate hypothesis is rejected, and null hypothesis is accepted whereas N represents the number of participants in the table.

Hypotheses		t-Value	Hypothesis Status
Moderating Variable			
H1	Attitude towards use of platforms → Intention to use digital platforms	61.021	+
Antecedent Variables			
H2	Perceived usefulness → Attitude towards use of digital platforms	16.897	+
H3	Perceived value creation → Attitude towards use of digital platforms	3.804	+
System characteristics			
H4	Mobility → Perceived usefulness	2.053	+
H5	Mobility → Perceived value creation	3.220	+
H6	Compatibility → Perceived usefulness	5.421	+
H7	Compatibility → Perceived value creation	1.625	-
H8	Convenience → Perceived usefulness	3.282	+

H9	Convenience → Perceived value creation	3.129	+
H12	Later payment → Perceived usefulness	1.941	+
H13	Later payment → Perceived value creation	0.748	-
H14	Single payment platform → Perceived usefulness	1.940	+
H15	Single payment platform → Perceived value creation	0.913	-
Individual differences			
H10	Innovativeness → Perceived value creation	0.618	-
H11	knowledge → Perceived value creation	0.039	-
H16	Perceived trust → Perceived usefulness	0.373	-
H17	Perceived trust → Perceived value creation	0.274	-
H18	Perceived content relevance → Perceived usefulness	1.234	-

H19	Perceived content relevance → Perceived value creation	0.619	-
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Note. N = 262. *significant at 1%, **significant at 5%.

Table 5.11.: Source Author

5.16. Conclusions of Chapter 5:

The findings of the pilot research interviews were presented at the beginning of this chapter, and the findings of the main study interviews were presented at the end of the chapter. The results of both investigations were very consistent with three of four newly discovered external variables from the pilot research, which matched the findings of the complete study in terms of consistency. The Alpha research model has been expanded to include four more components that were discovered during the stage two main study interview. After completing the first stage of the primary study, the empirical second stage examined the 19 connections between the different components in the entire Beta 2 model, 10 of which were considered to be statistically significant by the researchers (53 percent). It was determined if the interaction effects of the antecedents, the moderating variable, and the willingness to use digital platforms for adaptation were significant. Chapter Six confirms the survey findings from the empirical portion of the thesis, which were supplied by the users who participated in the survey. In order to assure external validity, the quantitative data from stage two of the primary study is presented to a board of academic and industry experts for their review. Following a thorough review of the results and recommendations derived from the aggregated research on the adaptation of digital platforms, Chapter Seven concludes the book. The research project comes to a close with an offer to seek more research opportunities.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This DBA thesis began with an investigation of the academic literature on business models for digital platforms, in general, and digital platform adaptation, in particular, as it related to the issue of digital platform adaptation. Following that, the relevant literature for adapting digital platforms and associated e-commerce was reviewed, with an emphasis on the relevance of consumer behaviour research on attitudes toward and intentions to use online digital platforms being placed on the importance of consumer behaviour research.

Additionally, the antecedents of perceived usefulness and perceived value production, as well as external variables that are anticipated to have an impact on the use of online digital platforms in the United Kingdom, were discussed in depth. For this research project, we generated a research question, a research aim, and a set of four specific research goals in a sequential manner to specify the scope of the investigation. As a result of this, a study of the theoretical background literature was carried out, and an initial conceptual model was developed, replete with various integrated assumptions that mirrored the model's links.

Following that, the technique for the pilot research and the main study, as well as the empirical inquiry, were developed in parallel. Following that, a pilot study was carried out, with the results serving as a prologue to the larger examination that was to follow. Following that, the major research was carried out in two stages, with the first stage aimed at including new variables into the basic conceptual model — particularly those related to digital platform adaptation — and resulting in the Alpha 1 model, and the second stage aimed at including new variables into the basic conceptual model — especially those related to digital platform adaptation — and resulting in the Alpha 2 model. In the second step of the main inquiry, the experimental analysis of the links within the Alpha 1 model was carried out. Following the statistical analysis conducted during the primary research and the refinement of the Alpha 1 model, the Alpha 2 model was verified, with ten statistically significant associations and nine non-significant relationships found in the final Beta 2 model after the statistical analysis and refinement of the Alpha 1 model.

After that, we'll go through the results from the various stages of the research process in more detail. Various strategic approaches for adapting online digital platforms to the research

challenges are presented in this study, which includes a thorough set of management implications as well as several strategic recommendations. The author recognises the contribution of the research study to the literature as well as the significance of the findings for management. Finally, the limitations of the study are highlighted, as well as the potential for future research.

6.1. Research objective One

Constructing a conceptual model that explores the relationship between factors impacting the adaptation of digital platforms and consumers' attitudes about their desire to use digital platforms is the goal of this study.

It was constructed utilising TAM as well as related research on digital platforms and e-commerce to create the conceptual model for this study. Sidinik and Graeybeal (2002) further developed the TAM model to account for user acceptance of new technologies in a business setting. Davis (1995) introduced the TAM model, which was later updated by Davis in 2000. The model presents a plethora of behavioural predictors of actual information technology utilisation, including the consumer's attitude toward and willingness to use information technology, among other things. Customers' perceptions of usefulness and perceived value generation were examined in this research using TAM to determine the aspects that influence their actual user ratings. TAM was employed in this study to predict user acceptance of online platform use since it has been shown to be a reliable research approach for predicting the adoption of new technologies in previous studies. Aspects of external drivers of new technologies, such as system features and individual variances (Davis, 1993; Venekatesh, 2000), may be summarised in two dimensions, which have previously been utilised to investigate consumer behaviour on digital platforms (Davis, 1993; Venekatesh, 2000). (Kiim et al., 2010; Zhosu, 2013). Following that, a thorough review of the literature on digital platforms and e-commerce processes was conducted in order to have a better understanding of user acceptance requirements as well as consumer behaviour patterns. The researcher compiled a list of key external elements that have an impact on customer adoption of platform-based services. Included among these factors were system qualities such as portability, compatibility, and convenience, in addition to person variations such as inventiveness and understanding of digital platform adaptability. Every relationship between

the elements listed above was tied to actual digital platform use in the conceptual model shown in Figure.

6.2. Research objective two

Research undertaken in the United Kingdom was used to find and apply new system features and particular factors linked with the adaptation of digital platforms, which were discovered and used in the United States.

However, while the conceptual model was constructed from theoretical constructs and was based on studies of online platforms, the researcher investigated additional factors that should be considered for inclusion in the conceptual model, particularly in the context of online platform usage in the United Kingdom. The results of the pilot study confirmed the existence of such extra characteristics that have a compelling impact on customer use. Additional influencing factors in the context of platform adaptation were provided by the pilot participants, who included universal payment systems, equitable communication, and unique value as potential additions. Fair communication and distinctive value were classified as individual characteristics due to their subjective nature on how and why users use digital platforms, whereas universal payment platform was classified as a system characteristic due to its technical and systemic arrangements, and universal payment platform was classified as individual characteristics due to their subjective nature on how and why users use digital platforms, whereas universal payment platform was classified as a system characteristic due to its technical and systemic arrangements, and universal payment platform was classified as both. Before then, none of these components had been recognised as external elements in the context of the special adaptation of digital platforms in the UK sector's particular setting. These additional aspects were included into the investigation's conceptual model, which resulted in the Alpha model being developed.

A slew of external elements that impact consumer acceptance of platform use were uncovered during the primary research (stage one interview) phase of the project. Delay in payment and the usage of a single payment platform, according to industry experts, are two additional system characteristics that impact platform users' views of their usefulness and perceived value generation. Additional industry professionals have opined that consumer perceptions of trust and relevance of information are two elements that influence the adoption

of digital platforms by their respective clients. Due to the fact that these four newly discovered factors had not previously been identified in the research literature, they were included as additional external variables in the study model. Because the availability of a single payment platform, perceived trust, and perceived content relevance had all been established among pilot participants prior to the main investigation, the results of the pilot research were highly supported by the findings of the main study. The Alpha 1 model depicts the relationships that exist between all of the components.

6.3. Research objective three

The purpose of this study is to undertake an empirical investigation of the influence of existing and emerging factors on the use of digital platforms in the UK consumer market. Aiming to experimentally test the Alpha 2 model's connections, which are comprised of existing components from the literature review and new variables from the main study's interview stage one, the primary research conducted a survey (survey stage two) and interviewed participants. The direct link between attitude and intention to use digital platforms was shown to be statistically significant at the one percent level, and it was also found to be the most strong positive relationship in the research model, according to the findings (path coefficient of 0.954). Customers' perceptions of the adaptability of digital platforms had a substantial impact on their actual willingness to use digital platforms, as shown by the findings. Another significant positive relationship between perceived usefulness and attitude has been seen (path coefficient of 0.879). Furthermore, if a reader considers the adaptation of online digital platforms to be advantageous, research indicates that he is extremely inclined to make use of them. In a similar vein, a stronger sense of value creation enhances users' understanding of the importance of adapting to digital platforms that are available online. As a result, the Beta 1 and Beta 2 models, which serve as an essential intermediate step in the purchasing process of consumers, have been verified as vital components. Attitude, perceived utility, and perceived value creation have all been validated as significant components of the models. These results from the original study also provide credibility to the connections that have been established within the theoretical framework. The results also verified tangential findings from a past study on related mobile and e-payments studies, which were provided by Mang-Yen Teoh et al (2014).

Additionally, the primary study showed that seven links between external factors and antecedent variables were significant — three at the 1 per cent level and four at the 5 per cent level — according to the results of the main research (see Beta 1 model). According to the findings, mobility has a statistically significant impact on both perceived usefulness and perceived value creation (at the 5% level of statistical significance) (1 percent significance level). Conspicuousness had a substantial positive effect on both antecedent variables, with each relationship statistically significant at the one percent level of statistical significance. Aside from that, perceived usefulness was significantly influenced by compatibility (1 percent significant level) and later payment (5 percent significant level), both of which had a considerable favourable impact on perceived usefulness. Additionally, it was shown that using a single payment platform was a major behavioural predictor of platform adoption. It is possible to infer that system qualities are significant when it comes to user adaptation in the United Kingdom, but more research is needed. Users were able to identify all of the relationships between the five system features and perceived usefulness, as well as two of the four relationships between the system characteristics and perceived value generation.

Customer attitude was not found to be influenced by individual variations via the use of antecedent variables, on the other hand. This is a problem in the Beta strategy, as shown by customers' acceptance behaviour in the market.

6.4. Research objective four

To provide recommendations based on the results from aims 2 and 3, both from the consumer and industry expert viewpoints, in order to further our understanding of the acceptability of digital platforms by their users and other stakeholders.

Digital platforms must be mobile, interoperable, and simple to use in order to increase customer adoption. They must also provide later payment capability and work with a single payment platform in order to increase consumer adoption. Users put a high value on the qualities of the system. Between external elements, perceived compatibility with digital platforms is the one that has the most impact on consumers' willingness to use digital platforms. As a result, in order for platforms to consider adopting platform services, they

must design them in a manner that is consistent with the present behavioural patterns of their consumers. The same is true for mobility, which implies that mobile services will undoubtedly become more important in the future. Additionally, convenience was identified as a critical motivator, and consumers expect it to be a primary component of online digital platforms from the start of their experience. Additionally, it was discovered that perceived utility, perceived value generation, and attitude toward real intention to use digital platforms, all of which have a significant impact on consumer awareness of online platforms in the United Kingdom, all have a significant impact on consumer awareness of online platforms in the United Kingdom.

In the opinion of industry experts, the data demonstrates that platform providers' digital platform methods aimed at non-subscribers must be reinforced in order to boost money generated by online content. One possible solution that has been suggested for enabling owners to deal with this issue is the adaptation of online digital platforms. For platform services to be successful, however, they need to meet or exceed client expectations, as the empirical data in this study reveals. Platforms that prioritise the most crucial system qualities will be given the highest level of consideration. Overall, the findings may be used as a guide for industry experts in developing and executing appropriate ways for adapting to and adopting digital platform adaptation. Also necessary to acknowledge is that the predicted predictors of platform use, namely innovativeness, familiarity with digital platforms, perceived trust, and perceived content relevance, had no influence on consumer behaviour. So individual qualities have little effect on the buying decision, and platforms must take this into consideration when developing their marketing strategies. Future studies should examine how and why consumers make use of digital platforms available on the internet. The next section offers clear recommendations about the managerial ramifications of this study's findings.

6.5. Implications of the Study:

This study is one of the few that does empirical research on the behavioural components that influence consumer adaptation to online digital platforms, and it is also one of the most comprehensive. On the basis of theoretical considerations, the researcher developed a study model that defined the characteristics that influence customers' willingness to use digital platforms to shop. By integrating data from semi-structured interviews with industry professionals with results from an online survey of digital platform users, empirical support for a number of the recommended model's linkages was identified. As a consequence, several significant contributions to the literature have been made, as will be discussed more below. As a starting point, this study fills in the gaps left by earlier research on the variables impacting digital platform adaptability and e-commerce adoption, respectively (Gao et al., 2012).

Second, the topic of digital platform adaptation, which can be defined as the development of business strategies for organisations in order to economically monetise digital platforms, has been discussed in detail. This research (Mitchell et al., 2017) was the first to establish consumers' desire to use online digital platforms, which was groundbreaking at the time. Additionally, the study highlights concrete qualities that have an impact on the usage of platforms. The findings add to experimental micropayment studies, such as those conducted by the Nielsen study (Covey, 2010).

Third, the elements that influence consumer acceptance of digital platforms were investigated in this study. Mobility, compatibility, convenience, post-pricing, and the demand for a single payment platform are some of the qualities that influence the utility and value judgments of platforms, which in turn influence their attitude and use. Consumers recognised each of these criteria as a feature of the system in question. There have been a plethora of prior studies that have investigated the factors that influence user acceptance; however, there is no analogous collection of variables for digital platform adaptability; as a result, this study addressed the incremental research gap indicated by Siindik and Graybeal (2011).

Experts decided that four more criteria were necessary to include in the conceptual model, and that these criteria were all key predictors of client approval of digital platform adaptation. The exploratory component of this study looked at the system characteristics of later payment and single payment platforms, as well as individual differences in feelings of trust and perceived relevance of content in the study. Customer preferences for two factors were shown in the research question 2 results, namely delayed payment and a single payment platform, demonstrating the importance of system features in the purchasing decision process. For the first time, an empirical study was carried out on the relationships between newly found components and their assessed utility and perceived value production in this thesis. Fifth, the establishment of a single payment platform would remove the barrier produced by unreliable and disruptive payment methods, which are particularly problematic for minor transactions. This is in direct opposition to Gidner and D'Arrrey (2015), who previously stated that "there is currently no reliable mechanism for processing tiny payments" (p. 4), but in agreement with Smieth (2003), who stressed the importance of having a viable payment-processing system that aggregates small sums. Customers will see digital platform flexibility as favourable and helpful as a result of the implementation of this one-of-a-kind payment infrastructure, which will have a positive impact on their purchasing behaviour.

On the sixth point, Szaebo (1999) claims that the adoption of digital platforms creates fundamental hurdles for consumers, as they must determine whether a product is worth the price before purchasing it. The discovery of a later payment element addresses the mental transaction costs raised by Szaebo (1999). Customers would no longer be forced to do an informal profit-loss analysis on each product they intended to buy if a post-pricing capability were included in digital platforms, hence reducing mental transaction costs.

On the seventh point, this research contributes to bridging the gap that exists between research and practice in the area of new technologies. Sakseena and Holliifield (2002) addressed the lack of a link between executives' viewpoints on new technologies and their use of customer feedback, advising that industry managers do consumer research on the topic of new technology acceptability in their respective industries. Our research team established a comprehensive approach by bringing together the perspectives of industry experts and consumers.

More specifically, some studies emphasised the importance of including user feedback on platform use factors while researching platform adaptation while others emphasised the importance of including user input on platform design features (Graybeal and Hayes, 2011). These researchers gave indicators of the generally favourable conditions for digital platform adaptation, largely via theoretical formulations, which were based on their findings. It was discovered via this study that not only did consumers provide feedback, but that attitude is the most important component in platform utilisation.

Aspect eight, in respect to the TAM theory, this thesis makes major contributions to the methodology used in this study, which combines semi-structured interviews with industry experts and a web survey of users of digital platforms. The approach that was used was intended to clarify the link between the TAM model and the data.

Recommendations for practice

Despite the fact that this study is confirmatory in nature and that its primary goal is not to make instrumental recommendations, the findings have a wide range of managerial implications. For platform owners that provide digital services to customers, understanding how to correctly implement and deploy solutions to non-subscribers is crucial.

6.6. Develop digital platforms adaptation strategies

In summary, the findings highlight the significance of the numerous behavioural traits that were investigated, allowing managers to make strategic recommendations on the use of digital platforms. Overall, the results suggest that business owners should spend in strengthening their digital platform services in light of the favourable client acceptance shown in the research. Without a question, internet services must meet or exceed the expectations of their customers. According to the findings of the main study, solutions should show their value first, followed by their simplicity of use, in order to draw non-subscribers attention to platform usage and encourage them to subscribe. A reference for Platforms, the results may enable the formulation of appropriate strategies aimed at increasing revenue from digital platforms as a result of the findings. With the evolution of a strategy, it is vital to take into account the issues that have been examined in order to effectively adapt and distribute

services. Not only will this enhance client awareness, but it will also result in increased revenue and market share growth as well.

6.7. Improve the antecedents of attitude.

Adaption attitude seems to be significantly predicted by perceived usefulness and perceived value creation, which drives platform utilisation and, as a result, legitimises greater platform attention through influencing platform usage. These characteristics, which have been confirmed by clients, must be taken into account by business owners. Because of its high t-value, the perceived utility should be given special consideration, since digital platforms have been shown to a) benefit users, b) simplify the buying process, and c) drive consumers to pay for digital platforms. The last criterion, which was one of the most often cross-loaded, demonstrates consumers' real willingness to pay for platforms as well as the pace at which they would do so in the future. These characteristics are crucial from a consumer's perspective, and they should serve as a guide for platform design. It is also important to recognise the vital importance of perceived value production and the features associated with it. The platform owner must pay particular attention to the replies received from consumers, ensuring that the digital platform a) allows for flexible product purchases, b) allows for market scanning, and c) is easy to incorporate into existing business processes. In any case, while considering platform adaption, platforms must prioritise perceived usefulness and perceived value creation above other considerations.

6.8. Focus on system characteristics.

Adaption attitudes seem to be significantly predicted by perceived usefulness and perceived value creation, which impact platform usage and, as a result, legitimise increased platform attention. As confirmed by clients, owners must take these characteristics into mind. The high t-value of perceived utility should be given particular attention since digital platforms were found to a) benefit users, as well as ease the purchasing process and as a motivator for users to pay for the usage of digital platforms. Lastly, and one of the most often used cross-loading criteria, it represents both current and future consumer willingness to pay for platform use, in addition to the growth rate in the short term. This list of features is essential from the

perspective of the user, and it should serve as a guideline for platform development. Not to mention the important significance of perceived value production and the traits associated with it. The platform owner must pay particular attention to the replies received from consumers, ensuring that the digital platform a) allows for flexible product purchases, b) allows for market scanning, and c) is easy to incorporate into existing business operations. Anyhow, when considering platform adaptation, platforms must place a high priority on perceived usefulness as well as perceived value creation.

Areas for further research

Researchers may often reproduce earlier work by duplicating the circumstances and then analysing their results in the same manner (literal replication) or by adjusting some characteristics of the conditions (theoretical replication) (Yin, 2013).

More specifically, this study provides as a road map for future research on the features of platform use. While this study aimed to discover many qualities that contribute to platform acceptance, future research may focus on features that are more relevant and acceptable to the platform's intended audience. As new variables, it is recommended that soft factors and price risk be introduced. It is recommended that the impact of antecedent factors and moderating variables on intention to use be investigated further. Ideally, a researcher will be able to create connections between the newly found components and relationships, as well as the qualities revealed in this study, in the future. The findings of future research should include an examination of additional mobile payment methods, with a particular focus on the consequences of mobile websites vs mobile apps.

It is crucial to emphasise that the findings are limited to the United Kingdom because of the country's unique environment. Because this study used a sample of digital platform users from the United Kingdom, it is difficult to extrapolate the results to a larger population. Non-subscribers, on the other hand, are the group most likely to adapt to digital platforms. A representative sample of Swiss or foreign residents should be used in future research to replicate the findings of this study.

In a similar vein, perceived trust and perceived relevance of information in connection to digital platform adaptation should be investigated in more depth. A different kind of study

may evoke a different type of response from clients. Finally, more research should be performed to define the types of platforms, value amounts, payment systems, and currencies that will be used. In addition to providing insight into the conditions in which users can adopt digital platforms, the results might have a significant impact on consumers' perceptions about digital platforms in general.

Limitations of the study:

The study's major flaw was that it only looked at the United Kingdom and not other countries in the world. Because of the study's interview phase's use of simple non-probabilistic purposive sampling, the findings may not correctly reflect the characteristics of the general population in the United Kingdom, as previously stated. Following the definition of the study's scope, the researcher recognised the limitations of the study. It was necessary to keep the study's scope constrained in order to retain a high level of attention while also allowing it to be finished within the restrictions of time and resources available. The research team used a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches to gather data, and they then examined the pros and cons of each strategy. The disadvantages of each strategy are lessened when they are used in conjunction with one another. Alternatively, one may argue that this study could have been carried out utilising a number of alternative data collection methods. Nonetheless, semi-structured interviews were selected as the qualitative strategy, and a web survey was used as the quantitative approach in this research endeavour.

APPENDIX A: CONSTRUCT FOR SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

Construct	Open questions (item)	Expected outcome to extract from the question and sample answer
Beginning	Can you please tell us about your job duties and your role in a business?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ice breaker question. • To get a better understanding of the role of the interviewee in the organisation. • Influence of interview in his organisation. • Learn about consumer behaviour.
Digital Platforms	What is your view regarding digital platforms in the UK?	For example, The use of digital platforms will increase or decrease over time?
Business model	What are the factors you believe impact on users' behaviour of businesses	Example: Users will not be interested in paying a commission and other costs associated with the use of digital platforms?
Users' perception	How do you perceive digital platforms as a business model? How do you describe your perception of digital platforms? In your opinion, why there is a demand for digital platforms in the UK?	Examples: Amazon, Uber, Just Eat. Example: The system reduces business friction and helps to connect. Example: Change in social trends. More knowledge of technology.
Variables Identification	In your opinion what factors have a positive impact on consumers regarding digital platform adaptation?	Examples: Value creation Usefulness Trust Security Ease of use
	In your opinion what factors have a negative impact on users regarding digital platforms adaptation?	Examples: Cost of using the platform Laws and regulations Other issues
	Upon review we found that the following factors impact users' perception of platform adaptation: Sensing, seizing and integrating capabilities of the platform, Mobility, compatibility, convenience, later payments, single	Examples: Value creation is most important Explain mobility for us Innovation is irrelevant All factors are important Examples: Additional factors

	<p>payment platform, innovation, knowledge of platform and trust issues associated with it.</p> <p>What other factors are vital in choosing a platform from users' point of view?</p>	Pandemic impact
Barriers	<p>What are the main challenges in digital platform adaptation?</p> <p>What type of issues do you face after adapting to the online marketplace?</p>	<p>Limited knowledge</p> <p>Management decisions</p> <p>Examples:</p> <p>Difficult interface</p> <p>Target audience</p> <p>No software</p>
Country specific issue	<p>What are UK specific factors exit for online platform adaptation?</p>	<p>To learn about UK specific variables such as social trends.</p>
Other	<p>Do you have any other comments on this topic of platform adaptation</p>	<p>Examples:</p> <p>Any emerging issues</p> <p>Any changes in legislations</p>

APPENDIX B: INFORMED CONSENT FORM

This study examines the factors that impact the adaptation of the digital platform in the UK. The results from this interview will help the digital platforms to understand why users use online platforms across the UK. The interview is supported by the University of West of Scotland and will help me to complete my doctoral degree.

Project title

EXAMINING THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE DIGITAL PLATFORMS
ADAPTATION IN THE UK.

Research team:

Primary investigator:

Mudassar Mehdi

Purpose of the study

You are invited to participate in this research study because you are an expert or an executive employee of a business that uses a digital platform. The purpose of this research study is to investigate the factors that influence consumers' usage of online platforms in the UK industry. The primary investigator will conduct the research in two stages: semi-structured interviews with industry experts (stage 1) and a nationwide web survey among consumers of online platforms (stage 2). Your participation comprises part 1 only. The findings of this study will assist in producing recommendations to create innovative business models in the industry, specifically related to digital platforms.

Time

Your involvement in the study will last for a maximum of 1 hour.

During the study

The principal investigator will conduct a semi-structured interview. Interview questions will ask about your perspective on factors that are responsible for consumers to use digital platforms. The principal investigator has a set of questions designed to help you to relate your perspectives; however, throughout the interview, additional clarifying questions may be asked. During this study: 1. you will be asked to sign this informed consent document for your research participation; 2. you will be offered a copy of this document for your records, and 3. you are free to skip any questions that you would prefer not to answer, and you may end your participation at any time.

Audio recording

One aspect of this study involves making audio recordings of your participation. The audio recording will be used to transcribe the semi-structured interview. Recordings will be made on a digital voice recorder and stored in a locked location until transcription, at which time they will be destroyed. Complete transcriptions will be stored on a password-protected computer. The recorded information may be used as a citation to underpin relevant and important information.

I permit you to make audio recordings of me during this study.

Yes

No

Confidentiality

This study is anonymous. The study does not collect or retain any information about your identity except for using your role and the organisation's industry. The records will be kept strictly confidential. You will be given the opportunity to review and approve any material that is published about you.

Questions

We encourage you to ask questions. If you have any questions about the study, please contact

Mudassar Mehdi

Personal details
withheld.

Your signature indicates that this research study has been explained to you, that your questions have been answered and that you agree to take part in this study.

Subject's name (printed): _____

(Date) _____

Signature of subject) _____

Statement of person who obtained consent

I have discussed the above points with the subject or, where appropriate. It is my opinion that the subject understands the risks, benefits and procedures involved with participation in this research study.

Name of the person who obtained consent (printed): Mudassar Mehdi

(Signature of person who obtained consent)

(Date)

APPENDIX C: SURVEY INSTRUMENT

Table C.1: Measurement scales utilised in web-survey

Stage in research model	Construct and scale items for micropayment characteristics	References from literature
Implication	<p>Intention to <u>use</u> Given the opportunity, I will use digital platforms for buying. I am likely to use digital platforms for online purchases in the next six months. Five years from now I intend to use digital platforms for business transactions.</p>	Davis (1989); Venkatesh and Davis (2000)
Moderating variable	<p>Attitude to <u>use</u> I like the idea of digital platform for online purchases. I would enjoy purchasing online through platforms. Digital platforms for online shopping are interesting. Digital platforms for online business are beneficial.</p>	Fishbein & Ajzen (1975); Davis et al. (1989)
Antecedent variables	<p>Perceived usefulness Digital platforms are usefulness medium for business. Online platforms have help me to access the products I need quicker. Using digital platforms would enable me to shop more comfortably. When using digital platform for online purchases, my choices as consumer are improved (e.g. flexibility, access).</p>	Taylor and Todd (1995); Bhattacharjee (2001)
	<p>Perceived Value creation Digital platforms create value for me. Online platforms have connected me to right product hence while generating value for me. Using digital platforms would enable to save time and effort to reach the desired products and audience.</p>	Teece (2018)

External variables	<p>Laws and regulation Laws and regulation regarding online purchases protect me from fraud. Laws and regulation regarding shipment of products protect me as a user. I trust the platform that they will follow the rules and regulation regarding consumers protection.</p>	(Shu-Chiang, et al., 2014), (Krishnasamy & Nayan, 2015).
	<p>Mobility I believe digital platforms for online purchases are independent of time. I believe digital platforms for online purchases are independent of place. I can use platforms for online purchases anytime while travelling.</p>	Kim et al. (2010); Schierz et al. (2010)
	<p>Compatibility I believe platforms are compatible with existing (payment) technology. I trust platforms are compatible with my lifestyle.</p>	Karahanna et al. (1999); Mallat et al. (2006); Chen (2008)
	<p>Convenience Platforms are convenient because I can access online products anytime. Digital platforms are convenient because I can access online market anywhere. Digital platforms are convenient because they are not complex.</p>	Davis (1989); Kim et al. (2010)
	<p>Innovativeness I know about new technologies before other people do. I am usually among the first to try new technologies. I often recommend new technologies to others.</p>	Goldsmith and Hofacker (1991); Gao et al. (2012)
	<p>Knowledge I enjoy purchasing products of small amounts online. I use credit cards or internet banking for online purchases. I would be confident to use digital platforms for online purchases.</p>	Kim et al. (2010)
	<p>Perceived Trust I am comfortable with the risk that I will receive the products I order from online platform. I am comfortable with the risk that my financial data will not be compromised by platform.</p>	(Hoffman , et al., 1999), (Pavlou & Gefen, 2004) and (Swaminathan, et al., 1999). (Triandini, et al., 2013), (Oduor, et al., 2016)

	I am comfortable with the risk that the product will perform as advertise by platform	
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APPENDIX D: Web survey

EXAMINING THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE DIGITAL PLATFORMS ADAPTATION IN THE UK

This study is regarding the user's perception of digital platforms and how these platforms create and enhance value for businesses.

1. Solicitation Letter

Dear Respondent, this questionnaire is part of an empirical innovation research study at the University of West of Scotland. The main objective of this research is to better understand the process of value creation and value enhancement in digital platforms and attempt to explain why some platforms are perceived better than others by users. By addressing you, I intend to reach out to a broad array of service professionals and gain insight into service innovation in practice.

Why should you complete this questionnaire?

This questionnaire is part of an academic research study on platform adaptation. By completing the questionnaire, you help to create a better understanding of the development in digitalization and generate new knowledge. This questionnaire will not be used for commercial purposes. It is solely of academic interest.

What will be done with the information provided?

All complete answers will be evaluated and used as empirical research part in a doctoral thesis on new service development. As such, the information will be published, but without allowing inferences or identification of individual answers. Therefore, full confidentiality in handling information obtained through this questionnaire is assured. If you have any questions or concerns about completing the questionnaire or about participating in this study, please do not hesitate to contact me by email [REDACTED]. If you have any questions about the background of this research, you can also contact the doctoral office at the University of West of Scotland Business School for inquiries. Personal details withheld.

This study was collated according to the university's research standards. Thank you for your support.

Sincerely,

Researcher

Section A: Respondent's profile

1. What is your age?

Ⓐ 18-25 (1)

Ⓑ 25-29 (2)

Ⓒ 30-35 (3)

D 35 and above (4)

2. What is your gender

A Males (1)

B Female (2)

C I don't want to mention (3)

3. Your monthly gross income

A Upto 4000 pounds (1)

B 4000 to 6000 pounds (2)

C 6000 to 8000 pounds (3)

D 8000 and above pounds (4)

4. Have you ever used digital platforms?

A Yes (1)

B No (2)

do you agree with the following statement?

Please rate your experience.

Section B: Perceived Usefulness (PUN)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
PUN 1	5	Digital platforms are useful for purchasing online?	1	2	3	4	5
PUN 2	6	Digital platforms are easy to choose?	1	2	3	4	5
PUN 3	7	Using digital platforms enable me to save time	1	2	3	4	5
Section C: Perceived Value Creation (PVC)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
PVC 1	8	Digital platforms create value for me.	1	2	3	4	5
PVC 2	9	Online platforms have connected me to the right products hence generating value for me.	1	2	3	4	5
PVC 3	10	Using digital platforms would enable to save time and effort	1	2	3	4	5
Section D: Attitude towards Use (ATT)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
ATT 1	11	I like the idea of purchasing online products.	1	2	3	4	5
ATT 2	12	I would enjoy purchasing online products through digital platforms.	1	2	3	4	5
ATT 3	13	Digital platforms for online shopping are interesting.	1	2	3	4	5
Section E: Intention to Use (INT)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
INT 1	14	Given the opportunity, I would use digital platforms for online purchases	1	2	3	4	5

INT 1	15	With platforms, I would access online markets more often.	1	2	3	4	5
	16	I am likely to use digital platforms for buying in the next six months					
Section F: Mobility (MOB)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
MOB 1	17	I believe digital platforms for online purchases are independent of time.	1	2	3	4	5
MOB 2	18	I believe digital platforms for online purchases are independent of place.	1	2	3	4	5
MOB 3	19	I can use platforms for online purchases anytime while travelling.	1	2	3	4	5
Section G: Compatibility (COM)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
COM 1	20	I believe platforms are compatible with existing (payment) technology.	1	2	3	4	5
COM 2	21	I believe Digital platforms are compatible with my consumption and online shopping behaviour.	1	2	3	4	5
COM 3	22	I trust platforms are compatible with my lifestyle.	1	2	3	4	5
Section H: Convenience (CON)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
CON 1	23	Platforms are convenient because I can access online products anytime.	1	2	3	4	5

CON 2	24	Digital platforms are convenient because I can access the online market anywhere.	1	2	3	4	5
CON 3	25	Digital platforms are convenient because they are not complex.	1	2	3	4	5
Section I: Later Payment (LPM)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
LPM 1	26	It bothers me when my shopping flow is interrupted by a payment process	1	2	3	4	5
LPM 2	27	I want to use the product first and pay later.	1	2	3	4	5
LPM 3	28	I would like to receive an overview of my shopping list at the end of the month.	1	2	3	4	5
Section J: Single Payment Platform (SPP)							
SPP 1	29	I want to pay for online shopping with one click	1	2	3	4	5
SPP 2	30	I would like to deposit credit card data only once and avoid later data entry	1	2	3	4	5
SPP 3	31	I would like to have a single payment platform for all digital newspaper content	1	2	3	4	5
Section L: Innovativeness (INN)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
INN 1	32	Innovativeness I know about new technologies before other people do.	1	2	3	4	5

INN 2	33	I am usually among the first to try new technologies.	1	2	3	4	5
INN 3	34	I often recommend new technologies to others.	1	2	3	4	5
Section M: Knowledge (KNO)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
KNO 1	35	Knowledge I enjoy purchasing products of small amounts online.	1	2	3	4	5
KNO 2	36	I use credit cards or internet banking for online purchases.	1	2	3	4	5
KNO 3	37	I would be confident to use digital platforms for online purchases.	1	2	3	4	5
Section N: Perceived Trust (PTR)			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Partly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
PTR 1	38	Platform payments are among the most trusted payment methods.	1	2	3	4	5
PTR 2	39	I am comfortable with the risk that my financial data will not be compromised by the platform.	1	2	3	4	5
PTR 3	40	I am comfortable with the risk that the product will perform as advertised by the platform	1	2	3	4	5
Section N: Perceived Content							

Section N: Perceived Content Relevance (PCR)							
PCR 1	41	I would like to pay for articles that are relevant to me	1	2	3	4	5
PCR 2	42	Digital platforms will help me to buy the products that are important to me	1	2	3	4	5
PCR 3	43	I am ready to pay for products or services that are especially valuable to me	1	2	3	4	5

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